

Analysis of the Application of Immersive Technologies and Gamification to Computer Science Education

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Abstract

Virtual reality and augmented reality technology have the potential to revolutionise education by providing immersive, interactive learning experiences that engage students in a way that traditional methods cannot. Several studies show the benefits of bringing immersive technology into the classroom and there is even more research that shows gamification of a subject has additional benefits to the traditional and standard teaching method; improved student engagement, quicker learning attainment, higher achievement in learning outcomes and gains in knowledge retention are some positive results found throughout these research papers. However, implementing VR in education requires careful planning and consideration of several factors.

While it is possible to learn programming through the use of VR games, there are few VR games and educational programs that are specifically designed to teach programming concepts and skills. Using immersive technology and gamification in education is gaining popularity due to the hardware becoming easier to use and more affordable and have also observed improvements in software applications with serious game elements or an educational aspect. Computer science is a rapidly growing field that is expected to continue expanding in the coming years. According to data from the U.S. Bureau of Labour Statistics, employment in computer and information technology occupations is projected to grow 11% from 2019 to 2029, which is much faster than the average for all occupations. Yet, there has been limited investigation into the implementation of this new learning paradigm within the computer science field.

Through a holistic approach consisting of the development and analysis of virtual reality applications, the construction of a database of educational VR applications, comprehensive literature reviews, and active involvement in academic communities, this Ph.D. research has sought to extensively investigate the potential of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education. The research has found that the use of interactive, immersive environments engages learners and makes the learning process more enjoyable and interactive which improves knowledge to increase the impact on education retention and improves learning outcomes. For example, some VR games and educational programs can use puzzles, challenges, and other game-like elements to teach programming concepts, such as looping, branching, and data structures. Other programs can use more traditional teaching methods, such as video lectures and interactive exercises. A VR game to teach the fundamental of programming was built for this study and found that while learning programming skills through VR games may not be the same as learning through more traditional methods, such as textbooks or online courses, VR games can be a fun and engaging way to learn programming concepts and skills. However, it is important to keep in mind that VR games are just one tool among many that can be used to learn to program, and they may not be suitable for all learners or in all learning frameworks. To increase the impact on education in the field, further research and development, practical suggestions and guidelines have been summarised and shared.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	12
1.1	Research Aims	14
1.2	Methodological Considerations	15
1.3	Expected Contributions to Knowledge	16
1.4	Publications.....	17
1.5	Additional activities.....	17
2	Background and context of the research	19
2.1	Through the Looking Glass.....	19
2.1.1	Virtual Reality.....	24
2.1.2	Augmented Reality	27
2.1.3	Mixed Reality.....	28
2.2	Immersive Education: The Next Frontier of Learning Technologies	29
2.2.1	The Virtual Classroom.....	34
2.2.2	Distance Education	35
2.2.3	Cross-Platform Education with AR and VR	36
2.2.4	Immersive Technologies in Science Labs.....	38
2.2.5	Virtual Meeting Spaces.....	39
2.2.6	Emerging Technologies Converging in the Metaverse.....	41
2.3	Gamification and Game-based learning.....	43
3	Literature Review.....	46
3.1	Overview.....	46
3.2	Use Cases for Immersive Technologies in Classroom Delivery.....	48
3.2.1	Benefits of Immersive Technologies	51
3.2.2	Challenges of Using Immersive Technology.....	52
3.3	Gamification In Education.....	54
3.4	Computer Science education.....	55
3.4.1	Challenges Faced in Computer Science Education.....	55
3.4.2	Computer Science Innovative Teaching Methods	56
3.5	Overall Summary of Key Findings	58
4	Presentation of the Research Findings.....	61
4.1	Research Paradigms & Methodology	63
4.1.1	Study 1: Virtual Reality vs Pancake Environments	63
4.1.2	Study 2: Systematic Review of Virtual Reality Applications for Education	65
4.1.3	Study 3: MoonBase VR: Learning to Program in a Virtual Reality Game.....	67
4.1.4	Summary	69

5	STUDY 1: Virtual Reality vs Pancake Environments	71
5.1.1	The 3D Environment.....	72
5.1.2	Methodology	74
5.1.3	Findings.....	75
5.1.4	Data Analysis	79
5.1.5	Conclusion	80
6	STUDY 2: A Systematic Review of Virtual Reality Applications for Education	81
6.1.1	Results.....	82
6.1.2	Conclusion	87
7	STUDY 3: MoonBase VR: Learning to Program in a Virtual Reality Game.....	89
7.1.1	Advantages and Limitations of Using VR Technology in Education.....	90
7.1.2	Overview of MoonBase VR.....	90
7.1.3	Programming.....	91
7.1.4	The Game.....	92
7.1.5	Brief overview for the development process	94
7.1.6	The Study	96
7.1.7	Findings.....	97
7.1.8	Conclusion	101
8	Discussion.....	102
8.1	Framework for the use of Immersive Gamification.....	103
8.2	Considerations for the use of Immersive Technology	105
8.2.1	Sensory simulation.....	113
8.2.2	Interaction	114
8.2.3	Storytelling and narratives	115
8.2.4	Comparing VR to other media	117
8.2.5	Challenges and research needs.....	118
8.3	Considerations for the Implementation of Immersive Experiences	119
8.4	Immersive Computer Science Education.....	131
8.4.1	AR and VR Experiences in Computer Science Education.....	131
8.4.2	Designing AR and VR Experiences for Computer Science Education.....	134
8.4.3	Accessibility.....	138
8.4.4	Guidelines for Educators.....	140
9	Conclusions.....	142
9.1	Key Contributions and Findings	142
9.1.1	Theoretical Contributions	143
9.2	Critical Evaluation of Research Limitations	144

9.2.1	Study 1:	144
9.2.2	Study 2:	145
9.2.3	Study 3:	145
9.2.4	Limitations:	146
9.2.5	Potential biases and gaps:	146
9.3	Implications for Practice	147
9.4	Future Works	149
10	References.....	151
11	Appendix.....	176

List of Figures

FIGURE 5-1 DESKTOP UI (LEFT) VIRTUAL REALITY UI (RIGHT).....	73
FIGURE 5-2 MODELS PRESENTED IN THE VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT	73
FIGURE 5-3 A PARTICIPANT USING ROOM-SCALE (LEFT) AND A PARTICIPANT USING TELEPORTATION (RIGHT)	75
FIGURE 5-4 HAVE YOU USED VIRTUAL REALITY PRIOR TO THIS STUDY?	76
FIGURE 5-5 WHAT BEST DESCRIBES YOUR VR EXPERIENCE LEVEL?	76
FIGURE 5-6 TIME SPENT LOOKING AT THE MODEL	77
FIGURE 5-7 DID THE PARTICIPANT PICK UP THE MODEL?	78
FIGURE 5-8 DID THE PARTICIPANT GET A CLOSER LOOK AT THE MODEL?	78
FIGURE 6-1 SINGLE-PLAYER AND MULTIPLAYER EXPERIENCES	83
FIGURE 6-2 AGE RANGE RATING OF THE APPLICATION.....	83
FIGURE 6-3 GAMEPLAY TYPE	83
FIGURE 6-4 LEARNING CONTENT.....	84
FIGURE 6-5 LEARNING THEORY	84
FIGURE 6-6 DESIGN ELEMENTS	85
FIGURE 6-7 OVERLAPPED DESIGN ELEMENTS VENN DIAGRAM	85
FIGURE 6-8 SUBJECT AREA.....	86
FIGURE 6-9 SCIENCE CATEGORY BREAKDOWN	86
FIGURE 6-10 AGE RANGE RATING OF THE APPLICATION.....	87
FIGURE 7-1 MOONBASE VR TITLE GRAPHIC	91
FIGURE 7-2 (LEFT TO RIGHT) MENU UI, CONSOLE WITH CONTROLLERS FUNCTIONS, THE PLAYER HANDLING A CODE BLOCK, GHOST WALKING MOVEMENT.....	92
FIGURE 7-3 MOONBASE VR GAME IMAGES SHOWING (LEFT TO RIGHT) THE MOON BASE ENVIRONMENT, THE CODING PROBLEM AND CODE BLOCKS, THE HOLOGRAM PROJECT OF THE LEVEL TO SOLVE AND A PLAYER BUILDING THE PROGRAM.	93
FIGURE 7-4 CODE STATION, BLOCKS AND HOLOGRAM	94
FIGURE 7-5 WHAT GENDER DO YOU IDENTIFY AS?.....	97
FIGURE 7-6 WHAT IS YOUR AGE?.....	98
FIGURE 7-7 HAVE YOU USED ANY FORM OF VISUAL SCRIPTING?.....	98
FIGURE 7-8 IF YOU HAVE USED VR FOR EDUCATION, IN WHAT SUBJECT AREA?	99
FIGURE 7-9 MOVEMENT IS SIMPLE AND NATURAL.	99
FIGURE 7-10 HIGHLIGHTING THE AREAS WHERE THE BLOCKS CAN BE PLACED IS USEFUL.	99
FIGURE 7-11 THE DIFFICULTY OF THE GAME INCREASES PROGRESSIVELY AT EACH LEVEL..	100
FIGURE 7-12 I THINK PROGRAMMING LIKE THIS CAN BE FUN	100
FIGURE 7-13 HOW ENGAGING WAS THE GAME?	100
FIGURE 7-14 DID VISUALISING CODE IN THIS WAY MAKE IT EASIER TO UNDERSTAND?.....	101

List of Tables

TABLE 1 LITERATURE SEARCH TERMS AND KEYWORDS.....	47
TABLE 2 SUMMARY OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW FOR IMMERSIVE TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION	176
TABLE 3 SUMMARY THE LITERATURE REVIEW FOR BENEFITS IMMERSIVE TECHNOLOGIES .	179
TABLE 4 SUMMARY OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW FOR CHALLENGES OF USING IMMERSIVE TECHNOLOGY	182
TABLE 5 SUMMARY OF THE DEFINITIONS IN THE LITERATURE REVIEW FOR GAMIFICATION IN EDUCATION	183
TABLE 6 SUMMARY OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW FOR CHALLENGES FACED IN COMPUTER SCIENCE EDUCATION.....	185
TABLE 7 SUMMARY OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW FOR INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS IN CS	187

List of Images

IMAGE 2-1 THE SENSORAMA (SENSORAMA, THANKSGIVING - HOW TO KILL AN HOUR, 1962) ..	20
IMAGE 2-2 TRACKING METHODS (DELIGHT XR, NO DATE)	22
IMAGE 2-3 THE EXIT-SUIT, PUSHING THE BOUNDARIES OF VR IMMERSION. (EXIT SUIT — ZACHARY BERRY, NO DATE)	23
IMAGE 2-4 SIMPLIFIED REPRESENTATION OF A "VIRTUALITY CONTINUUM"	24
IMAGE 2-5 SELECTION OF DIFFERENT VR HEADSETS. (VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCE DESIGN PLAN BY KUMAR AHIR AR/VR JOURNEY: AUGMENTED & VIRTUAL REALITY MAGAZINE)	25
IMAGE 2-6 COMMON TYPES OF AR DEVICES. (COLES, 2020).....	28
IMAGE 8-1 EXPLODED VIEW OF A TYPICAL VR HEADSET. (UNCROSS THOSE EYES: RESEARCHERS SOLVE VR'S DEPTH-OF-FOCUS HEADACHES ARS TECHNICA, NO DATE)	126
IMAGE 8-2 NVIDIA'S NEW VERSION OF VR LIGHT FIELD DISPLAY APPEARED AT THE VRLA VENUE, THE DISPLAY PRINCIPLES OF THE OLD AND NEW GENERATIONS ARE QUITE DIFFERENT T KEBANG, (2016)	127
IMAGE 8-3 HORIZON WORLDS SCRIPTING TOOLS. (HEATH, 2023)	129
IMAGE 8-4 REC ROOM MAKERPEN. (HOW TO CREATIVE TUTORIALS — REC ROOM, NO DATE)	130
IMAGE 8-5 ENGAGE VR VIRTUAL CLASSROOM. (ENGAGE VR REVIEW 2019 DECEMBER – ANCIENTC BACKSTAGE, 2019)	135

Glossary

HMD

Head mounted displays are what people use to experience virtual reality. Commonly this is a headset, or it might be goggles or a helmet. A HMD is positioned in close in proximity to your eyes, allowing users to easily view and focus on a VR experience.

Tracking

- **Head Tracking**
 - Head tracking means following users' head movements. This means that when you look around a VR experience, the images or video moves with you.
- **Position Tracking**
 - This can be used to alter your position in virtual space using sensors to track your movements. Some virtual reality headsets require you to stay in one place or move using a controller, but headsets with position tracking allow you to get up and walk around in virtual space.
- **Outside-in tracking**
 - This term refers to the use of externally placed positional sensors to track users moving in real-time
- **Inside-out Tracking**
 - This tracking method uses cameras fixed to the device being tracked in order to determine how its position changes relative to its environment.

360 Video

360 videos are the building blocks of any virtual reality experience and can be viewed even without a VR headset. Some social sites like Facebook and YouTube support 360 videos, which allows people to “look around” the video using a mouse, or trackpad, or by physically moving their phone.

Stereoscopic

This term refers to what is done to either an image or a video in order to make it appear three-dimensional. Two photos or videos are captured at slightly different angles, and when viewed together create the appearance of depth. Not all VR experiences are stereoscopic. allowing open-world exploration.

FOV

FOV stands for “field of view,” which states how much the human eye sees in its normal field of vision. Through the clever use of lenses and screens, VR does its best to replicate the human eye’s FOV. Although different VR headsets have various fields of view and usually the higher the field of view the better.

DOF

Three Degrees of Freedom (3DOF) refers to 3 axis of movement inside an area. The three degrees of freedom are yaw, pitch, and roll.

Six Degrees of Freedom (6DOF) refers to 6 axis of movement inside an area. The six degrees of freedom are pitch, yaw, roll (that make up 3DOF) forward/back, up/down, and left/right.

1 Introduction

Immersive technologies, comprising Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR), have experienced significant advancements in recent years, stimulating interest in their potential applications within educational contexts. Moreover, the integration of gamification strategies and the rapidly evolving field of computer science education has fostered growing enthusiasm among academics, educators, and students alike (Lanier, 2017; Nguyen, Hite and Dang, 2019; Filter *et al.*, 2020).

This doctoral thesis delves into the emerging yet budding field of immersive technologies and gamification, scrutinising their potential impact on computer science education. This research project seeks to demonstrate the complexity and intricacies of innovative approaches to teaching and learning through a comprehensive investigation. Drawing from an array of disciplines, such as education, psychology, and computer science, this research identifies the diverse challenges and opportunities that underpin the integration of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education.

Immersive technologies and gamification lie at the intersection of various areas of research. This presents a unique opportunity for groundbreaking research. By exploring this juncture, my study aims to not only bridge these disparate areas but also to contribute significantly to the understanding of how these technologies can be effectively utilised in computer science education. In order to unravel their complexities, a variety of approaches are necessary. Therefore, this research is founded on a strong theoretical framework, encompassing fundamental concepts from education, psychology, and computer science, to provide an all-encompassing understanding of the topic. From an educational perspective, this research explores the numerous ways by which immersive technologies and gamification can enhance student engagement, accelerate learning attainment, and promote higher achievement in learning outcomes. Furthermore, the study examines how these approaches can enhance knowledge retention, a significant challenge in traditional educational paradigms. Drawing on theories from the psychology field, the research explores cognitive, affective, and motivational theories, highlighting the relationship between these theories and the implementation of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education. Additional studies have demonstrated that gamification of a subject has advantages over and above traditional and standard teaching approaches (Filipcik and Bielikova, 2014; Ibanez, Di-Serio and Delgado-Kloos, 2014; Hanus and Fox, 2015; Ahmed and Sutton, 2017). Improved student engagement, quicker learning attainment, higher achievement in learning outcomes and gains in knowledge retention are some of the positive results found throughout research papers on the subject (Kapp, 2012; Wouters *et al.*, 2013; Landers and Landers, 2014a; Scepanovic and Zaric, 2017).

Furthermore, within the field of computer science, this study scrutinises the latest and groundbreaking advancements in immersive technologies, analysing their potential applications in computer science education. The challenges faced by novice programmers, such as the linguistic barriers to acquiring basic programming concepts, are often exacerbated by traditional teaching methods. My research seeks to address these challenges by exploring the efficacy of immersive technologies and gamification, offering potentially transformative solutions for computer science education., such as the linguistic barriers to acquiring basic programming concepts, and illustrate how immersive technologies and gamification can provide innovative solutions to these difficulties.

The exponential growth of the computer science field, fuelled by the rapid development of technological advancements, presents both opportunities and challenges for educators. With employment in computer and information technology occupations is projected to boom (Zilberman and Ice, 2021) there is an urgent need to devise novel, engaging, and effective approaches to computer science education that will

meet the demands of this rapidly expanding field. Given the projected boom in computer and information technology occupations, the urgency for advancing educational methods in this field cannot be overstated. This research is timely and aligns with the evolving needs of the computer science industry, ensuring that educational practices keep pace with technological advancements. However, traditional teaching methods have often proven insufficient in preparing students for the varied and complex challenges posed by the computer science discipline (Parmar *et al.*, 2016; Gentry *et al.*, 2019). The incorporation of immersive technologies and gamification in the learning process presents a unique and innovative opportunity to overcome these hurdles. Nevertheless, the implementation of these approaches within the computer science field remains largely uncharted territory, warranting further investigation and empirical research. New programming students often struggle to write code (Blikstein, 2011), partly because it requires them to change their use of the written word from linear communication to the creation of sequences of operations that are often nested within more complex functional structures (Vihavainen, Helminen and Ihantola, 2014; Rivers, Harpstead and Koedinger, 2016). This written barrier can hinder the conceptual acquisition of basic programming concepts (e.g. data structures, functions, variables) and thus visual aids are often employed to help when teaching programming (Bau *et al.*, 2017). Existing work has looked at the use of gamification to teach coding (Olsson, Mozelius and Collin, 2015; Arawjo *et al.*, 2017), helping learners to develop metacognitive strategies for learning that is built around low-stakes competition as a means of attaining basic conceptual knowledge and skills. Crosswords, missing word games and jigsaw puzzles can assist in closing the linguistic gap, but the conceptual linkages between coding processes are less suited to these methods (García-Peñalvo, Cruz-Benito and ..., 2016; Kim and Ko, 2017). Providing the learner with visual representations of programming characteristics has been shown to engage a learner and overcome some of the difficulties that novice students face (Jehng and Chan, 1998).

1.1 Research Aims

This doctoral research project endeavours to conduct a comprehensive investigation into the potential of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education. The overarching aim of the study is to explore the impact of these approaches on student engagement, learning attainment, and knowledge retention, with a specific focus on the teaching and learning of programming concepts and skills. Despite the growing interest in immersive technologies, there is a notable paucity of comprehensive research on the pedagogical use of virtual reality (VR) within higher education in the UK, particularly in the context of VR gamification. This gap is significant given the potential of these technologies to revolutionise educational methodologies.

To achieve this aim, the research is guided by the following objectives:

- To conduct a thorough analysis of the current state of immersive technologies, such as VR, AR, and MR, as well as their potential applications in computer science education.
- To examine the principles of gamification and game-based learning in the context of computer science education, elucidating their benefits, limitations, and potential synergies with immersive technologies.
- To explore the unique challenges faced by novice computer science students, particularly in relation to programming, and assess the effectiveness of immersive technologies and gamification in addressing these issues.
- To develop and evaluate innovative pedagogical approaches that integrate immersive technologies and gamification strategies in computer science education, with a specific focus on programming concepts and skills.
- To compare the efficacy of these novel approaches with traditional teaching methods in computer science education, providing empirical evidence to inform best practices and future developments in the field.

1.2 Methodological Considerations

Given the complexity and multifaceted nature of this research, a comprehensive and rigorous methodological approach is essential. The research employs a mixed-methods design, combining both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a more nuanced understanding of the potential impact of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education.

Quantitative data, including experimental and quasi-experimental designs, will be utilised to assess the effectiveness of immersive technologies and gamification in enhancing student engagement, learning attainment, and knowledge retention. Additionally, surveys and questionnaires will be employed to gauge students' perceptions of these approaches and their impact on their learning experiences.

Qualitative data, comprising in-depth case studies, will be used to explore the experiences of students and educators who have been exposed to immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education. This data will provide valuable insights into the challenges, benefits, and practical implications of these approaches in real-world educational settings.

1.3 Expected Contributions to Knowledge

The potential impact of this research is multifaceted. By providing empirical evidence on the efficacy of immersive technologies and gamification in enhancing student engagement, learning attainment, and knowledge retention, this study aims to inform and inspire innovative teaching methodologies in computer science education, thus contributing to a more effective and engaging learning environment.

This research not only contributes to the existing literature by filling the identified gaps but also sets the foundation for future studies. It aims to establish a comprehensive framework for the integration of immersive technologies in computer science education, thereby paving the way for further academic inquiry and practical application. The study aims to provide valuable insights into the following areas:

- The current state of immersive technologies, such as VR, AR, and MR, and their potential applications in education.
- The principles, benefits, and limitations of gamification and game-based learning in the context of computer science education, as well as how they might be combined with immersive technologies.
- The unique challenges faced by novice computer science students, particularly in relation to programming, and the potential of immersive technologies and gamification to address these issues.
- The development and evaluation of innovative pedagogical approaches that integrate immersive technologies and gamification strategies in computer science education, with a specific focus on programming concepts and skills.
- The comparison of the efficacy of these novel approaches with traditional teaching methods in education, providing empirical evidence to inform best practices and future developments in the field.

By conducting a comprehensive investigation into the potential of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education, this research aims to pave the way for more effective, engaging, and innovative approaches to teaching and learning in this rapidly evolving discipline. Ultimately, it is hoped that the findings of this study will contribute to the ongoing quest for excellence in computer science education, ensuring that future generations of students are equipped with the skills, knowledge, and competencies required to thrive in the digital age.

1.4 Publications

Within the scope of this comprehensive doctoral research, several significant publications and activities have emerged, disseminating the findings and contributing to the broader academic discourse. This section focuses on the details of these research activities, summarising their significance, and highlighting the relevance and impact of the author's contributions. Furthermore, the review of the events in which the author has actively participated demonstrates the wide-ranging nature of the research, including not only written publications but also the vital role of conferences, workshops, and seminars in furthering the academic community's understanding and insights.

The first publication, Holder, R., Carey, M. & Keir, P., 7 Sep 2020, "Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, and Computer Graphics: 7th International Conference, AVR 2020, Lecce, Italy, September 7–10, 2020, Proceedings, Part I", the report demonstrates the extensive research and analysis undertaken in the area of immersive technologies. Published in the well-respected Lecture Notes in Computer Science series (vol. 12242) by Springer International Publishing AG, this work presents a comprehensive analysis of virtual reality and computer graphics, offering a broad range of perspectives and insights that contribute to an understanding of the intricate relationship of these cutting-edge technologies.

The second publication, "A Systematic Review of Virtual Reality Applications for Education" (Holder R, Carey M., Walder P., and Keir P., 2023), submitted to IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies in April 2023, offers a comprehensive analysis of the growing field of virtual reality applications in education. This work examines in detail the strengths and limitations of these applications, therefore providing as a valuable resource for educators and researchers seeking to harness the power of virtual reality in pedagogical contexts. At the time of writing this paper is under review for publication.

The third publication, "Moon Base VR: Learning to program in a virtual reality game" (Holder R, Carey M., Walder P., and Keir P., 2023), was presented at the 2023 International Conference on Educational Informatics (ICIEI 2023), delves into the interesting world of virtual reality-based game learning. This work, accepted for publication in the ICIEI '23: Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Information and Education Innovations by the Association for Computing Machinery, investigates the concept of teaching programming through an immersive virtual reality game environment, providing an insight into the potential collaboration between technology and education. This presentation was honoured with the award for the best presentation at the conference.

1.5 Additional activities

In addition to publications, the author has actively participated in multiple events that have facilitated the exchange of ideas and encouraged collaborations within the academic community. The first event,

the SICSA (Scottish Informatics & Computer Science Alliance): HCI Research Theme: Socially Distant Research Methods Workshop, held on January 14, 2021, saw the author participate as an invited speaker. This workshop, aimed to foster a deeper understanding of human-computer interaction during the pandemic, thereby contributing to the development and advancement of cutting-edge technologies and methodologies in the field.

The second event, the KTP Associates Conference, held from June 8-9, 2022, brought together a diverse group of researchers, including the author, who contributed as an organiser alongside Marco Gilardi, Luke Beveridge, and Wei Ning. This conference provided a dynamic platform for the presentation and discussion of various research topics, including the innovative integration of technology in education.

In the scope of academic activities, the Three Minute Thesis (3MT) stands as a formidable challenge. This unique competition calls upon doctoral candidates to condense their intricate research topic into a mere three-minute spoken presentation, emphasising not just clarity but also the significance of their work. In the 2022 competition, the candidate emerged as the winner of the UWS 3MT competition, proceeding to the semi-finals of the UK national competition with an engaging presentation entitled 'Welcome to the Oasis'. This accomplishment marks the highest placement a UWS PhD candidate has achieved in the national competition up until this point.

The publications and activities undertaken during the course of this doctoral research illustrate the varied aspects of the research, emphasising the interdisciplinary nature of the study, publication, and engagement within the academic community. Through these diverse activities, the author has not only contributed to the existing body of knowledge but has also forged connections and sparked dialogues that will, in turn, propel the field of immersive technologies and education forward. The combination of publications and activities highlights the dynamic partnership between theory and practice, as well as the importance of collaboration and intellectual exchange in the pursuit of innovative solutions to the challenges faced in this field.

As the scientific landscape continues to evolve and new technologies emerge, it is imperative for researchers and practitioners to stay abreast of the latest developments and engage in meaningful dialogues with their peers. The author's participation in the previously mentioned conferences, workshops, and seminars underscores the significance of such events in fostering a spirit of collaboration, enhancing the quality of research, and elevating the overall impact of the work conducted. By delving into diverse areas such as augmented reality, virtual reality, computer graphics, and game-based learning, the author has contributed valuable insights to a rapidly growing and evolving field, laying the groundwork for future research and advancements in the area of immersive technologies and education.

In summary, the publications and activities showcased in this section reflect the results of the author's extensive research and engagement with the academic community. Through these activities, the author

has made significant contributions to the understanding and application of immersive technologies in educational settings, providing valuable insights and resources for researchers, educators, and practitioners alike.

2 Background and context of the research

This chapter delves into the background and context of the research on immersive technologies, exploring their various forms and potential applications in the education landscape. The chapter begins with an examination of the fundamentals of immersive technologies, including virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality, along with a discussion on the integration of emerging technologies in the metaverse.

The chapter then investigates the transformative potential of immersive technologies in education, focusing on aspects such as the virtual classroom, distance learning and virtual meeting spaces. Additionally, the chapter dips into how the future of virtual worlds might have an impact on immersive education in the Metaverse.

The final section looks at another key aspect of this research, with an overview of gamification and game-based learning. It explores the concept of gamification, a technique that incorporates game-like elements into educational contexts to boost engagement and motivation. This approach, although novel in terminology, is rooted in historical practices of integrating play into learning. The chapter emphasises that while gamification enhances the allure of educational activities, it does not fundamentally alter the core pedagogical approach. It draws a distinction between gamification and more immersive game-based learning, where educational objectives are achieved through interactive and engaging gameplay.

2.1 Through the Looking Glass

Immersive technology blurs the boundary between the physical and virtual worlds and enables users to experience a sense of immersion (Lee, Chung and Lee, 2013; Lee, Shan and Chen, 2013). The phrase ‘Immersive technology’, which encompasses augmented reality and virtual reality, is becoming part of modern life. Research has been undertaken in diverse fields that cover all aspects of our lives, such as education (Frank and Kapila, 2017; Pribeanu, Balog and Iordache, 2017), marketing (Huang and Liao, 2017), entertainment (Arino *et al.*, 2014), and healthcare (Zhao, Ong and Nee, 2016).

Studies have demonstrated that the use of immersive technology enhances learning experiences (Huang, Chen and Chou, 2016), encourages gains in participation in learning activities (Fonseca *et al.*, 2014), and has improved creativity and educational engagement (Huang, Rauch and Liaw, 2010). Although there has been an increased uptake in research on the effect of immersive technology, an incoherent

description of what is classed as immersive technologies has emerged, the way studies have been implemented, conducted, methods implemented and the conditions the studies were conducted have muddied the waters of the results produced making any definitive effects of immersive technology implementation unclear.

Immersive experiences are formed by simulating a three-dimensional environment with the aid of computer software and hardware technologies. In the Oxford English Dictionary (2015), Virtual Reality is defined as “a realistic and immersive computer simulation of a three-dimensional environment, created using interactive software and hardware, and experienced or controlled by movement of the body.” Crucially, this highlights the importance of these simulated environments are not just visually engaging, but also interactive, as they allow users to experience and control them through their body movements.

VR/AR has evolved since its (modern) origins in the 1960s with the development of heads up displays for US Navy pilots. The roots of VR can actually be dated back to the 19th century with 360-degree panoramic murals, followed by the invention (nearly one hundred years later) of the Sensorama (Image 2-1), a mechanical device that combined three dimensional colour film with sounds, smells and even the simulation of weather to the audience (Jones and Dawkins, 2018).

Image 2-1 The Sensorama (Sensorama, Thanksgiving - How to Kill an Hour, 1962)

The concept of VR refers to a whole simulated reality, which is built with computer systems by using digital formats. Building and visualising this alternative reality requires hardware and software powerful enough to create a realistic immersive experience (e.g. VR helmets or dedicated glasses and 3D software) (Martín-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2017). This Immersive technology aims to blur the boundary between the physical and virtual worlds and enables users to experience a sense of immersion (Lee, Chung and Lee, 2013; Lee, Shan and Chen, 2013).

Sensory simulation is at the heart of virtual reality technology. Typically, vision, and often auditory, touch and force feedback are combined to allow the participant to perceive the virtual environment as reality and provides the user with immersion. When referring to VR, “immersion” is usually used with the more restricted meaning of “spatial immersion”. Spatial immersion into the virtual reality environment is a perception of being physically present in a non-physical world (Freina and Ott, 2015). This is done by surrounding the VR user with images/sound and/or other stimuli such as smell, touch and environmental simulations. All these factors make the user feel that they are actually present, making the experience feel authentic and real. Generating high quality visual representations of simulated environments is of great importance since vision is our dominant sense (Riedl and Young, 2011). When combined with a wide field of view, stereoscopic vision, head and hand tracking with low latency between movement and visual updates, they all improve the realism of the experience for the participant. VR recreates a 3D spatial experience where the participant perceives that they belong to a virtual world (e.g. a player in a videogame), influenced by his or her perceived feeling of being transported into the artificial environment (Koleva *et al.*, 2000).

VR’s real power is not to produce an accurate reproduction of “reality” but to allow the participant to step outside the normal constraints of reality and experience the world in new and unpredicted ways (Graziano, Yap and Gross, 1994). When using VR as an “unrealities” simulator, we are given a chance to undertake experiences virtually. No other platform can offer this. The events that are undertaken may be ones that are highly implausible or cannot possibly happen (Gavish *et al.*, 2011). We can compare the current state of VR to that of the transition between theatre and movies as pointed out by Pausch *et al.* (1996). Movies were originally an extension of the theatre experience. It was many years before moviemakers developed a new ‘grammar’ and invented new ways of presenting a story unique to film. So, the same will be true of VR (Pausch *et al.*, 1996).

VR environments can offer enough cues to deceive our perceptual system into it assuming “this is a room” and then based on a current visualised internal model infer a version of this room using a perceptual fill-in mechanism (Slater and Sanchez-Vives, 2016). There are three key features integrated into any VR system: Immersion, Interaction and Visual Realism. Immersion can only be created by surrounding the user with virtual technologies and devices (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Immersion into the virtual world is a key aspect to us believing the simulation and trusting the realism of the experience. However,

any misalignment of the sensory cues can break the perceived realism causing cognitive differences, these discrepancies within the virtual environment can recreate a sensory imbalance such as vertigo or motion sickness. This may break the immersion for some users, but it can also be deliberate and welcomed within VR experiences such as thrill rides (Marshall *et al.*, 2019).

A particular property of immersion is presence. If a participant in VR perceives by using his or her body in a natural way, then the simplest interpretation for the brains' perceptual system to make is that what is being seemingly experienced is the participant's actual surroundings. This becomes an illusion to the participant that is referred to in literature as presence – the impression of “being there” in the environment as shown by the VR displays even though you are aware that you are not there (Groom, Bailenson and Nass, 2009). Interactions in the VR world are crucial elements of any VR experience. The foremost device used for interaction in VR is the HMD (Head Mounted Display) (Schultze, 2010).

Image 2-2 Tracking methods (Delight XR, no date)

A HMD system often works in parallel with head motion tracking or eye tracking for enhanced realism. HMDs are often both an input and an output device. Inputs can include head motion tracking sensors (Alves Fernandes *et al.*, 2016), eye motion tracking (Essig *et al.*, 2012) gyroscopes (Hyde *et al.*, 2008) and accelerometers (Vaughan, Gabrys and Dubey, 2016). Using an active input system can create a deeper immersive feeling. Some of the input devices available that allow a user to interact with a virtual environment are:

- Handheld controllers (Liang *et al.*, 2015).
- Gloves with movement sensors (Weissmann and Salomon, 2003).

- Surround sound (Madole and Begault, 1995).
- Other components to create sensorial stimuli, or sensors allowing the user to interact with a virtual environment as they would be able to in a real environment (Martín-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2017).

Image 2-3 The Exit-Suit, pushing the boundaries of VR immersion. (EXIT SUIT — Zachary Berry, no date)

Despite the increasing popularity of immersive technology and its influence on business and society (Huang and Liao, 2015), most of this research focuses on the development of hardware/software for deployment, without focusing on a better understanding of the effects of how immersion relates to learning outcomes, regardless of being positive or negative or in fact indifferent to other well tested teaching approaches.

The work of Milgram and Kishino "A Taxonomy of Mixed Reality Visual Displays, (1994)" presents a groundbreaking classification system for immersive realities, which has been influential in shaping our understanding of this domain. Their work introduced the concept of the Reality-Virtuality (RV) Continuum (Image 2-4), which categorises environments based on the extent of virtual content and interaction with the real world.

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Image 2-4 Simplified representation of a "virtuality continuum"

This continuum ranges from the completely real environment to the fully virtual environment, with mixed reality (MR) and augmented reality (AR) falling in between. In this taxonomy, MR is a hybrid of both real and virtual worlds, creating a scenario where physical and digital objects coexist, enhancing the way individuals interact with their surroundings. This concept has been pivotal in the development of AR technologies, where digital overlays augment our perception of the real world, and in VR technologies that immerse users in entirely virtual experiences. The classification proposed by Milgram and Kishino not only provided a framework for understanding various mixed realities but also spurred further research and development in the field, leading to advancements in AR and VR technologies that continue to revolutionise interaction and visualisation techniques in various sectors, including education, entertainment, and medicine (Skarbez, Smith and Whitton, 2021; Ebert and Lindblom, 2023).

2.1.1 Virtual Reality.

Virtual reality headsets can be categorized based on various factors, such as the hardware setup, connectivity, and tracking systems. Here are some main categories of virtual reality headsets:

- **Tethered VR Headsets:** These headsets are connected to a high-powered gaming PC or console via cables. They offer a high-quality VR experience, usually with superior graphics, positional tracking, and refresh rates. Examples include the Oculus Rift series, HTC Vive series, and PlayStation VR(2).
- **Standalone VR Headsets:** These headsets have all the necessary hardware built-in and do not require a connection to a PC or console. They are more portable and user-friendly but may not offer the same level of graphical fidelity as tethered headsets. Examples include the Oculus Quest series and the Pico Neo series.
- **Smartphone-based VR Headsets:** These headsets utilise smartphones as their display and processing unit. Users insert their smartphone into the headset, which then functions as a VR

device. While these headsets are relatively affordable and accessible, they generally provide a lower-quality experience compared to standalone or tethered headsets. Examples include Samsung Gear VR and Google Cardboard.

- Hybrid VR Headset: These headsets can function both as standalone devices and tethered devices, offering greater flexibility. They can be connected to a PC for a higher-quality VR experience or used independently for convenience and portability. An example of a hybrid VR headset is the HTC Vive Focus series.
- Enterprise/Industrial VR Headsets: These headsets are designed for specific professional or industrial applications, such as training, medical simulations, and engineering. They may have specialized features tailored to their intended use, and their pricing can be significantly higher than consumer VR headsets. Examples include the Varjo VR series and the XTAL VR headset by VRgineers.

Image 2-5 Selection of different VR Headsets. (Virtual Reality experience design plan | by Kumar Ahir | AR/VR Journey: Augmented & Virtual Reality Magazine)

2.1.1.1 PC VR

Utilising a desktop or a laptop PC, the headset is connected to a more powerful computer that processes the heavy graphics in real time while taking in positional inputs via the sensors either on the headset and/or in the room where the VR is set up to provide six degrees of freedom (6DOF) immersive experience. The computer could be a Windows PC, Mac, Linux, or a gaming console. Most likely, the headset is connected to the computer with wires although several wireless solutions are now available. The game runs on a powerful machine remotely and the HMD (head-mounted display)

is a peripheral display. Leaders in this field are the Meta (Oculus) and HTC and Valve, these are examples of a device where the headset has integrated displays for each eye, sound and built-in sensors with motion controllers for each hand, both systems used to rely on external sensors to map the position of the user in a room (Room Scale) however, since mid-2019 a new generation of headsets now have an inside-out tracking system. Sony's PlayStation VR2 has a simpler set up but relies on a PlayStation 5 console to run the game and its own camera system for positional tracking. Microsoft has invested in the sector also by partnering with some big names in PC manufacturing such as HP, Lenovo and Acer to produce a HMD that can run its Windows Mixed Reality platform, these devices don't need an external sensor to track the location of the user to provide 6DOF, everything is taken care of within the headset's sensors and its two motion controllers. These headsets can run on a lower spec computer also, however, the experience can be compromised by this.

2.1.1.2 Mobile VR

Mobile VR found its popularity with the launch of Google's Cardboard, a simple housing (originally made from cardboard hence the name) for a mobile phone. It has two lenses, like the desktop VR headset, but it has no positional tracking other than the phone's gyroscope to track the head rotation allowing you to look around in the virtual world, this provides the user with a three degrees of freedom (3DOF) experience. Cardboard also provides the user with the ability to click or tap on the side of the headset to make selections in a game. The complexity of the imagery is limited because it uses a phone's processor for rendering the views on the phone's display screen. There are versions of Cardboard-compatible headsets that are available for all sizes of phones—both Android and iOS. Others have taken this 'pare down' VR experience and made their own cardboard-esque headsets, some have been quite successful like Samsung's Gear VR, which only works with a few flagship Samsung devices. The Gear VR has a compatible controller too, allowing a greater variety of games/experiences to be developed for the platform. Google upgraded their cardboard experience by adding a controller and a more premium headset in the Daydream device. One other noteworthy mention in the mobile sector is the Oculus Go, this has its own screen like its big brother the Oculus Rift but runs on a mobile platform with a single motion controller. Although the quality of the VR experience with a mobile device is limited it's more seen as a "starter" device that is fine for small projects, and 360 video/photo viewing for affordable, quick or large-scale. Oculus (now known as Meta) released the first mobile 6DOF VR system in mid-2019 with the launch of the Quest, the completely mobile system doesn't have the power of PC VR but can run a more comprehensive VR experience than any other mobile system. In autumn 2020 the second generation of this Quest device, the Quest 2 quickly became the flagship headset driving the adoption of VR with an estimated 20 million units sold to date (Heath, 2023).

2.1.2 Augmented Reality

Augmented reality, commonly abbreviated to AR, is a technology that overlays computer-generated elements on the top of the real-world. These are coming in many different form factors. A sister technology to VR, AR, is where a superimposed computer-generated image is put over views of the real world. AR can be found on smart phones, tablets, handheld gaming systems such as the Nintendo 3DS, and even in some science museum exhibits, which overlay the CGI on top of live video from a camera. The latest innovations in AR are mixed reality headsets, such as Microsoft HoloLens and the Magic Leap and the recent Tilt5 headset, these devices show the computer graphics directly in your field of view. If a VR headset is like a closed set of goggles, the AR headsets are like a pair of sunglasses that employ a similar technology to the VR headset to combine the real-world with CGI. These devices scan the real world and map it out to allow it to know where you are and where it can place the computer-generated objects. These devices can track hand/gesture or controller movement. The Magic Leap doesn't even need to have a standalone computer attached to it to produce its CGI content, however, a small pocket size 'pod' is attached via a cable which houses the brains of the unit, the user needs to carry this around with them, clipping it to a belt or a pocket.

Here are some common types of AR devices:

- Smartphones and tablets: Many smartphones and tablets now have built-in AR capabilities that allow users to view digital content overlaid in the real world through the device's camera.
- Smart glasses: These are glasses that use AR technology to project digital content onto the user's field of view. Examples include Google Glass and Microsoft HoloLens.
- Head-mounted displays (HMDs): These are devices that are worn on the user's head, like VR headsets, but use its cameras to 'pass-through the real world. Devices such as the Meta Quest Pro and the Linx R1 have been built specifically for this but some VR headsets have a rudimentary implementation of some AR features.
- Wearables: These are devices that are worn on the body, such as smartwatches and fitness trackers, that use AR technology to provide information or enhance the user's experience.
- Smart helmets: These are helmets used in industries such as construction and manufacturing that use AR technology to display information about the user's environment, such as safety warnings or instructions.
- Projection systems: These are devices that project digital content onto real-world surfaces, such as walls or tables, creating an AR experience for the user.

Image 2-6 Common types of AR devices. (Coles, 2020)

The field of AR is rapidly evolving, and new types of devices are being developed all the time. As the technology continues to improve and become more accessible, we can expect to see even more innovative and useful AR devices in the future.

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2.1.3 Mixed Reality

Mixed Reality (MR) combines the real world with digital items to create a new environment in which users can interact with both. To produce a hybrid experience, MR integrates components of both Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). In MR, digital items are not just superimposed on the real world (as in AR) but rather are seamlessly incorporated into it, giving the impression that they are a natural part of the surroundings. MR technology uses sensors to map the physical environment and track the user's movements, allowing the digital objects to interact with the real world in real-time. MR technology enables real-time interaction between digital items and the physical world. The ability to create more immersive and interactive experiences is one of the key advantages of MR. A player may see a virtual object in a mixed reality game that they may physically manipulate, for instance, by picking up and manipulating a virtual ball with their hands. Another potential application for MR is in education and training. By creating realistic simulations that blend the physical world with digital elements, MR can allow users to practice skills in a safe and controlled environment. It can be described as either mixed reality, MR or hybrid reality. The term refers to any technology that isn't a fully immersive VR system. This is also (confusingly) used to describe Microsoft's virtual platform, which includes both VR and AR devices.

2.2 Immersive Education: The Next Frontier of Learning Technologies

Of key interest to this Ph.D., is the potential for VR's use in education. VR provides learning opportunities for students to experience, repeat and debrief scenarios which would otherwise be difficult to replicate in real life. Importantly, it provides a space for experimentation and learning with minimal risk to pupils (Dieker *et al.*, 2014a). There is potential for the use cases of VR within education across varying disciplines including but not limited to teacher training, engineering, medical education, mathematics, and computer sciences. Researchers in the field of learning theory and VR have generally agreed that VR technology is exciting and provides a unique and effective way for students to learn (Monahan, McArdle and Bertolotto, 2008) when it is appropriately designed and applied, and that VR projects are highly motivating to learners (Ausburn and Ausburn, 2004). However, the majority of higher education is taught traditionally through a non-immersive form where a student learns in a decontextualised environment.

The application of VR to professional situations which are emotionally rich and socially complex, such as a classroom environment, remains limited (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). Despite this, several studies have considered its use in teacher education, including recent work by O'Connor and Andrews, (2018) and multiple studies by Stavroulia and colleagues (Kalliopi Evangelia Stavroulia, 2015; Stepan *et al.*, 2017a; Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019; Demitriadou, Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2020).

Dieker *et al.*, (2014b) have explored the use of VR in teacher training. They propose that if learning methods for children in school are adapting to technological advances, then so must the field of teacher education. They also state that for simulated teacher training environments to be useful they must define the specific target teacher behaviours being addressed. For example, Guerra-Tamez, (2023) suggests that the physical environment of VR is one which engages students. This, therefore, has the potential to be used as a targeted behaviour for the development of learning spaces. Students teachers using VR would have the opportunity to experiment with different classroom layouts, exploring how these may influence a child's learning experience. Dieker also proposes three fundamental factors for simulated environments to be effective. These include:

- A sense of 'real presence' where the student suspends their disbelief.
- Opportunities for self-reflection based on collaborative work and debriefing with tutors and peers.
- A cyclical process allows repetitions and practice, also known as the Action Review Cycle (ARC) (DeGrosky and Parry, 2011).

A VR platform, known as Second Life, has been examined in regard to its potential in providing a virtual training environment for online teaching students. The experience of using Second Life was explored by O'Connor and Sakshaug, (2009) with 30 trainee teachers from three different teacher

training courses. Students met within the virtual environment to interact and complete set tasks e.g. produce a science project. Their feedback and that of the instructor were used as the basis of the evaluation. Findings demonstrated that the students responded well to the VR training environment. This, however, involved a steep learning curve for most students and required effort and engagement to familiarise themselves with the technology. Students reported a ‘suspension of belief’ when in the VR environment, making the interactive aspects particularly engaging. The physical environment appeared to be particularly engaging for students. They made suggestions for how they wanted their environment to look and feel, putting forward ideas for room design and other physical characteristics. Overall, this study highlighted the potential use of VR in teaching. Positive findings were found for online student interaction and task completion. However, it did not explore how a VR environment could be used to provide students with ‘immersive experiences’, for example, to deliver learning outcomes to a class. In relation to bias, although the author of this study was also the Second Life instructor, and students knew beforehand that their feedback would be analysed, the feedback appears constructive and helpful to the development of VR in education.

At the core of the implementation of VR technologies and educational applications is a Virtual Reality learning environment (VRLEs) (Chittaro and Ranon, 2007). The VRLE allows the educator to run a stimulated immersive experience for the student to safely interact, explore and acquire knowledge and skills. The student can repeatedly run through the experience without worrying about safety or cost, reducing any risk to the students and educators. VR can therefore offer a valuable substitute for real life experience (Huang, Rauch and Liaw, 2010). Building a VRLE can be quite a technical feat, even the most basic form requires a high level of programming knowledge (Mantovani, 2001). Many educators will not have the ability or time to invest in gaining the practical knowledge and experience to build a custom VRLE. Also, a teacher might not have the experience of implementing a virtual reality system within a classroom setting, causing them difficulties to put such a system into practice (Chittaro and Ranon, 2007). Pre-built learning experience and support on an institutional level will be needed for the non-technical practitioners adding to the cost and complexity of integrating the technology. Once an institute or individual has invested in the technology and/or application they have the problem of it becoming out-of-date due to rapid technology advances (Hanson and Shelton, 2008).

The usability of VR in an educational setting is a key factor to the learner’s experience and therefore any gains they may not get from a learning outcome. Thought around the user interface (UI) and its usability needs to be investigated before mass adoption, currently many VRLEs are being built for functionality, and users can find it difficult to navigate around these environments (Chittaro and Ranon, 2007) making the experience less effective in the goal of creating a more engaged learning experience, leaving users to get lost or experience motion sickness (Fernandes and Feiner, 2016). Learners may have a negative attitude toward using the technology. According to Chittaro, the virtual approximation of the real world can be off putting for some people. Being placed inside a headset or tied to a computer

could be uncomfortable for some. This could be extenuated if the user has a physical or learning disability.

Theories around promoting positive learning experiences put forward by Piaget, (2003) and Garrett, (1997) believe that the educator's role was to shape a learner's real experience (Ornstein and Hunkins, 2018). Five key learning styles are named as:

- (i) Situated learning: Placing a student in a real-world situation to allow them to practice improving their skills. A virtual reality simulation is replacing the real world for high quality realistic environments that can offer richer perceptual cues and feedback via visuals, sounds and haptics. This has the potential to offer a deeper learning experience (Hanson and Shelton, 2008);
- (ii) Role playing: Learning through role playing takes advantage of the capability of a VRLE to provide learners with specific characteristics and personalities (Holmes, 2007). The ability to construct and explore a variety of virtual worlds and avatars is not unique to VR. It has been used within other digital platforms and games for many years, this gives us some background research where Shih and Yang, (2008) found learners prefer playing and engaging in multi-players gaming because it offers a context, a chance to role play and competitive interaction tasks. Since immersion and interactivity are the major added value of VR these properties are reinforced by the platform;
- (iii) Cooperative/collaborative learning; Through working together in groups learners share experiences, exchange ideas and learn how to cooperate to acquire knowledge (Dimitropoulos, Manitsaris and Mavridis, 2008). A VR shared space, an avatar and chat rooms enable users to share a common learning environment which can stimulate users' motivation and aspiration toward collaborative learning. Stavroulia and Lanitis, (2017) have explored using VR to simulate bullying in schools, where the teacher was able to experience an incident of bullying from two different perspectives: (a) that of the teacher, and (b) that of the pupil. Results showed that teachers who experienced the bullying simulation in a physical real classroom gained a lower score for reflection and empathy than teachers in the VR group, who got to experience the bullying simulation from the perspective of the pupil. The use of VR in collaborative learning can give the users a richer experience with enhanced social interactions more than a regular flat screen platform;
- (iv) Problem-based learning is a fundamental skill necessary for learning that encourages learners to solve a problem by working through it, failing and repeating until an adequate solution is found. This promotes learners to develop independent thinking abilities and collaborative learning (Brenton *et al.*, 2007). The ability to be able to run a scenario repetitively and safely within the VR learning environment provides learners with a rich

and focused learning environment and allows learners to collectively understand and solve visualisation problems in a group (Wollensak, 2002);

- (v) Creative learning. According to Hsiao *et al.*, (2006), creativity is one of the core resources for problem solving, and Isaken and Parnes, (1985) state that problem solving, creative thinking and creativity learning are correlated. Most problems need creative thinking to solve. The imagination aspect of VR promotes learners in developing problem-solving capacity for open-ended problems. Creative visualisation is the technique of helping learners to develop imagination in what learners want to learn in VR learning environments.

The integration of augmented reality technologies within the educational landscape has emerged as a promising approach to enhance learning experiences and outcomes too. Current AR technologies and their applications are being used in various educational fields, including nursing, neurosurgery, civil engineering, primary education, and chemistry.

Augmented reality is an interactive technology that blends the physical and virtual worlds, providing users with an immersive and engaging experience. As a result, AR offers unique affordances for education, including continuous and implicit user control of the point of view and interactivity (Kesim and Ozarslan, 2012). The potential of AR has been recognised in various educational fields, from nursing (Foronda *et al.*, 2016) and neurosurgery (Pelargos *et al.*, 2017) to civil engineering (Dinis *et al.*, 2017), primary education (Demitriadou, Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2020), and chemistry (Nechypurenko *et al.*, 2020). AR technologies can be categorized into marker-based, marker-less, projection-based, and location-based systems. Marker-based AR uses physical markers, such as QR codes, to trigger digital content, while marker-less AR relies on image recognition and tracking to overlay virtual elements onto the real world. Projection-based AR projects digital images onto physical surfaces, and location-based AR uses GPS or other positioning systems to deliver context-specific information (Wang *et al.*, 2018).

This medium offers the unique possibility of combining physical and virtual worlds, with continuous and embedded user control for the point of view and interactivity. Kesim and Ozarslan, (2012) provide an introduction to the technology of augmented reality and its possibilities for education. The implementation of AR in education varies depending on the pedagogical approach and the subject matter. In nursing education, six emerging products and systems have been introduced to improve training, such as simulation-based learning and collaborative AR environments (Foronda *et al.*, 2016).

Advancements in VR and AR represent some of the newest modalities being integrated into neurosurgical practice and medical education. In neurosurgery, AR has been integrated into surgical practice and resident education to enhance surgical planning, navigation, and visualization of complex anatomical structures (Pelargos *et al.*, 2017). Wang *et al.*, (2018) research categorises current AR technologies, introduces a review of relevant literature, and presents case studies illustrating AR

implementation utilising different pedagogical approaches. Taking advantage of the ability of virtual and augmented reality to visualise 3D objects (Demitriadou, Stavroulia and Lanitis, 2020) investigate the potential of using virtual and augmented reality technologies for teaching the lesson of geometric solids to primary school children. The purpose of Nechypurenko *et al.*, (2020) is an analysis of opportunities and a description of the experience of developing and implementing augmented reality technologies to support the teaching of chemistry in higher education institutions in Ukraine. Other influential work includes Lee, (2012); Ma, Jain and Anderson, (2014); and Elmqaddem, (2019).

One significant benefit of AR in education is its ability to foster student engagement and motivation. Radu, (2014) demonstrated that AR technologies can promote active learning and increase student motivation by providing an immersive and interactive learning environment. Similarly, Ibáñez and Delgado-Kloos, (2018) found that AR could lead to better learning outcomes, as students were more engaged in the learning process due to the interactive and immersive nature of AR technology.

Also, AR has been shown to enhance the understanding and retention of complex concepts. Wu *et al.*, (2013) reported that AR could help students visualize and comprehend abstract or difficult concepts through the use of interactive 3D models, thus promoting deeper understanding and long-term retention. In a study by Akçayır and Akçayır, (2017), the researchers found that students who used AR in their learning process achieved better retention rates and improved understanding of the subject matter compared to students who did not use AR.

In summary, several studies have demonstrated the potential benefit of using immersive technologies in education. Although there is not an extensive body of literature the key findings to date suggest that VR:

- has the potential to enhance the students' experience.
- may involve a steep learning curve and willingness to learn from teachers and students
- requires several fundamental components including a sense of 'real presence', opportunities for reflection, and a cyclic process of repetition and feedback.

Although initial studies show promising results, this is very much an emerging field. Despite the numerous benefits of immersive technology in education, there are challenges to its widespread adoption. One challenge is the cost associated with AR devices and software. As Kipper and Rampolla, (2012) noted, the high cost of AR devices can be prohibitive for many educational institutions, particularly those with limited budgets. Additionally, the development and implementation of AR/VR solutions often require specialized technical skills that may not be readily available within schools and universities (Bacca *et al.*, 2014). Another challenge is the potential for privacy and data security concerns. As AR and VR technologies often rely on collecting and processing of personal data, educators and institutions must ensure the appropriate measures are in place to protect student privacy

(Bermejo *et al.*, 2017). The pedagogical use of AR/VR is not common. However, as they continue to gain in popularity it may become a key training tool for teachers to use with students in their own learning environments. More will become known about the utility as they increase in their use and popularity, however, to date there are key gaps including studies specifically exploring the use of VR to teach, and whether it is feasible and effective for deployment within an educational setting.

2.2.1 The Virtual Classroom.

One of the ways immersive technology has opened up new possibilities is by delivering 360-degree content to learners. This is where VR and AR technologies are used to create a virtual environment that provides a '360-degree' view of the surroundings. Learners can interact with the virtual environment, manipulate virtual objects, and engage in collaborative activities with their peers. The technology can create virtual classrooms, where learners can access the content at any time and at their own pace.

One application of 360-degree learning in education is studying a new language with the technology creating an immersive environment for students to interact with native speakers of the language, allowing them to practice and improve their language skills in a real-world context. This provides an engaging learning experience that may be difficult to provide with traditional language learning methods, and almost impossible given that the learner could choose and language in the virtual world. Another application of 360-degree learning in education is in science and engineering education. Using the technology to create realistic simulations of experiments and procedures, allows learners to practice and refine their techniques in a safe and controlled environment. This provides an opportunity for learners to gain practical experience that due to cost or safety issues would not be possible with traditional methods. Other uses of 360-degree learning can be in training, particularly in fields such as healthcare and manufacturing. For example in healthcare, VR and AR technology can create realistic simulations of surgeries and procedures, enabling medical professionals to practice and refine their skills without putting patients at risk. Allowing professionals the opportunity to gain practical experience that is not possible with traditional methods. In manufacturing, 360-degree learning can be used to provide training on complex machinery and equipment. VR and AR technology can create simulations of the machinery and equipment, allowing learners to practice and refine their techniques without the need for expensive equipment or putting themselves at risk.

In a study conducted by Fealy *et al.*, (2019) the researchers demonstrated the effectiveness of VR as an alternative to traditional field laboratory exercises in transportation engineering. They found that the use of VR provided students with a more realistic and interactive learning experience, which enhanced their engagement and understanding of complex concepts. Another study by Jitmahantakul and Chenrai

(2019) focused on the development of 360-degree VR environments for geoscience classrooms. The researchers created 360-degree VR environments, which allowed students to explore geological formations and interact with scientific data in a more engaging and interactive way.

Researchers have also explored the potential of VR in healthcare education. For example, Davis and Summers (2015) explored the use of cinematic VR (cine-VR) training programs to address social causes of health issues like diabetes in the Appalachian population. The researchers found that the use of cine-VR training programs provided healthcare professionals with a more effective way of learning about complex medical issues that engaged the user.

However, the use of VR technology in education also presents several challenges. For instance, Anwar *et al.* (2020) conducted a study on the quality of 360-degree videos in VR and found that factors such as perceptual quality and motion sickness significantly impacted the learner's experience. The study highlighted the need for careful attention to the technical aspects of video production for VR to ensure that the learning experience is enhanced. Zucchi *et al.* (2020) emphasised the importance of designing VR environments that provide learners with a sense of presence and immersion, acceptability, reality judgment, and attention captivation. Resolution and frame rate of the VR experience has huge implications on the experience, this should be taken into consideration when developing VR learning experiences.

As demonstrated by the work of Fealy *et al.* (2019), Jitmahantakul and Chenrai (2019), Taubert *et al.* (2019), and Adnan *et al.*, (2020), the use of VR in education can provide a more interactive and realistic environment, which enhances the learner's engagement and understanding of complex concepts.

In addition, VR technology can provide learners with a more flexible and accessible learning experience. The benefits are obvious for the student who has limited or no access to labs or is able to attend in person giving the possibility to undertake an activity that may be restricted otherwise. Although, the use of this technology presents several challenges. With the need for careful attention to be paid to the technical aspects of its development to ensure that the user is not made to feel uncomfortable or even sick through the use of the technology.

2.2.2 Distance Education

Immersive technologies offer significant opportunities for remote learning by simulating real-world environments and providing interactive, engaging experiences. These technologies enable students to access personalised educational content from anywhere, promoting self-paced and self-directed learning. Here are some ways immersive technology can support remote learning:

- Virtual Field Trips: VR can transport students to remote locations, such as museums, historical sites, or even outer space, providing them with engaging, context-rich learning experiences without the need for physical travel.
- Collaborative Learning Environments: AR and VR can create shared virtual spaces where students can work together on projects, participate in group discussions, or receive personalised feedback from instructors, regardless of their physical location.
- Simulation-Based Learning: Immersive simulations can provide students with hands-on experience in a variety of subjects, from science experiments to language practice, allowing them to learn at their own pace and receive immediate feedback.

The aim of (Chen *et al.*, 2010) are to improve the learning of underrepresented students; provide a platform to publish the VR-Lab courseware developed in senior projects; promote inter-institutional collaboration by developing and sharing VR-Lab courseware; develop faculty expertise through research and teaching initiatives; and circulate results and findings of the project to other universities and colleges. Chen *et al.* (2019) present “ImmerTai”, a system that is designed for effective remote motion training, particularly for Chinese Taichi, in an immersive way. Souza *et al.* (2020) introduce a VR serious game to support teaching and learning processes in neuroanatomy health education. With the objective to address these limitations, the work introduces a new process to create VR content that is easy, rapid, and affordable for educators to adopt and implement into their curriculum. The results indicate great potential for low-cost VR in remote learning as the sample of students reported that they enjoyed the ‘first-hand experience’ of touring places that were inaccessible to them due to the pandemic (Mujuru and Lopez, 2021). The long-term purpose of Demirel *et al.* (2021) is to develop a completely immersive VR chemistry lab. Karan V and TSubha (2021) propose a VR and AR-based virtual classroom environment system called "Edu VR" which encourages students to learn with a high level of participation and focus. Wilkerson *et al.* (2022) contain quantitative and qualitative ratings of VR as an educational tool.

2.2.3 Cross-Platform Education with AR and VR

Cross-platform learning has become a popular teaching method, as it highlights the ability to deliver educational content seamlessly across various devices and platforms. The literature on cross-platform learning with AR/VR/MR is full of innovative approaches and promising results.

- Immersive VR and Pedagogical Value: Yahaya (2006) pioneered the use of immersive VR technology to create authentic learning environments at a large technology-based university in Australia. Despite the burgeoning popularity of serious games, the pedagogical value of immersive worlds remains nascent and under-researched. Nevertheless, seminal works such as

those by Bell, Savin-Baden and Ward (2008) have laid the groundwork for the exploration of the pedagogical purposes of these digital spaces, even if they are not rooted in empirical research.

- Effectiveness of 3D Interactive Environments: Mayrose (2012) investigated the efficacy of 3D interactive environments on learning, engagement, and preference among 180 students, yielding significant results favouring this novel technology over conventional educational practices. Cai, Tay and Ngo (2013) extended this line of inquiry by examining a diverse range of educational settings, including gifted programs, normal (technical) streams, and special needs education.
- Context Conditioning and immersive VR: Kroes *et al.* (2017) addressed the challenges and potential solutions to optimise future studies of context conditioning utilising immersive virtual reality (iVR). Their work provides crucial insights into the methodological hurdles associated with implementing iVR in educational contexts.
- AR/VR Technologies in Language Classroom Settings: Scrivner *et al.* (2018) provide methodological recommendations for the design and employment of AR and VR technologies in language classroom settings, underscoring the importance of understanding the unique affordances of these tools in order to maximise their pedagogical benefits.
- Mixed Reality and RFID-Assisted Learning: Wu *et al.* (2021) scrutinized a taught subject on radio frequency identification (RFID) bolstered by mixed reality technologies within a higher education institution, employing the soft systems methodology (SSM) to gauge the alterations in learning performance. This investigation sheds light on the potential for MR to revolutionise the way complex subjects are taught and learned.

Capitalising on the unique affordances of AR, VR, and MR, educators can cultivate immersive learning environments that foster deeper understanding, enhanced engagement, and improved learning outcomes. Each of the technologies has its own benefits and weaknesses, VR, as a part of this framework, can provide immersive learning experiences that complement other digital platforms. For instance, students can use VR for experiential learning, AR for contextual information in real-world settings, and MR for interactive simulations that blend the virtual and physical worlds. This combination of immersive technologies offers students a diverse and engaging educational experience that transcends the limitations of traditional educational settings. Integrating VR with other platforms can enhance cognitive processes and motivation, as it caters to diverse learning styles and preferences. For instance, some students may benefit from the immersive nature of VR, while others may prefer the contextual information provided by AR or the interactive elements of MR. By offering a variety of experiences, cross-platform learning with VR can cater to different cognitive and emotional needs, ultimately promoting deeper understanding and improved learning outcomes.

The intersection of AR/VR/MR with other methods of learning lies in the development and implementation of sophisticated technologies that facilitate seamless integration of various immersive experiences. By refining and optimising the technological underpinnings of VR, AR, and MR, computer scientists can ensure that these tools function harmoniously within a cross-platform learning framework. This integration requires the development of interoperable systems, data synchronization, and user-friendly interfaces that allow learners to transition seamlessly between different platforms and experiences.

2.2.4 Immersive Technologies in Science Labs

Science labs, in particular, can greatly benefit from VR technology as it provides a safe and accessible alternative to traditional physical labs. This section will explore the current and future implementation of VR technology in science labs. It will highlight the benefits and challenges that come with using this technology in education. VR simulations can provide an immersive and engaging learning experience that helps students develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts.

Firstly, looking at the advantages of AR and VR in Science Labs, Thisgaard and Makransky (2017) demonstrate that immersive VR simulations can enhance students' learning experiences by providing them with realistic, engaging environments. Similarly, Lai *et al.* (2020) found that inquiry-based VR science labs improved learning outcomes in junior high school students, suggesting VR's potential as a valuable teaching tool. AR and VR can provide accessible, cost-effective alternatives to traditional laboratory environments, as highlighted by Rodriguez *et al.* (2016), who describe the use of affordable VR technologies for teaching purposes. Furthermore, AR and VR can offer unique opportunities for interdisciplinary research, as showcased by Portman *et al.* (2015), who discuss VR environments' applications in architecture, landscape architecture, and environmental planning. Timmers and Weppo (2020) focus on the spatial implications of VR, exploring how the technology influences our daily lives and understanding of space.

Despite the numerous advantages of AR and VR, these technologies also present certain challenges. Diniz Bernardo *et al.* (2021) highlight the need for further research on the integration of subjective and physiological outcomes in VR mood induction studies. Additionally, Zhang, Chembumroong and Surephong (2021) emphasise the importance of understanding the learning environment's role in the successful implementation of VR in education. Also, there may be concerns about the feasibility and scalability of AR and VR applications in science labs. In addition, there may be potential resistance to adopting these new technologies in traditional educational and research settings.

VR technology is already being used in science labs to provide a more immersive and engaging learning experience. Some universities and institutions have developed VR simulations for chemistry, biology, and physics experiments. These simulations allow students to conduct experiments in a virtual environment, which is safer and more cost effective than traditional physical labs. VR technology also allows students to repeat experiments and make mistakes without wasting resources, something that is not possible in physical labs. The use of VR in science labs has also been shown to improve student engagement and motivation. VR simulations can be designed to be interactive and engaging, which can help students develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Additionally, VR technology provides a level of realism and detail that traditional textbooks or lectures cannot match, making it an ideal tool for visual learners. One area where VR technology is expected to have a significant impact is in the training of future scientists. VR simulations can be used to train students in complex procedures, such as surgical procedures or chemical reactions, without the need for expensive equipment or putting students in danger. VR technology is also expected to transform science education by providing access to science labs for students who may not have the opportunity to attend a physical lab. Students in remote or underprivileged areas can access high-quality science education through VR simulations, levelling the playing field for all students.

VR in science labs has many benefits. One of the main benefits is that it provides a safe and cost-effective alternative to traditional physical labs. Students can conduct experiments without the risk of harm or injury, and institutions can save money by not maintaining expensive lab equipment. Additionally, VR technology allows students to repeat experiments and make mistakes without wasting resources, something that is not possible in physical labs. Another benefit of VR in science labs is that it allows for a more immersive and engaging learning experience. VR simulations can be designed to be interactive and engaging, which can help students develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Additionally, VR technology provides a level of realism and detail that traditional textbooks or lectures cannot match, making it an ideal tool for visual learners. However, there may be a learning curve for students and instructors unfamiliar with VR technology. Another challenge of VR in science labs is that it may not be able to replicate all aspects of a physical lab. While VR simulations can provide a realistic representation of experiments, they may not mimic the experience of working with physical equipment or the interpersonal interactions that occur in a physical lab.

2.2.5 Virtual Meeting Spaces

Highlighted by the pandemic virtual meeting spaces have gained considerable attention as an effective means of facilitating communication, collaboration, and learning across various fields. As the technology behind virtual reality and augmented reality continues to evolve, the potential applications

and impact of virtual meeting spaces become increasingly far-reaching. This analysis, delves into the development, deployment, and reception of virtual meeting spaces, taking into account the insights provided by recent research in the area.

The effectiveness of virtual meeting spaces depends significantly on the participants' ability to establish a sense of social presence and emotional connectivity. Ongoing research endeavours to develop advanced avatars, non-verbal cues, and real-time facial expression tracking to improve interpersonal communication and enhance empathy in virtual environments. As these technologies mature, virtual meeting spaces can encourage more meaningful and authentic connections between users, contributing to the overall success of collaborative projects and educational endeavours. Lee *et al.* (2021) introduced Post-Post-it, an innovative VR interaction system designed to overcome the physical limitations associated with traditional Post-it notes. This system allows for greater flexibility, ease of rearrangement, and efficient documentation and storage, demonstrating the potential for VR technology to revolutionise traditional organizational methods.

Ensuring that virtual meeting spaces are accessible and inclusive is crucial for maximising their potential impact. By promoting accessibility and inclusivity, virtual meeting spaces can empower a broader range of individuals to participate in collaborative and educational activities, thereby fostering a more diverse and innovative environment. Virtual meeting spaces can also bridge geographical boundaries, allowing students and teachers from around the world to engage in collaborative learning experiences and create a 'global classroom. Some notable examples of projects and research in this domain include:

- Stanford University's Virtual Human Interaction Lab (VHIL) (*VHIL | Virtual Human Interaction Lab*, 2019): VHIL is a pioneer in using VR for research and education. The lab explores the potential of VR for fostering empathy, promoting environmental conservation, and enhancing cross-cultural communication by exposing users to various global scenarios and perspectives.
- The British Council's VR English Language Classrooms (*How I built a virtual lab for schools | British Council*, 2018): The British Council has partnered with VR technology companies to develop immersive virtual classrooms that allow students worldwide to practice English language skills in realistic settings, such as business meetings and social gatherings.
- Harvard Business School's Virtual Reality Global Collaboration (VRGC) Project (Neeley and Leonardi, 2018): This project explores the use of VR as a tool for global collaboration among business school students. Participants engage in simulated business negotiations and decision-making processes with students from other institutions worldwide.
- The VR School Study (Southgate *et al.*, 2019): Conducted by researchers from the University of Newcastle in Australia and the University of Northampton in the United Kingdom, this study

investigates the use of VR and AR technologies in K-12 education settings. The study seeks to determine the effectiveness of immersive technologies in enhancing learning outcomes, engagement, and collaboration among students from diverse backgrounds.

- MIT's Education Arcade (*MIT Scheller Teacher Education Program*): This initiative focuses on developing immersive educational games and experiences, leveraging VR and AR technologies to create engaging and interactive learning environments

Another area being explored is virtual conferences and events. Virtual meeting spaces can facilitate large-scale conferences and events, reducing travel costs, and environmental impact while promoting networking and knowledge-sharing among professionals. Some notable examples of virtual conferences and events that utilize immersive technologies include:

- IEEE VR Conference (*IEEEVR Conference*): As one of the leading conferences in the field of virtual reality, IEEE VR has employed immersive technologies for presentations, workshops, and interactive demos. The conference has been exploring the use of virtual environments to facilitate global participation, offering remote attendees the opportunity to engage in the conference sessions and interact with fellow participants.
- The Virtual Reality Global Summit (*Vr/Ar Global Summit*): This event brings together experts, researchers, and practitioners from various industries to discuss advancements in VR and AR technologies. The summit leverages immersive environments to facilitate networking, collaboration, and knowledge-sharing among participants worldwide.
- Laval Virtual (Virtual, 2018): As a prominent international conference and exhibition focused on VR and AR, Laval Virtual employs immersive technologies to showcase cutting-edge applications, products, and research. The event uses virtual environments to enable attendees to engage with the latest innovations, exchange ideas, and create professional connections.
- Educators in VR (Educators in VR, 2022): This international organization hosts regular virtual events and conferences focused on the integration of VR and AR technologies in education. Educators in VR enable educators, researchers, and students to connect and collaborate on projects, research, and best practices in the field of immersive learning.

2.2.6 Emerging Technologies Converging in the Metaverse

The term the Metaverse has many different connotations depending on who is using the term and its context. Here we explore the Metaverse as a type of virtual world, where users can interact with each other and objects in real-time and how the metaverse can be used for educational purposes, as well as its potential benefits for students and educators alike. Covering everything from virtual reality

classrooms to individualised learning experiences and exploring the key issues as elucidated by various scholars and researchers in the field, considering diverse perspectives and applications.

In a 3D virtual reality environment Metaverse, individuals can communicate with each other and engage with digital content and although it only resides online, it resembles the real world. Science fiction author Neal Stephenson initially used the word "metaverse" in his book *Snow Crash*. In the book, the metaverse is a shared virtual world where people can meet and interact with each other. The metaverse has since been used to describe various VR environments, including those used for gaming, social networking, and education. There are a variety of VR platforms that offer different features and experiences. Amongst many some popular platforms include Horizon Worlds, Rec Room, and VR Chat. Users of these platforms can make avatars, or virtual versions of themselves, which they can use to engage with other users and explore virtual worlds. Virtual worlds provide a unique way of learning. Without ever leaving their homes, students can conduct experiments, attend classes, and visit museums in the Metaverse. To engage students in active learning, teachers might design immersive lesson plans that make use of the 3D environment.

The Metaverse's complex design is explained by Jaynes *et al.* (2003), who also discuss the underlying technical challenges that must be overcome to assure its practicality. To enable seamless interaction between users, devices, and virtual environments, the authors stress the significance of developing scalable, secure, and interoperable digital infrastructures. Additionally, they stress the importance of developing robust protocols for data management, access control, and user authentication. In their investigation of how virtual environments might be used to advance social inclusion, community involvement, and environmental supervision, among other things, Duan *et al.* (2021) explore the Metaverse's potential for social good. By doing this, they highlight how the Metaverse has the ability to transcend geographical borders and promote understanding between cultures.

The metaverse offers an exciting and immersive learning experience in education. There are several ways to integrate the metaverse into education, such as employing it for virtual field trips, classroom simulations, and online courses. The metaverse can additionally be used to supplement the traditional classroom, for example, students can use the metaverse to practice presentation skills or work on collaborative projects. Kye *et al.*, (2021) explored the educational potential and limitations of the Metaverse, who defined its four primary types and assessed their pedagogical implications. The authors explain the diverse educational contexts in which the Metaverse can be employed, ranging from collaborative learning environments to immersive simulations. They address potential drawbacks such as digital inequality and privacy concerns. The Metaverse also can provide a more personalised learning experience, as students can explore different areas at their own pace. In their examination of the digital "big bang," Lee *et al.*, (2021) suggested that the Metaverse could cause a paradigm shift like the advent of the internet. The authors argue that the combination of immersive technologies, such as virtual

reality, augmented reality, and holography, will transform how we interact with one another. This will fundamentally alter our perception of reality. The metaverse is still in its early stages, but it has already shown promise as an educational tool. The future of the metaverse is exciting, and it will be interesting to see how it develops over time.

2.3 Gamification and Game-based learning

In recent years, digital gaming has increasingly become a central aspect of entertainment, popular culture, and academic research. The UK Interactive Entertainment Association (UKIE) highlights that the digital gaming sector's growth, marked by unprecedented sales of gaming consoles and the popularity of online multiplayer platforms, has catalysed studies into their impact in our modern era (Ukie, 2022). Contrary to the outdated stereotype of a young, solitary male gamer, the demographic of average gamers has evolved significantly:

- The typical gamer is around 35 years old.
- Nearly half, about 46%, are female.
- Preferred games include puzzles, board games, and casual gaming genres.
- A significant portion, approximately 63%, engages in social gaming experiences.

While the concept of digital games may seem contemporary, the tradition of gaming has deep roots in human history, serving as a medium for entertainment, social bonding, education, and even survival since ancient times (McGonigal, 2011). These games have become a fundamental part of our cultural and recreational activities, influencing our society in ways both unprecedented and yet foreseen.

Moreover, the rise of digital gaming has opened new avenues beyond mere entertainment. One notable development is the concept of gamification, which involves integrating game-like elements into non-game environments to enhance user engagement and motivation. This approach, while still in its nascent stages, lacks a universally accepted definition and theoretical foundation, presenting diverse interpretations and applications in interactive systems (Deterding, 2012).

The academic community's reaction to integrating digital games into educational contexts has varied widely, ranging from scepticism to enthusiastic exploration through research and symposiums (Bigdeli and Kaufman, 2017; Kanthan and Senger, 2011; Dankbaar et al., 2016; Al-Hileh, 2018). As a relatively new field of study, gamification offers a fertile ground for scholarly inquiry, both as an academic subject and a methodological approach in the realm of computer-assisted systems (Seaborn and Fels, 2015).

Gamification as a term was coined in the early 2000s by British IT expert Nick Pelling, but only recently has it become widely used (Shpakova, Dörfler and MacBryde, 2016; Christians, 2018). Vianna et al.

(2014) expands on the description of gamification as “game mechanics used in different contexts in order to increase participation and generate engagement and commitment on the part of potential users”. While Domínguez *et al.* (2013) classify game mechanics as a variety of actions, behaviours and control mechanisms used to “gamify” an activity to create a compelling and engaging user experience. The game dynamics are the results of desires and motivations provided by the game mechanics, causing the person to participate in a more interesting way, and engaged in carrying out a specific activity (Colpani and Homem, 2015).

Although the term “gamification” is new, the concept is not (Al-Azawi, Al-Faliti and Al-Blushi, 2016). It has developed within recent years to be a more sophisticated means of engagement. Sectors such as marketing are using reward systems, points collection, and levels to attract and retain consumers (Seaborn and Fels, 2015). It has also gained the attention of educators who have introduced these elements into their learning activities (Hwang and Wu, 2012). Gamification in education refers to the layering of game-like elements over existing learning activities. While adding gamification elements does not fundamentally alter the underlying teaching approach, it may make learning activities more engaging for students (Papastergiou, 2009), notably by introducing a competitive aspect. Gamification is distinct from gaming, where game principles are employed at a deeper level. Many of today’s game-like educational activities vary from traditional tasks with gamification elements layered over the top, to true games which have been repurposed for education. Both gamification and gaming may be associated with computer, mobile and web-based platforms (Huang and Soman, 2013). Simple games may come in the form of drill-based or quiz-based educational apps, while more developed applications can come in the form of augmented and virtual reality games. Common gamification elements which can easily be layered over the top of existing learning activities include:

- Badges, which can be collected by players to demonstrate achievement.
- Levels with players progressing to higher levels once they have demonstrated competence at lower levels.
- Leader boards with top players able to see their positions relative to competitors.

Therefore game-based learning keeps the defined learning outcomes (Shaffer, 2006) but tackles them through game play.

In the field of education, there is considerable interest in using games to motivate and engage student learning (Papastergiou, 2009; Miller *et al.*, 2011). This interest is fed by the rhetoric of games as a “fun” way to engage students in learning. It is hoped that the fun and enjoyment of playing digital games lead in some peripheral and painless manner to student mastery of curriculum subject matter. Compared to players of popular casual games, players of educational simulation games perform complex procedural knowledge related operations; thus, greater focus and involvement in the game and its learning content during the gaming process are required (Chee, Mehrotra and Ong, 2015).

However, (Adams, 2019) states that the underlying game dynamics and concepts (Freedom to fail, Rapid Feedback, Progression, Storytelling) are very important to create motivation and not just achievements, badges and game looking graphics. The utilisation of gamification may not always be beneficial for teaching and learning motivation, but it certainly is a concept to enhance motivation (Tüzün *et al.*, 2009). It must be carefully developed, with the user in mind to actually achieve a motivation increase. This work addressed questions about teachers' use of analogue or virtual games to analyse if gamification has a basis of interested people in the teaching community. Generally speaking, it is beneficial if the teacher has basic skills in gaming to use gamified systems or to create game-like experiences during teaching. However, a user (teacher) centred ICT tool should be capable of enhancing the teachers' motivation irrespective of their gaming knowledge or skills (Schulz, Isabwe and Reichert, 2015).

The use of digital technology in classrooms has risen steeply in the past decade. The speed at which technology has advanced, and its use within education, means that teachers often now use different digital resources throughout the day. Examples include computers, tablets, interactive white boards, smart TVs and projectors. Research suggests, however, that a traditional classroom, which often remains unchanged, is not always optimal for the diffusion of digital learning to take place (Byers, Hartnell-Young and Imms, 2018). Byers *et al.*, (2018) suggest the traditional classroom, with its front-facing didactic arrangement, is a barrier to effective use of digital technologies. They propose actively designing classroom spaces not only to use digital technologies but 'how to use' them. Many educators have either seen or experienced an application of immersive technology within their subject area and found it compelling.

3 Literature Review

3.1 Overview

The use of immersive technology and gamification in education is gaining popularity. Implementing the technology is becoming easier and more affordable, while software packages that have a serious game element or educational aspect to them, continue to improve. Over the past few years, the sector has rapidly expanded with big names in the technology sector (Meta, Google, Apple, and Microsoft) investing significant amounts of money. Given the fast pace of change in hardware and software, the technology has outpaced researchers' understanding of the field. To fill this gap, this research will focus on the use of immersive technology as well as gamification for computer science teaching and learning. The question of how technological advances in the field will impact education is difficult to answer at present with any degree of certainty but is one that must be considered by educational researchers, teachers, and administrators. Connolly, (2005) presents the foundational definitions and positions of several investigators in this area, along with thoughts on difficulties and complex issues that currently hinder the application of virtual reality in educational settings.

This section will review studies on the effectiveness of immersive technologies in various educational contexts and outline the research undertaken to gain a better understanding of the key terms. It will then look at gamification in education and review studies on the effectiveness of gamification in enhancing motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes in education. Then provide an overview of the challenges facing computer science education, such as the high dropout rates, the low motivation of students, and the difficulty in grasping abstract concepts (Kelleher, Pausch and Kiesler, 2007). Reviewing studies that have employed immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education and analyse the benefits and limitations of these approaches reported in the literature to determine the importance of innovative teaching methods for improving student engagement and learning outcomes (Guzdial, 2008). Any research gaps and opportunities will also be identified.

For this literature review, a selection of scientific articles on virtual reality, augmented reality, gamification, and their use within education were selected. It was decided that a systematic quantitative review would be the most suited method for identifying the limits of current knowledge (Pickering *et al.*, 2014) as well as providing an efficient method for finding current trends within a research area (Pickering and Byrne, 2014). Traditional narrative reviews are less rigid and arguably more thorough (Mays, Pope and Popay, 2005). It was decided, however, that this would not be appropriate for this literature review since these research methods are rarely used to map trends. A five-review procedure was implemented to process the content of this section:

- Compiling a list of research questions and review aims
- List search terms

- Conduct a database search, record and categorise gathered information.
- Review, evaluate and extract appropriate information.
- Report the finding. Using a systematic quantitative method in a literature review.

A rigorous search of the academic literature was undertaken in all of the relevant subject fields using Google Scholar, JSTOR, ProQuest, Scopus, Web of Sciences and EBSCOhost. A multidisciplinary selection of databases was chosen to encompass domains that are within and outside the scope of human-interaction computing to be able to capture published works from a wide field. A comprehensive search, using the terms shown below in table 1, was undertaken to gather the source review material of books, academic journals, reports, conference papers and Theses.

Table 1 Literature search terms and keywords

Field of search	Immersive Technology	Gamification	Education
Search terms	immersive, immersive technology, augmented reality, AR, virtual reality, VR, VR learning, virtual reality education, Virtual reality learning environment (VRLE).	Gamification, game-based learning, gamify, serious games, gamification learning.	Educational technology, educational/teaching/student development, technology integration, virtual learning.

A search over the timeframe by this PhD resulted in the yield of 1997 documents by January 2023 after adjustments for duplicates. The papers were collated using the Mendeley reference management application which enables the documents to be filtered into subject areas and produce a refined reading list. Producing spreadsheets containing data on the publication's title, authors, and date and they were published with a brief overview of the content of the paper to allow refinement of the document put forward for the literature review.

During the course of this review, particular emphasis was placed on keeping abreast of leading research groups within the field. These include renowned groups such as the Stanford Virtual Human Interaction Lab, MIT Media Lab, the HCI Group at Carnegie Mellon University, and the Immersive Technologies Lab at the University of British Columbia. Each of these groups has contributed significantly to the body of knowledge in virtual reality, immersive technology, and computer science education, and their work has provided invaluable context and direction for this thesis.

To maintain a comprehensive and current understanding of the field, a selection of key journals has also been regularly reviewed. Topics covered in the journals ranged from technical aspects of virtual reality and associated hardware to more pedagogically focused content on computer science and education. The insights gathered have been essential in shaping the direction and focus of this review.

The dynamic nature of this field of study necessitates an openness to new ideas and perspectives. As such, paper suggestions from colleagues were actively sought and responded to, which often led to the discovery of pertinent research outside of regular reading lists. This interdisciplinary approach has enriched the breadth of this review, enabling it to draw upon a diverse range of sources in understanding the current state of knowledge in this area.

3.2 Use Cases for Immersive Technologies in Classroom Delivery

The emergence of immersive technology in education has presented both opportunities and challenges for students, teachers, and administrators, particularly through the utilisation of virtual and augmented reality. Although learning with varied types of technology has been popular for some years, the pedagogical value of immersive worlds is currently not only undeveloped but also under researched. While several articles are not based on empirical research, they do offer new ways of considering the pedagogical purposes of using these kinds of digital spaces (Bell, Savin-Baden and Ward, 2008).

There are several theories that support the application of immersive technology in education, including situated cognition, constructivism, and experiential learning. Based on situated cognition, knowledge is constructed by actively engaging in meaningful contexts (Brown, Collins and Duguid, 1989). Immersive virtual environments provide learners with authentic, context-rich scenarios, facilitating situated learning experiences (Pena-Rios *et al.*, 2020). In constructivism, learners actively construct knowledge through interactions with their environment and experiences (Piaget, 2003). Virtual reality and augmented reality technologies can create environments that encourage exploration, problem-solving, and collaboration, fostering knowledge construction. Lastly, experiential learning emphasises the importance of direct experience and reflection for effective learning (Kolb and Kolb, 2014). Through immersive technology, learners can interact with virtual objects and environments, process their learning, and apply what they have learned to real-world situations.

Immersive technologies can be employed across a broad spectrum of educational domains, including gifted programs, normal (technical) streams, and special needs education (Cai, Tay and Ngo, 2013). In nursing and midwifery education, VR can provide realistic simulations for clinical practice, allowing students to develop practical skills in a safe and controlled environment (Fealy *et al.*, 2019b). Similarly,

immersive VR applications can train students in telecommunications engineering, preparing them for workplace scenarios (Pena-Rios *et al.*, 2020). Peña-Rios presents a plan to study the use of situated cognition theory as a learning framework to develop an immersive VR application that would be used to train and prepare students studying Telecommunications Engineering for the workplace. The study only has a limited number of participants so the results must be verified with further exploration.

Immersive technology offers several advantages for education, such as enhanced engagement, improved learning outcomes, and reduced cognitive load. By providing rich, interactive, and realistic environments, immersive technology increases learner motivation and engagement (Bell, Savin-Baden and Ward, 2008). Studies have shown improved problem-solving skills, better knowledge retention and transfer from using an immersive learning experience (Wu *et al.*, 2021b). Additionally, the use of immersive technology can reduce cognitive load by presenting information in a more intuitive and accessible manner, supporting the comprehension of abstract concepts (Kriukova, Holub and Ameridze, 2021).

An important benefit of immersive technologies in education is their ability to motivate and engage students. By placing students in realistic, interactive virtual environments, these technologies foster a sense of presence and immersion that traditional learning modes often fail to achieve. Students who are more engaged are more likely to improve their learning outcomes and retain information. For example, Torda (2020) demonstrated that the use of VR clinical scenarios combined with interactive online learning modules resulted in high levels of student engagement and learning gains in medical ethics. Although self-perceived knowledge gains were reported and the study did not introduce self directed students to the use of VR, it was found that immersive technologies can be particularly beneficial in areas such as healthcare, engineering, and science where complex problem-solving and decision-making skills are required.

Immersive technologies also promote collaboration and interdisciplinary learning, breaking down traditional barriers between subject areas and encouraging students to work together to solve complex problems. Students placed in virtual environments can collaborate in real-time, share ideas, and learn from one another, regardless of their physical location. In a causal comparative study by Wang and Sun, (2021), the researchers examined student engagement in VR co-creation, demonstrating how immersive technologies promote teamwork and collaboration. In another example, Karan V and TSubha (2021) proposed a VR and AR-based virtual classroom environment system called "Edu VR," which encourages students to learn with a high level of involvement and attentiveness, however, the author doesn't offer empirical data on the effectiveness of the application. As the world becomes increasingly reliant on the internet, Immersive technologies can better prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of the 21st century by giving them the skills necessary to navigate these platforms. Also engaging with immersive technologies in the classroom, found that students develop digital literacy

skills, such as adaptability, creativity, and problem-solving which are critical to their thriving in and outside of the classroom. The literature also shows that scenarios that maybe difficult or impossible to replicate in traditional classroom settings can be implemented in immersive education to expose students to real-world scenarios and experiences. For example, Gunn *et al.* (2021) reported on the experiences of medical imaging and radiation therapy students integrating VR education for learning computed tomography (CT) scanning. Although these types of simulations may lack in authentic realism by simulating clinical situations, immersive technologies can provide students with valuable hands-on experience and the opportunity to practice and refine their skills before entering the workforce.

Immersive technologies also have the potential to address accessibility and inclusivity challenges in education (Martín-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2017). There may be benefits to using immersive learning with students that have physical or cognitive disabilities as they have the potential to be adapted to the unique needs and abilities of the learner. For instance, VR can allow students with mobility impairments to virtually explore environments that may otherwise be inaccessible, while AR can provide additional support and information to students with learning disabilities. Furthermore, the ability to access content from anywhere in the world can help with bridging the digital divide, making high-quality education more accessible to students in remote or under-resourced schools. By leveraging cloud-based VR solutions and affordable hardware options, such as standalone headsets, educators can deliver immersive learning experiences to a broader range of students.

To summarise, the research has found that there are numerous benefits of using immersive technologies in education, these range from improved student engagement and better learning outcomes to encouraging collaboration and preparing students for the future. These technologies will continue to evolve, become more affordable and accessible, growing their potential to transform education. By embracing immersive technologies in the classroom, educators can provide students with the skills, experiences, and opportunities necessary to grow with this evaluation.

Despite the potential benefits, these immersive technologies can also present several challenges. High costs associated with the development and implementation of VR and AR systems can limit their accessibility in educational settings (Gnanadurai, Thirumurugan and Vinothina, 2022). There is a need for additional empirical research on the pedagogical effectiveness of immersive technology, as well as the development of best practices for its integration into curricula (Dreimane and Zalite-Supe, 2022) . Furthermore, potential negative effects of prolonged use of immersive technology, such as motion sickness and cognitive overload, warrant further investigation (Suri *et al.*, 2023).

3.2.1 Benefits of Immersive Technologies

Numerous studies have explored the impact and effectiveness of immersive technologies across various disciplines, including medicine, engineering, and nursing. By providing students with realistic and engaging experiences, immersive technologies have the potential to facilitate a greater understanding of complex subjects, foster expert reasoning, and expose students to high-fidelity scenarios that may not be easily accessible in traditional learning environments.

Student engagement with immersive technology in education has become a critical area of exploration in recent years. Research has focused on the effectiveness of virtual reality and augmented reality (in various educational contexts, including health sciences, medical anatomy, and language learning.

The subject of Moro *et al.*, (2017) was to assess whether learning structural anatomy utilising VR or AR is as effective as tablet-based applications, investigating whether these modes allowed enhanced student learning, engagement, and performance. The study didn't conclusively find that using the immersive technology was superior to the 2D display but it was limited by the participant mainly having little prior anatomy knowledge. 274 participants from the Taiwanese University of Science and Technology participated in Chen and Hsu (2020) study of self-regulation mobile game-based English learning in a virtual reality environment. Even though this study is only observational and does not include a control group, motivation, relevance, and test anxiety significantly influenced game engagement and game experience.

Calvert and Abadia, (2020) experimental study aimed to explain the benefits of VR in transforming learning and student experiences in classrooms, while Torda (2020) demonstrated that VR clinical scenarios combined with interactive online learning modules resulted in demonstrable high-level student engagement and learning gains in medical ethics, as well as knowledge transfer to clinical application. Gunn *et al.* (2021) reported on the experience of integrating VR education for medical imaging (MI) and radiation therapy (RT) students in learning computed tomography (CT) scanning.

Marks and Thomas (2022) evaluated the adoption of virtual reality technology in higher education. An evaluation took place across five teaching semesters in a purposely designed virtual reality laboratory that was formed in 2017 at The University of Sydney, containing 26 Oculus Rift headset units. Their study revealed the potential of VR in enhancing student learning experiences. As this was just an evaluation it does not ensure positive learning results for others using the same technologies.

Other notable works include those by Alwedaie *et al.* (2018) who analysed learning through a virtual reality environment using EEG-based analysis, and Ruiz-Cantisani *et al.* (2020), who explored virtual reality as a tool for active learning and student engagement in the context of industrial engineering education. Brown *et al.* (2023) discussed a large-scale, multiplayer VR deployment as a novel approach

to distance education in human anatomy. Furthermore, studies have investigated the potential of immersive technology in integrating art and STEM learning (Crayton and Svihla, 2015) and developing soft skills in STEM education (Hickman, Akdere and IEEE, 2017).

Collectively these studies demonstrate the potential of immersive technologies, such as VR and AR, to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes in a variety of educational settings. However, it is crucial to recognise that the effectiveness of these technologies may vary depending on the discipline, student population, and specific learning objectives. Further research is needed to optimise the integration of immersive technologies into educational environments and ensure that they complement traditional teaching methods rather than replace them.

However, despite the promising potential of immersive technologies, it is essential to acknowledge potential limitations, such as the effectiveness of technologies in varying disciplines, student populations, and learning objectives. As with any educational intervention, it is crucial to evaluate the effectiveness of immersive technologies on a case-by-case basis, ensuring that they are used as a complement to traditional teaching methods rather than a replacement.

3.2.2 Challenges of Using Immersive Technology

Existing literature investigates the use of immersive technologies in teaching and learning contexts with several studies exploring the different aspects of integrating these technologies into educational settings. Some highlight the potential challenges and benefits of using immersive technologies in education to offer insights into the design and implementation of these tools to enhance the sector. However, despite the promising benefits, the successful integration of such technology into educational environments is not without its challenges. This section discusses the main obstacles faced when incorporating VR into education and explores possible solutions to overcome these challenges, paving the way for more effective and widespread adoption of VR in the learning process.

It has been found that a primary challenge of integrating VR into education is the need for adequate technical infrastructure and resources. Schools and institutions may lack the necessary hardware, such as access or funding to supply VR headsets, computers with sufficient processing power, and high-speed internet connections, to support the style of education. Furthermore, many educational VR applications require ongoing maintenance and updates, which can strain limited IT resources. Dunleavy, Dede and Mitchell (2009) aimed to demonstrate how teachers and students describe and comprehend how augmented reality simulations aid or hinder teaching and learning. It focuses on developing student teachers' ability to use ICT in teaching and learning. A number of limitations are identified in this study, including scalability, cost, and adoption issues. The literature on integrating AR in classrooms is

especially limited when it comes to the challenges teachers face. Design-based research was the focus of this study.

Making high-quality educational content for VR is a complex and time-consuming process that requires collaboration between experts on the subjects, syllabus administrators, and VR developers. There is currently a limited amount of VR content available for education, and much of it focuses on limited subjects or age groups. In a similar vein to Divaharan, Lim and Tan, (2011) examined the learning trajectory of student teachers in a course that aimed to develop their capacity for using information and communication technology (ICT) in teaching and learning. Their reflection on the course design and university faculty's pedagogical practices revealed the importance of immersing pre-service teachers in the learning of ICT tools for knowledge creation, as well as the need for continuous adaptation and improvement. Nevertheless, this study is over 10 years old and technology has advanced since then.

Han (2019) investigated the advantages and limitations of immersive projection in the analysis of historical buildings, seeking to understand how high tech and low-tech methods could complement one another in design communication. The study illustrated the benefits of combining immersive environments with traditional methods, promoting a more comprehensive understanding of architectural design and historical context.

The literature demonstrates a growing interest in the application of immersive technology across various educational domains. For instance, Tahar Messadi *et al.* (2017) experimental study analysed immersive learning for sustainable building design and construction practices, while Young *et al.* (2020) explored the use of VR in higher education classrooms, seeking to understand how such technology could facilitate knowledge building and understanding. However, this study was only an evaluation of 39 participants so could be limited in its scope.

Integrating VR into education requires the development of new pedagogical approaches that reevaluates traditional teaching methods to allow the effective delivery and utilising the unique capabilities of VR. Educators must determine how to best utilize VR to meet learning objectives and enhance student engagement while avoiding potential distractions or negative impacts on learning outcomes. The purpose of Stojšić *et al.* (2018) is to present a literature review of VR applications in education (with emphasis on both technological and pedagogical aspects, integration, and evaluation criteria), as well as to show the results of a small qualitative study conducted with teachers and an educational media specialist (all familiar with using VR as a teaching tool) in the Republic of Serbia. Due to the small size of this study, this method of collecting data could be limited.

Despite the potential benefits, the implementation of immersive technology in educational settings faces numerous challenges, such as technological constraints, concerns about learning outcome accuracy, cognitive overload, and the need for continuous revision and improvement. To ensure the effective integration of these tools, it is crucial to address these challenges, while considering the unique needs

and characteristics of the individual educational setting and the people using them. A thorough understanding of the affordances and limitations of immersive technology can ultimately contribute to the development of more effective pedagogical practices and enhanced learning experiences for students.

3.3 Gamification In Education

Gamification has recently seen rapid growth in education, with an increasing number of studies being conducted over the past few years to explore its potential benefits and limitations. The method is being put forward as a promising approach to enhance engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes in education, with many studies having been conducted to investigate the potential. Researchers have found that, to be effective game elements need to be tailored to learners' individual needs. Compared to traditional teaching methods, one of the key advantages of gamification is that it provides a more interactive and engaging learning experience. By incorporating game elements such as points, badges, levels, and leader boards, learners are motivated to participate and progress in their learning journey. Furthermore, gamification can create a sense of competition and social interaction among learners, which can foster a sense of community and collaboration.

In the literature review several studies have been found on the use of gamification in different fields, such as software engineering, health professions, and science education. For instance, Ivanova *et al.* (2019) developed an approach for using games to teach software engineering methods and concepts, while Gentry *et al.* (2019) evaluated the effectiveness of serious gaming/gamification for health professions education compared to other types of learning interventions. The use of gamification in higher education has also been explored, with studies like Ofosu-Ampong *et al.* (2020) investigating the students' perception and acceptance of gamification in learning. For example, a study by Huang *et al.* (2020) examined the impact of gamification on students' engagement and academic performance in a high school science class. The findings suggested that the gamification intervention improved students' motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes. Similarly, a study by Zhang, Chembumroong and Sureephong, (2021) investigated the effects of gamification on students' engagement and performance in an online learning environment. The results showed that the gamified course had a significant positive effect on students' motivation, satisfaction, and learning outcomes.

Kalogiannakis, Papadakis and Zourmpakis (2021) present empirical findings on the use of gamification in science education, highlighting the potential benefits of gamification in promoting scientific thinking and motivating students towards science learning. Saleem, Noori and Ozdamli (2022) review the current literature on gamification and online education, discussing the reported benefits and challenges of gamification applications in online education.

Even though gamification can have potential benefits, there are opposing opinions (Hung, 2017; Ofosu-Ampong, 2020) and drawbacks that may occur with its implementation, such as the risk of becoming too dependent on rewards, the risk of losing interest if the game elements are not well designed, and the risk of reinforcing unhealthy gaming habits (Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017). It is important to tailor game elements according to learners' preferences and needs when implementing gamification in education (Hanus and Fox, 2015). This involves identifying the learners' interests, goals, and learning styles, and designing the game elements to align with these factors (Landers and Landers, 2014b). For example, learners who prefer competition may benefit from leader boards and ranking systems, while those who prefer collaboration may benefit from team-based games or social learning activities.

It is clear that gamification can enhance motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes in education if it is implemented in a thoughtful and evidence-based manner. Identifying and developing best practices for gamification implementation in various educational settings should be the focus of future research.

3.4 Computer Science education.

3.4.1 Challenges Faced in Computer Science Education

Over the past few decades, computer science (CS) education has grown significantly, with a vast body of research focusing on the challenges and issues that educators and students face. Several studies and research projects have explored various aspects of CS education, highlighting its complexities and challenges.

One of the challenges encountered in CS education is the integration of CS into the curriculum and the provision of support for teacher professional development (Sentance, Dorling and McNicol, 2013). Teachers often struggle to effectively teach complex CS concepts and techniques, highlighting the need for continuous professional development and support. The challenge is further complicated by the diversity of educational systems worldwide, as seen in Saudi Arabia (Malik *et al.*, 2018), Brazil (Epifânio *et al.*, 2019), and Mexico (Escherle *et al.*, 2016). The pedagogical skills and knowledge of teachers and professors in Information Technology (IT) and CS is a critical aspect that influences the quality of education (Martins de Souza *et al.*, 2021). Pedagogical approaches and teaching methods adopted by educators have an important impact on student learning. Moreover, the lack of face to face interaction, mental stress, and connectivity problems brought about by the shift to online learning environments due to the COVID-19 pandemic have further exacerbated the challenges faced by both students and educators (Haris and Al-Maadeed, 2021). Teaching assistants in CS face their own set of challenges, as they often need to navigate the complex landscape of multi-institutional and multi-

national academic environments (Riese *et al.*, 2021). Teaching assistants play a crucial role in teaching and a student's learning process, as they can provide valuable support.

There is an ambiguity surrounding the term "computer science" with a lack of clear definition that has added to a decrease in interest in CS education (Henderson, 2009). This confusion is seen in students, parents, and the general public, complicating the perception and understanding of computing and CS education. Various initiatives, such as the Scalable Game Design project (Basawapatna, Koh and Repenning, 2010) and research experiments conducted by Apiola *et al.* (2012), have sought to provide CS students with practical learning environments that foster creativity and engagement. Radenski (2006) suggested that CS course offerings could be made more attractive to students by introducing easy-to-learn scripting languages, such as Python, providing comprehensive online study resources, and offering detailed self-guided labs. Additionally, Falkner and Palmer (2009) proposed integrating cooperative learning techniques and authentic problem-solving processes throughout the curriculum to enhance student engagement.

Academic dishonesty is another concern within CS education, as students may be tempted to engage in unethical practices when completing coursework (Fraser, 2014). The development of educational serious games, as suggested by Rodríguez-Cerezo *et al.* (2014), may provide alternative learning methods that encourage ethical behaviour and reduce the likelihood of academic dishonesty.

Lastly, access to and barriers within CS education at the K-12 level have been investigated by Wang *et al.* (2016), who examined perceptions, access, and barriers to CS education in the United States through surveys of various stakeholders, including students, parents, teachers, principals, and superintendents.

In conclusion, there are many challenges faced in delivering computer science in education such as, pedagogical, curricular, technological, and ethical issues. There is a need for continued research as well as collaboration between educators, researchers, and policymakers to identify and address these challenges, ensuring the development of effective, accessible, and inclusive CS education for all.

3.4.2 Computer Science Innovative Teaching Methods

The field of computer science is constantly evolving, and innovative teaching methods can play a crucial role in maximising student learning outcomes. Presented here is a review of recent research in the area of innovative teaching methods in computer science, focusing on the use of VR, AR, and other emerging technologies in educational settings.

Several studies have explored the use of VR and AR technologies in various educational contexts, such as geography and building construction visualisation (Hedley *et al.*, 2002; Bashabsheh, Alzoubi and Ali, 2019). However, there remains a lack of empirical research comparing the educational impact of

AR and VR technologies (Huang *et al.*, 2019). Huang and colleagues addressed this gap by comparing the impact of immersive and non-immersive settings on learning outcomes, such as science retention, and found that VR was more effective than AR.

Educational fields that are abstract in nature, such as CS and other STEM fields, may benefit from alternative teaching methods to enhance student learning opportunities (Nersesian, 2020). For instance, Bourguet *et al.* (2020) describe a co-creation project between students and staff in two university departments to design and prototype VR and AR simulations for teaching materials science.

Several trends and hotspots in educational research have emerged, including cognitive load, learning environment, knowledge acquisition, training, gamification, assessment, children's education, engineering education, and higher medical education (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Oleksiuk and Oleksiuk (2020) describe the content of author training for practising teachers, while Turhan and Gümüş (2022) provide a brief history of VR/AR and their current roles in systems biology, as well as their advantages and disadvantages in augmenting user abilities. Other studies have focused on the impact of VR on learning outcomes in different educational areas, such as middle school education (Parmar *et al.*, 2022) and computer programming (Xie *et al.*, 2022). Veer, Phelps and Moro (2022) studied the incorporation of mixed reality for knowledge retention in physiology, anatomy, pathology, and pharmacology interdisciplinary education through a randomized controlled trial.

In addition to education, VR has been applied in clinical care and cognitive rehabilitation (Hilty *et al.*, 2020)). Agbo *et al.* (2021) developed a VR game-based application to support critical thinking knowledge, while Asadzadeh *et al.* (2022) presented a conceptual framework for the application of VR and AR technologies in managing child abuse. Finally, Li *et al.* (2022) presented a method for interior environment design for entrepreneurship education under the virtual reality and artificial intelligence-based learning environment.

The use of emerging technologies, such as VR and AR, has the potential to transform computer science education and other STEM fields. However, more research is needed to fully explore the educational impact of these technologies and to identify best practices for their implementation in educational settings. Also, there are some disadvantages to the use of emerging technologies in education. Firstly, these technologies can be expensive to implement and may require specialized equipment and training for teachers and students. Secondly, there may be concerns about the accessibility and inclusivity of these technologies, particularly for students with disabilities or from disadvantaged backgrounds. Additionally, there is a risk of over-reliance on technology and a potential reduction in human interaction and collaboration in the learning process.

Furthermore, it is important to note that not all students may benefit equally from these technologies, and there may be individual differences in learning styles and preferences that need to be considered.

Finally, there may be ethical considerations related to the use of VR and AR technologies, such as issues related to privacy, security, and the potential for addiction.

3.5 Overall Summary of Key Findings

Technology has a significant role in the teaching and learning space. Particular aspects of using the technology are known to affect learning in relation to attention, engagement, social interaction, creativity, sense of safety, empowerment and overall learning outcomes. As virtual reality and 3D learning environments become more accessible, educators are exploring technology as a way of delivering learning outcomes in a more immersive and engaging way. VR combined with the proven benefits of game-based learning can add value above that offered by more traditional approaches.

The current literature on immersive technology in education highlights several advantages and challenges of using tools like augmented reality, virtual reality, and mixed reality. However, there are some gaps that need further exploration:

- **Specific contexts:** While some studies focus on particular fields, like nursing or sustainable building design, more research is needed to understand how immersive technology can be tailored to a broader range of educational contexts and subject areas.
- **Long-term impact:** The existing literature mainly examines the immediate benefits and risks of using immersive technology. Further research should explore the long-term effects of these technologies on students' learning outcomes, engagement, and retention.
- **Integration with traditional methods:** Some studies touch upon the combination of high tech and low tech methods, but a deeper analysis is needed to determine the most effective ways to integrate immersive technology with traditional teaching practices.
- **Addressing risks and limitations:** The literature identifies several challenges, such as technological constraints, data accuracy concerns, and cognitive overload. More research is required to develop solutions that mitigate these risks while maximising the benefits of immersive technology.
- **Teacher training and support:** While some studies focus on pre-service teachers, more research is needed on how to best support in-service teachers in incorporating immersive technology into their teaching practices.

While there is a growing body of literature on gamification in education, there are still some gaps that need to be addressed. For example, there is a need for more research on the effectiveness of gamification in different educational contexts and for different types of learners. Additionally, there is a need for more practical guidance on how to design and implement gamification in a way that is aligned with

learning objectives and is not a distraction from the main content. Furthermore, there is a need for more research on the potential risks associated with gamification, such as the potential for disengagement if game elements are not well-designed, and the risk of reinforcing unhealthy gaming habits. To address these gaps, future research should focus on identifying the factors that influence the effectiveness of gamification in different educational contexts and on developing best practices for its implementation. Additionally, practical guidance on how to design and implement gamification in an effective and responsible way should be developed and disseminated to educators and educational institutions.

The current literature on computer science education highlights various challenges and approaches in different contexts. However, there are still some gaps that need to be addressed:

- Lack of comprehensive understanding: The term "computer science" remains poorly defined, causing confusion for students, parents, and the general public. More research is needed to clarify the scope and definition of computer science education.
- Diverse teaching methods: While some studies explore specific teaching methods, such as cooperative learning or problem-solving, a systematic comparison of various teaching approaches is missing. Further research could provide insights into the most effective methods for different learning contexts.
- Support for educators: Although some studies focus on teacher professional development, more research is needed on the best ways to support educators, including pre-service training, in-service training, and mentorship programs.
- Access and equity: Some literature addresses access to computer science education in K-12, but more research is needed to understand the barriers faced by different demographic groups, especially in terms of gender, socioeconomic status, and geographical location.
- Impact of technology: The role of technology in computer science education is not thoroughly explored, particularly how it affects student engagement, learning outcomes, and teaching methods.
- Evaluation of educational tools: While some studies mention the use of educational tools like serious games or Scalable Game Design, more research is needed to evaluate their effectiveness in teaching computer science concepts and skills.

While the research on computer science innovative teaching methods have made significant strides in exploring the potential of emerging technologies, there are still several gaps that need to be addressed in order to fully understand the benefits and challenges of implementing these technologies in educational settings. Based on the literature review for innovation in CS teaching, identified gaps in the current literature are:

- Limited empirical research: While some studies have explored the educational impact of VR and AR technologies, there remains a lack of empirical research comparing the effectiveness of different types of technologies and settings.
- Limited research on diverse student populations: Most of the existing research has focused on university students or middle school students, but there is a need to explore the effectiveness of these technologies for diverse student populations, including students from different socioeconomic backgrounds, cultures, and with different learning needs.
- Limited research on the long-term impact: Many of the existing studies have focused on short term learning outcomes, but there is a need to examine the long-term impact of these technologies on student learning and retention of knowledge.
- Limited research on ethical considerations: While some studies have identified ethical considerations related to the use of VR and AR technologies, there is a need for more research on the potential ethical implications of these technologies in educational settings.
- Limited research on implementation: While some studies have explored the effectiveness of these technologies, there is a need for more research on how to best implement these technologies in educational settings, including the necessary infrastructure, teacher training, and support for students.

There is a lack of empirical research comparing the educational impact of augmented reality and virtual reality technologies. There is also a need for alternative teaching methods in abstract fields such as computer science and STEM. Additionally, there is a limited understanding of the potential risks and negative effects of these technologies on students, such as VR sickness or desensitisation to violence or trauma. Lastly, there is a need for further research to identify the factors that influence students' behavioural intention when using VR training systems. These gaps highlight the need for more research and exploration in these areas to improve educational outcomes and enhance student learning experiences.

Delivering a learning outcome through this platform might offer creative computing students a better understanding of the fundamentals of programming by delivering it in an innovative way that allows learners to approach the subject through immersion that is not possible under traditional teaching methods . It could also provide experiences that are difficult or impossible to deliver in any other form. Despite the potential benefits there is a lack of evidence to support whether it is feasible, acceptable and effective within the context of computer science teaching.

4 Presentation of the Research Findings

This chapter presents the outcomes of three research studies conducted during the PhD programme driven by the findings of the Literature Review. The aim is to provide an overview of the research and to present the key findings of each study in a clear and concise manner.

The Literature Review explored immersive technologies, gamification, and innovative methods in computer science education. This discussion contextualises these findings within the broader academic landscape.

1. **Immersive Technologies in Education:** The review's focus on immersive technologies like VR and AR in education aligns with a significant body of academic research. These technologies have been heralded for their ability to create engaging, realistic environments that foster deeper learning (Brown et al., 1989). Pena-Rios et al. (2020) further reinforce this perspective, highlighting how immersive experiences can enhance spatial understanding and retention. Studies such as Bell et al. (2008) and Wu et al. (2021b) provide empirical evidence supporting the efficacy of VR in improving learning outcomes across various disciplines. This growing body of work indicates a shift towards more interactive, experiential learning methodologies in education.
2. **Gamification in Education:** The review's emphasis on gamification reflects a trend in educational research focusing on learner engagement and motivation. Huang et al. (2020) and Zhang et al. (2021) demonstrate that well-designed gamification strategies can significantly improve student motivation and engagement. However, as noted in the review, and echoed by Hung (2017) and Ofosu-Ampong (2020), the success of gamification in education depends heavily on its alignment with educational objectives and context. This balance between engagement and educational value is a critical consideration in implementing gamification effectively.
3. **Challenges in Computer Science Education:** Addressing challenges in CS education, the review sheds light on issues like curriculum integration and effective pedagogical approaches, reflecting concerns present in academic discourse. Sentance et al. (2013) and Malik et al. (2018) emphasise the need for innovative teaching methods to address the evolving nature of the field. Additionally, studies like Radenski (2006) and Falkner & Palmer (2009) support the review's call for novel educational strategies, suggesting that traditional teaching methods might not be sufficient for the dynamic and complex nature of CS.
4. **Emerging Technologies in CS Education:** The literature review's exploration of VR and AR as innovative tools in CS education is supported by academic studies highlighting their potential in enhancing understanding of complex concepts. Nersesian (2020) and Bourguet et al. (2020)

explore how these technologies can transform the learning experience by making abstract concepts more tangible and interactive. This is particularly pertinent in CS education, where conceptual understanding is key, and where traditional teaching methods may fall short in conveying complex, abstract concepts effectively.

The Literature Review's findings align well with current academic literature, providing a comprehensive understanding of the potential and challenges of using immersive technologies and gamification in education, particularly within the scope of computer science. These findings underscore the need for continued exploration and innovation in educational methodologies to keep pace with technological advancements and changing learner needs.

The research also emphasises the development and use of a VR game designed to teach programming fundamentals, addressing the need for alternative teaching methods in computer science and STEM fields. The study's findings show that while VR games may not replace traditional learning methods, they can be a fun and engaging way to learn programming concepts and skills.

By acknowledging the importance of further research, development, and practical guidelines, it tackles the identified gaps related to addressing risks and limitations, teacher training and support, and the evaluation of educational tools. Overall, this research connects with the research gaps by investigating the potential of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education and offering practical suggestions to enhance student learning experiences.

4.1 Research Paradigms & Methodology

This section will discuss the data collection, analysis and presentation methods used. Each research project used a different data collection method to gather information and a variety of data analysis methods to extract meaningful insights from the collected data and several techniques and tools used to present data. The following subsections will discuss the research paradigms and methods used in each project, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of each approach. By examining these we can gain a better understanding of how to conduct effective research in this field.

A research paradigm is a set of beliefs and practices that guide researchers in their pursuit of knowledge. Paradigms influence the research questions posed, the methods employed, and how results are interpreted.

The research methodology, outlining the various methods used to collect, analyse, and the results will also be presented. This is followed by a discussion of three research projects, Virtual Reality vs Pancake Environments, Systematic Review of Virtual Reality Applications for Education, and MoonBase VR: Learning to Program in a Virtual Reality Game. Each project is discussed in detail, including an introduction, the experiment undertaken and the findings of each study. The aim of this chapter is to present a comprehensive overview of the research findings, highlighting the key insights gained from each study and providing a broader context for understanding the implications of the research for the gamification of immersive technologies in computer science education.

4.1.1 Study 1: Virtual Reality vs Pancake Environments

The purpose of this study was to compare the effectiveness of learning in a virtual reality environment versus a traditional 2D “pancake” environment. The study utilised a mixed-methods approach to collect data from participants, consisting of both quantitative and qualitative data.

The first method used to collect data was a pre-test survey. The survey was designed to gather demographic information such as age, sex and previous experience with VR and programming, and assess the participants' knowledge and understanding of the programming concepts before and after the study. The survey questions were developed based on the learning objectives of the study.

The second method used was task based, where participants were asked to explore the 3D environment in both the VR and flat screen versions. This involved building a 3D virtual gallery for the participant to use in both flat screen and VR to undertake the study. The participants were given time to explore the virtual environment, while their progress was monitored and recorded by the researcher.

The third method used was a post-task survey and interview, where participants were asked to provide feedback on their experience completing the programming task in both environments. The interviews were conducted using a semi-structured approach, allowing the researcher to ask follow-up questions based on the participant's responses.

Overall, the mixed-methods approach used in this study allowed for a comprehensive collection of both quantitative and qualitative data, providing a more considered understanding of the effectiveness of VR compared to 2D environments.

The data analysis in this study involved statistical analysis of the results obtained from the participants' performance in virtual reality and pancake environments. This participant's movements were recorded within the software and saved. This was analysed by the researcher, extracting the time, location and movement of the participant. The pre-test measured the participants' initial knowledge of the topic, while the post-test and retention test measured the learning outcomes. The main advantage of using statistical analysis is that it provides objective and quantitative results that can be used to draw conclusions.

The results of the data analysis were presented in a clear and concise manner in the form of charts, graphs, and tables, making it easy for the reader to understand the findings. One of the strengths of this approach is that it allows for a quick and easy comparison of the data, which can be useful in identifying trends and patterns. However, one of the limitations of this approach is that it can sometimes oversimplify complex data, potentially leading to a loss of important information.

4.1.1.1 Research Paradigms

This study primarily engages with two paradigms: positivism and interpretivism. Positivism, with its emphasis on observable and measurable facts, is crucial in analyzing quantitative data from user interactions within VR and pancake environments. Interpretivism, on the other hand, aids in understanding the subjective experiences and perceptions of participants. These paradigms complement each other, offering a holistic view of the interactions in VR and traditional screen environments.

The chosen paradigms significantly influenced the research design. Positivism guided the quantitative analysis, leading to a more objective evaluation of user performance metrics. Interpretivism shaped the qualitative aspects, particularly the analysis of participants' feedback and experiences. This dual approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of user interactions in both environments.

4.1.1.2 Overview of Methodology

The methodology for this study is a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research. This approach aligns with the research paradigms and is particularly effective in exploring the multifaceted nature of user interactions in VR and pancake environments.

The research design is a comparative study that evaluates user interactions in VR and pancake environments. This design is suitable for highlighting the differences and similarities in user experiences and performance across these two platforms.

4.1.1.3 Participants

Participants were selected based on their familiarity with virtual environments and computer literacy. This selection criterion ensured that the data collected was relevant and informed by users who are representative of typical users in such environments.

4.1.1.4 Data Collection Methods

Data were collected through a combination of questionnaires, user interaction recordings, and observational techniques. These methods were chosen to capture both the objective performance metrics and the subjective experiences of the participants.

4.1.1.5 Research Ethics

Ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, were meticulously adhered to. Participants were fully briefed about the study's nature, and all data was anonymized to maintain confidentiality. Ethics application VR Gallery, submission 8089 was approved by the Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC in April 2019

4.1.1.6 Data Analysis

Data analysis involved statistical methods for the quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative data. This approach allowed for an in-depth exploration of both the measurable aspects of user interaction and the nuanced user experiences.

4.1.1.7 Limitations and Challenges

The study acknowledges limitations such as the sample size and the specific nature of the VR and pancake environments used. These limitations are important for contextualising the findings and understanding their applicability.

4.1.2 Study 2: Systematic Review of Virtual Reality Applications for Education

The purpose of this study was to conduct a systematic review of virtual reality applications in education. The study utilised a meta-analysis approach to collect and summarise data from existing applications.

The first method used to collect data was a comprehensive search of VR applications for education. Using multiple virtual reality curation platforms to search for relevant applications, using specific keywords and search criteria. The applications were then screened for relevance and were reviewed to determine their eligibility for inclusion in the study.

The second method used was a data extraction process, where extracted data from the selected applications, including design, learning theory, educational field, outcomes, and other relevant information. The extracted data were then examined to identify common themes and trends.

One potential limitation of this study is the potential for curation bias, as not all relevant applications may have been included in the review. Additionally, the quality of the included VR experiences may vary, which could affect the validity of the findings.

Overall, the systematic review approach used in this study allowed for a comprehensive analysis of existing applications for the use of VR in education. The use of multiple databases and search criteria increased the likelihood of identifying relevant applications and experiences, and the data extraction process allowed for a thorough analysis of the findings.

The data were analysed using a thematic approach, which involved identifying and analysing themes that emerged from the extracted data. The themes were then organised to provide an overview of the current state of virtual reality applications in education.

The main advantage of using a systematic review is that it provides a comprehensive and unbiased overview of the particular topic. The thematic analysis is appropriate for this study as it allows for the identification of patterns and trends. However, the limitations of this method are that it is time-consuming and requires a large amount of data to be analysed.

This data was presented via a collated database of all of the applications reviewed. The findings were organised thematically and presented in a way that provided a comprehensive overview of the research. The strengths of this approach include its ability to provide a detailed and nuanced analysis of the data. However, one of the limitations of this approach is that it can be time-consuming and difficult to navigate, potentially making it challenging for the reader to identify key findings.

4.1.2.1 Research Paradigms

The paradigms most pertinent to this review include constructivism, given its emphasis on learner-centered experiences, and pragmatism, which aligns with the practical applications of VR in educational settings. Constructivism underscores how VR can facilitate experiential learning, while pragmatism guides the review's focus on practical outcomes and applications in real-world educational settings.

The choice of these paradigms influences both the scope of the review and its methodological approach. Constructivism informs the analysis of how VR facilitates learning, while pragmatism shapes the review's focus on practical, actionable insights drawn from the analysed studies.

4.1.2.2 Methodologies and Methods

The review adopts a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative analyses. This approach is ideal for systematically examining the diverse range of VR applications in education, capturing both statistical trends and nuanced educational experiences.

The review follows a structured approach typical of systematic reviews, involving rigorous data collection from various databases and journals, followed by critical analysis. The selection criteria for studies are clearly defined, ensuring a comprehensive and unbiased examination of the available literature.

4.1.2.3 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations in this review include ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the sourced material and maintaining the objectivity of the analysis. These considerations are fundamental in upholding the integrity of the systematic review process. No ethics application was made (or needed) for this study.

4.1.2.4 Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis involves a combination of statistical evaluation of data from quantitative studies and thematic analysis of qualitative studies. This dual approach allows for a holistic understanding of VR's impact in educational contexts.

4.1.2.5 Limitations and Challenges

The review acknowledges potential limitations, such as the variability in the quality of the reviewed studies and the rapid evolution of VR technology, which might impact the generalisability and currency of the findings.

4.1.3 Study 3: MoonBase VR: Learning to Program in a Virtual Reality Game

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of a virtual reality game called MoonBase VR for teaching programming concepts. The study utilised a mixed-methods approach to collect data from participants, consisting of both quantitative and qualitative data.

The first method used to collect data was a pre- and post-test survey. The survey was designed to gather demographic information before and after playing the game. The survey questions were developed based on the learning objectives of the game. Participants were asked about their level of experience with VR, programming, and educational games. The survey also included questions related to the comfort level of the VR equipment used during the game, the ease of use of the movement options available in the game, the appearance and usefulness of the programming blocks used in the game, and the level of difficulty of the game. The participants were asked to rate their responses on a five-level Likert scale.

The survey questions were carefully designed to align with the learning objectives of the game and provide useful data on participants' experiences and perceptions. One limitation of the survey method is that it relies on self-reported data, which can be subject to biases and inaccuracies. Participants may

be reluctant to report negative experiences and feelings or may overstate their level of experience or understanding. Additionally, the survey questions may not capture all relevant information or perspectives.

The data analysis in this study involved the analysis of the results obtained from the pre-experience and post-experience surveys. The data was collected through a survey that was developed based on the learning objectives of the game. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics, which involved summarising the data using measures of central tendency and variability. The data was presented using tables and graphs.

The main advantage of using descriptive statistics is that it provides a clear and concise summary of the data. The use of tables and graphs is appropriate for this study as it allows for the visualisation of the data. However, the limitations of this method are that it does not provide insights into why the participants responded in a particular way. Additionally, the data may be influenced by response bias, where participants provide socially desirable responses.

The data was presented in the form of tables and charts. The results of the study were organised thematically and presented in a clear and concise manner. One of the strengths of this approach is that it allows for a quick and easy comparison of the data, making it easy to identify patterns and trends. However, one of the limitations of this approach is that it can sometimes oversimplify complex data, potentially leading to a loss of important information.

4.1.3.1 Research Paradigms

Constructivism plays a key role, emphasising learning through interactive, immersive environments. Pragmatism is also evident, focusing on practical outcomes of VR in learning, such as improved engagement and understanding of programming concepts. The selection of constructivism and pragmatism directly influences the study's approach, focusing on how VR facilitates experiential learning and the practical application of programming skills in a VR environment.

4.1.3.2 Methodologies and Methods

The study employs a mixed-methods approach, appropriate for exploring both the quantitative and qualitative impacts of VR in programming education. The design incorporates both experimental and observational methods. Participants interact with the VR programming game, and data is collected through questionnaires and direct observation of their engagement and learning progress.

4.1.3.3 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are addressed, particularly regarding participant consent and the responsible handling of data. Ethics application 13315: Code Blocks in VR, submission 11714 was approved by the Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC in November 2020

4.1.3.4 *Data Analysis Techniques*

Both statistical analysis for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative responses are used, providing a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of VR in programming education.

4.1.3.5 *Limitations and Challenges*

The paper acknowledges the limitations in terms of participant selection and the specificity of the VR environment used, which may impact the generalizability of the findings.

4.1.4 Summary

In the realm of virtual reality (VR) research, as exemplified by the studies on VR versus pancake environments, VR applications in education, and the MoonBase VR game, the use of a mixed methods approach is crucial. This approach, blending quantitative and qualitative methodologies, is vital due to the multifaceted nature of VR technology. Quantitative data in these studies provides objective, measurable outcomes, such as user performance metrics in VR environments. In contrast, qualitative data offers a deeper understanding of user experiences, perceptions, and interactions within these virtual spaces.

For instance, while the study on VR versus pancake environments quantitatively assessed user interaction differences, it was the qualitative insights that illuminated user preferences and experiences in these differing contexts. Similarly, the systematic review on VR applications in education and the study of the MoonBase VR game heavily relied on qualitative data to grasp the nuanced impacts of VR on learning and engagement. This integration of diverse data types not only enriches the analysis but also validates the findings, offering a well-rounded perspective that is essential for understanding the complex dynamics of VR in various settings. The synergy between quantitative and qualitative methods in these studies underlines the importance of a mixed-methods approach in VR research, ensuring comprehensive insights and a more complete understanding of this evolving field.

Overall, the methods used in these studies were appropriate for their research questions and provided valuable insights into the use of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education.

The data collection methods used in the three projects were thorough and aimed to capture a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences and perceptions. In the Virtual Reality vs Pancake Environments study, a mixed-methods approach was employed, combining qualitative feedback with quantitative metrics, such as task completion time and accuracy. In the Systematic Review of Virtual Reality Applications for Education, a rigorous search strategy was used to identify relevant studies, and a predefined set of inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to ensure only relevant applications were included. In the MoonBase VR study, a combination of pre- and post-

experience surveys, as well as gameplay data, were collected to understand the participants' perceptions and experiences with the game.

The data analysis methods used in the three research studies vary depending on the research questions and the type of data collected. The use of statistical analysis is appropriate when comparing learning outcomes between different environments, while a systematic review is suitable for providing an overview of the literature. Descriptive statistics are appropriate for summarising survey data. The presentation of data is an important aspect of any research study, as it allows the researcher to effectively communicate their findings to the audience. Different methods may be more appropriate depending on the nature of the data and the research question being addressed. It is important for researchers to carefully consider their options and select the method that is best suited to their specific needs.

5 STUDY 1: Virtual Reality vs Pancake Environments

(Holder, Carey and Keir, 2020)

With its ability to simulate three-dimensional environments and provide users with a sense of presence, VR has the potential to transform the way we interact with digital content and each other. However, as with any emerging technology, there are still many questions and concerns surrounding the use of VR, particularly when compared to traditional "pancake" 2D environments.

This project aimed to explore the advantages and disadvantages of VR environments compared to pancake environments. Hoping to provide a comprehensive analysis of the factors that influence user experience in both types of environments. Also discussing the implications of these findings for the development of immersive platforms used in virtual reality.

One of the main advantages of VR environments is their ability to create a sense of presence in the user (Kateros, Georgiou, et al., 2015), which is the feeling of being fully immersed in a virtual world. This feeling is often described as being "transported" to another place and can be a powerful tool for creating engaging and memorable experiences. In contrast, pancake environments are limited in their ability to create this sense of presence, as users are typically viewing content on a flat, two-dimensional screen. However, the level of presence experienced in VR environments can vary depending on a number of factors. For example, this research has shown that the level of immersion can be influenced by the quality of the graphics, the level of interactivity, and the presence of distractions or interruptions. Additionally, some users may experience discomfort or motion sickness when using VR, which can negatively impact their overall experience.

Another potential advantage of VR environments is their ability to provide users with a greater sense of agency and control (Slater and Sanchez-Vives, 2016). In a virtual environment, users can interact with objects and manipulate their surroundings in ways that are not possible in a pancake environment. This can be particularly useful in fields such as education and training, where users may need to practice complex tasks or procedures in a safe and controlled environment. However, some researchers have argued that the use of VR environments in these contexts may not always lead to better learning outcomes (Chittaro and Buttussi, 2015). For example, one study found that adding immersive VR to a science lab simulation actually led to less learning compared to a traditional pancake environment (Makransky, Terkildsen and Mayer, 2017). This highlights the importance of carefully considering the specific context and goals of a given immersive experience before deciding whether VR is the best option.

Another potential disadvantage of VR environments is their cost and technical requirements. Creating a high-quality VR experience typically requires specialised hardware and software, which can be expensive and difficult to develop (Moro, Štromberga and Stirling, 2017). Additionally, VR

environments may not be accessible to all users (Lindsay, 2007), as they require certain physical abilities (such as the ability to stand or move around) and can be uncomfortable or disorienting for some users. In contrast, pancake environments are typically much more accessible and easy to use, as they require only a standard computer or mobile device (Makransky, Terkildsen and Mayer, 2017). This can make them a more practical option for many applications, particularly those with limited budgets or resources.

The analysis presented in this study will have implications for the development of immersive platforms and applications. By gaining a better understanding of the factors that contribute to the user experience in VR and pancake environments, developers will be better equipped to design interfaces that maximise user engagement and immersion. Additionally, this analysis will help to inform the ongoing debate about the relative merits of VR and pancake environments and provide a more nuanced understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of each type of interface.

5.1.1 The 3D Environment

One of the key challenges is the design of the 3D virtual environment itself. In traditional 2D interfaces, the user is presented with a flat-screen, and the interaction takes place within that frame. In VR, the environment is three-dimensional, and the user can move around within it. This presents a range of design challenges (Aguayo, 2021), such as creating a sense of spatial orientation, providing visual cues to guide the user, and ensuring that the user does not become disoriented or overwhelmed. To address these challenges, designers of VR systems must employ best practices for creating 3D virtual environments. This may include using realistic graphics and textures, incorporating interactive elements that respond to user input, and providing feedback mechanisms to help the user understand their location and orientation within the environment. Additionally, designers must consider factors such as lighting, sound, and the use of haptic feedback to enhance the user's sense of immersion.

The application used in this study is a bespoke 3D virtual environment built using the Unreal Engine 4 game engine that allows a user to explore and interact using either VR or a flat screen, it has been intentionally designed with visual simplicity. The absence of an elaborate textured environment allows the experience to run at a high frame rate without encountering drops in framerate. Furthermore, the minimalist environment helps participants maintain focus on the task presented, preventing them from getting distracted by the "wow" factor of virtual reality experiences. This distraction could potentially skew the study results.

Upon launching the experience in both the flat screen and VR modes, users are presented with a user interface (UI) containing icons and text descriptions of the control system, as shown in Figure 5-1 below. This includes information on how to move and the corresponding actions for each button. In VR

mode, the UI is attached to the right controller and can be turned on and off using a button on that controller. In case users need to access the instructions again, a permanent notice detailing how to pull up the UI is placed in the user's field of view in a head-up display. In the flat-screen application, the UI is displayed as a HUD-style element, which is permanently shown but fades away when the user starts to interact with the 3D scene. If the user hovers the mouse over the faded element, the UI can be brought back up again. One additional feature included in the interaction design is the ability to disable texturing, which allows users to see the wireframe of the models' underlying geometry. This feature was included as the majority of participants in the study were students in the creative computing department.

Figure 5-1 Desktop UI (left) Virtual Reality UI (right)

In the virtual environment, four models have been placed on plinths encircling the user, with each model placed at equal distances from the user's starting position. The models include a non-human biped character model, a motorcycle, a robot, and a rifle, as depicted in Figure 5-2 below. The plinths that models sit on are translucent and are approximately one Unreal Engine unit in height, equivalent to one meter in real-world measurements. A simple floor with a grid pattern is provided, and post-processing fog has been implemented to prevent users from viewing beyond ten units (ten meters).

Figure 5-2 Models presented in the virtual environment

In the virtual reality experience, participants can navigate the environment by physically moving around the play space or using a teleportation system triggered by the user pressing and releasing a button on the left-hand controller. On the flat screen system, movement is executed using the mouse: double-clicking on a model moves the user's camera closer to the model's position, which can then be orbited by moving the mouse. The right-hand controller is equipped with a laser pointer, which users can aim at the models and depress the trigger to pick up a model in VR. Once lifted, the model can be moved

freely on any axis. On the flat screen, users can move a model in any linear axis, including up, down, left, right, back, and forth, and rotate it by depressing the right mouse button with the cursor over the model and moving the mouse in the corresponding direction.

5.1.2 Methodology

Methodology for testing VR systems is also an important consideration. Traditional methods for user testing may not be applicable to VR (Simões, Redondo and Vilas, 2013), as the immersive experience can be significantly different from that of a 2D interface. For example, developers may need to consider factors such as motion sickness (Hanson, Andersen and Dunn, 2019), which can occur when the user's physical movement is out of sync with their virtual movement. One approach to testing VR systems is through playtesting, which involves observing and analysing user behaviour in a controlled environment. This can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the VR system and help designers identify areas for improvement. However, care must be taken to ensure that the playtesting environment is representative of the intended use case and that users are given clear instructions and goals to guide their interaction with the environment. In addition to playtesting, other methods for evaluating VR systems include physiological measurements (Weidner *et al.*, 2017), such as heart rate and skin conductance, as well as self-report measures, such as questionnaires and surveys. These methods can provide valuable data on user experience and satisfaction, as well as help researchers identify potential areas for improvement.

For this study a 3D virtual gallery with four computer-generated models sitting on plinths is presented to the participant to explore in two forms: a computer screen using a keyboard and mouse; and also a virtual reality HMD and controllers.

Half of the test subjects explored the screen interface first, then the virtual reality interface. The other half explored the environment using the virtual reality interface first, and then the screen interface. Participants used the VR headset and controllers to explore the gallery of 3D models; produced by students from an undergraduate animation degree course. In the virtual environment, the user can walk around the play space; teleport to different locations using the controllers; as well as pick up, move and rotate the models as shown in Figure 5-3 below.

Figure 5-3 A Participant using room-scale (left) and a participant using teleportation (right)

The same virtual gallery was presented on the flat screen experience. The user can move around the play space using the mouse to orbit the viewpoint around each model. A double mouse clicks will move between models; a single click will grab and move them.

For both modalities, interaction data was recorded using virtual estimation software that records the user's movement, allowing the recreation of these movements in a game engine. A comparison between the participants' movement data for both interactions was also made side by side using laboratory-controlled analysis.

After the participants experienced both interfaces, they were asked to complete a survey consisting of comparison scale questions and qualitative questions.

5.1.3 Findings

From the questionnaires, the 31 participants filled out before and after the two experiences, data was compiled into spreadsheets for analysis.

5.1.3.1 Questionnaire Results

A large percentage of participants had used a virtual reality headset prior to this study with 64.5% of them having previous experience in a VR platform as seen in Figure 5-4 below. In spite of this, 51.6% of the participants classified themselves as beginners, according to Figure 5-5 below.

Figure 5-4 Have you used Virtual Reality prior to this study?

Figure 5-5 What best describes your VR experience level?

More people found using the VR system very easy compared to the desktop system with 19.4% versus 9.7%. Based on a rating system of 1 to 5, with 1 being easy and 5 being difficult, more people gave a 2 rating for navigating the VR system: 41.9% versus 32.3% for the desktop. Only 1 person found both systems difficult. When asked a question about if they thought that VR gave a better experience than the flat screen interface, 58.1% of the participants thought that it did; 22.6% disagreed and 19.4% were unsure. After undertaking both experiences a large majority of users preferred the VR system over the desktop with 80% versus 20% of all participants liking virtual reality more.

The participants were asked three questions regarding their thoughts on both experiences immediately after the playtests. The questions and some of the responses are presented here.

• *Question 1: Based on your previous answer (Which system did you prefer?) what did you like most about the system?*

- “I could bring the model right next to my face and look at it from very specific angles” (VR)
- “Use of the mouse provides better control” (Desktop)
- “VR allowed for better object movement to inspect small details that would be hard to check using the desktop version”
- “I could look around and walk closer to the objects in order to see them better” (VR)
- “The way that you could interact. It was fun” (VR)
- “It's easy to leave and I can take my time” (Desktop)
- “Easy ability to manipulate VR objects” (VR)

• *Question 2: What did you dislike, if anything, about the other system?*

- “In the desktop, you are not present in the environment” (Desktop)
 - “Visuals not as clear which made it difficult to appreciate” (VR)
 - “How simple and easy it was, it wasn't fun” (Desktop)
 - “I have to be very careful with the system and myself and can't relax and really properly look at the models” (VR)
- *Question 3: What suggestions or ideas do you have for improving the system? (Desktop and/or VR)*
- “Have a cinematic resolution for VR so textures can be more clearly seen”
 - “Desktop has no/little sense of scale”

5.1.3.2 Interaction Results

Based on the average time spent in each experience, virtual reality users spent nearly 10% more time in VR (average 3 mins 10 secs) than they did with the flat screen (average 2 mins 9 secs). VR experiences took the longest time to complete with a total of 7.38 minutes, while flat-screen 3D experiences took the shortest time with 1.51 minutes. There is a difference between the model that is looked at for the longest amount of time in VR and on the desktop. The most popular VR model was model 3 (the robot). Model 1 (the character model) has a slight advantage over Model 3 within the desktop environment. In Figure 5-6 below, the average time spent looking at the models is arranged from high to low:

Figure 5-6 Time spent looking at the model

VR	Model 3 (Robot) 57 seconds	Model 4 (Rifle) 51 seconds	Model 1 (Character) 48 seconds	Model 2 (Motorbike) 39 seconds.
Desktop	Model 1 (Character) 39 seconds	Model 3 (Robot) 37 seconds	Model 4 (Rifle) 31 seconds	Model 2 (Motorbike) 26 seconds.

Examining the effect of the way participants were spawned into the game on which model was interacted with first we find on the desktop, 56% of users went to Model 1 (Character) first, while 67% of users on VR went to this model first. Each participant in both experiences was spawned in the same

location, looking in the same direction. Models 1 & 2 were to the left, 3 & 4 were to the right, and initially obscured. Within VR, however, participants could easily look around, and we observed some users looking in all directions around the environment as soon as they put on the HMD, but returning to the direction they initially faced once they settled in.

In Figure 5-7 below, you can see how participants interacted with the models in each environment. In VR, all of them picked up all four models; on the desktop, this trend wasn't carried over with an average of only 2.4 users picking up a model.

Figure 5-7 Did the participant pick up the model?

Figure 5-8 below illustrates the statistics on the participant's interactions with the models and whether they looked closer at a model within the virtual reality experience. It could have been the participant leaning in to look closer at the model by moving within the VR's room-scale space (VR/RS) or by picking up the model and bringing it closer to their face (VR/PU). This would be accomplished by zooming in on the model in the desktop environment (SCR).

Figure 5-8 Did the participant get a closer look at the model?

The participants in VR spent a great deal of time examining Models 1 (Character) and 4 (Rifle). Using the pickup (VR/PU) method, only one person did not examine Model 2 (Motorcycle) closer and two people did not examine Model 3 (Robot) closer by picking it up (VR/PU). Model 3 (Robot) is the most looked at model with 19 people moving closer to view this model. The split between physical movement (VR/RS) in room scale is more even, with 19 people moving closer to view the model 3, but we see all the models had more participants moving closer to them. An average of 26 participants zoomed in to

take a closer look at the models in the desktop experience. There were 28 participants who looked at Model 3 (Robot) in detail, which was the most looked-at item in this category.

While in VR participants could either physically walk around the scene or use the controls provided by the app to 'teleport' around the scene. In the testing play space, the participants were able to physically walk around each model placed on the virtual plinths as well as between models. Based on the way participants moved around the virtual space, we see that approximately two-thirds of users used teleportation only for movement. 34% of participants explored the virtual space by teleporting and moving at room-scale.

5.1.4 Data Analysis

Most users found it easy to navigate around in the VR experience. Compared to the desktop, this level of ease was similar. Despite their unfamiliarity with VR movement, most users were able to adapt to it without much difficulty. A VR system might have given these participants an opportunity to explore a virtual environment in a novel way, which has been shown to have a positive effect on learning a new task (Kateros, Georgiou et al., 2015). There may be a sense of awe in exploring the virtual world with VR equipment and with more exposure to VR, this might balance out.

Taking note of the answers that the participant gave on the questionnaire. In general, VR offered a more intuitive way to interact with the environment, although some found it less comfortable, and it did not provide the same level of visual quality as desktop. This could be a result of the difference in screen resolutions, the VR system (1440 x 1440 pixel) does not have the same display properties as the desktop (1920 x 1080 pixels).

The results of the participants spending longer in the VR experience could be due to settling into VR, for example, by looking around; watching how their hands follow the controllers in the virtual world. In looking at the details of how much time the users spent looking at each model, we see a similar result of a higher time. So, this may back up the subjective data from the questionnaire, and participants enjoyed viewing the models in VR more than they did on their desktops.

As soon as the player is spawned in the virtual world, Model 1 will be visible to the left of the player. The left-to-right reading pattern of European languages suggests our attention is drawn to things on the left of our vision first in the Western world (Chokron and Imbert, 1993). In different cultures, this might be observed differently.

Our analysis of the data collected on whether participants picked up the models for inspection examined whether the VR experience enhanced their exploration of the environment. It was found that participants

were more engaged with the models in the VR environment, both picking them up and bringing them closer so they could see them better, as well as moving closer to see them in person.

The most common movement system was teleportation; this may have been influenced by being taught how to use the VR system during the pre-briefing. Therefore, prejudice their movement abilities before starting the experience. Furthermore, this method is used by most people for several reasons, including (i) They don't feel safe walking around in the real world while they can only see the virtual world; (ii) They aren't truly immersed. The user will certainly be reminded of that when they are holding a controller. Although nearly a third of the participants were aware of the teleportation system, they felt comfortable roaming as they would in real life, even though they were aware of it.

5.1.5 Conclusion

One of the key findings of the study was that participants reported feeling more engaged and immersed in the 3D virtual environment than in the pancake environment. Virtual reality technology is likely to facilitate this increase through a sense of presence. In the study, participants felt more engaged and performed better in the virtual environment because they felt more present. As a result of these findings, it appears that VR may be a more effective learning tool for schools and classrooms than traditional pancake 3D environments. The study also identified some limitations and challenges associated with the use of 3D virtual environments. For instance, VR has been reported to cause discomfort or motion sickness in some participants. Additionally, setting up and maintaining the virtual reality equipment presented some technical challenges.

Although this virtual reality experience has shown promising results, further research is necessary to draw definitive conclusions. We are likely to see even more widespread adoption of virtual reality technology in the years to come as virtual reality technology develops and improves. Therefore, in order to develop immersive platforms that enhance the user's experience, it is vital to examine the impact of the interface design. Also, when considering whether to implement this technology in a given setting, it's important to take into account the limitations and challenges it may pose. To fully explore the potential of VR and identify best practices for its use in different educational and training contexts, further research is required.

6 STUDY 2: A Systematic Review of Virtual Reality Applications for Education

The potential benefits of VR in education are numerous. VR can provide an immersive and engaging learning experience, which has been shown to improve knowledge retention and recall (Clark, Tanner-Smith and Killingsworth, 2016; Mayer, 2017). It can also provide a safe and controlled environment for learning practical skills, such as surgical procedures or emergency response training (Lee, 2004). In addition, VR can enable students to interact with abstract concepts in a more tangible and visual way, which can enhance their understanding of complex ideas (Kozhevnikov, Motes and Hegarty, 2007). Moreover, VR can provide a flexible and personalised learning environment, allowing students to learn at their own pace and in their own style (Slater, 2009).

However, the use of VR in education also presents challenges and limitations. VR technology can be expensive, requiring specialist equipment and software, which may not be accessible to all students (Milgram and Kishino, 1994). The use of VR may also require additional time and resources for development and implementation, which may not be available in all educational settings (Vorderer, Klimmt and Ritterfeld, 2004). Moreover, VR applications may require a certain level of technical proficiency, which may pose a challenge for some users.

To fully understand the current state of VR applications for education, a systematic review was conducted using a predefined methodology. The research methods used involved compiling a list of 342 educational VR titles available through Viveport, Steam, Oculus (Meta) game distribution platforms, and other sources. From this list, 307 VR applications were selected using an automatic and manual filtering process. The applications were then classified based on a learning theory framework, learning content categories, and application design elements.

- The learning theory framework consisted of seven categories: behavioural learning, experiential learning, generative learning, operational learning, game-based learning, contextual learning, and Jeffries simulation theory.
- The learning content categories were analytical and problem-solving, communication, collaboration, soft skills, procedural-practical knowledge, declarative knowledge, learning a language, behavioural impacts, and others.
- The application design elements were categorized based on their presence or absence in each application and included features such as realistic surroundings, basic interaction with objects, passive observation, and moving around.

The VR applications were then played in virtual reality by the author over a period of 6 months and tested using a desktop-based personal computer with a connected 6DOF virtual reality headset and controllers. Several of the application found didn't work at this point and were eliminated from the results. The data gathered from this systematic review allowed for a comprehensive comparison of the level and quality available on each platform.

The results of the review provide insights into the current trends and characteristics of VR applications in education. These applications covered a wide range of subjects, including science, history, art, and language learning. The selected applications were then analysed, and data were extracted on various aspects, including the subject area, gameplay style, learning theories, learning content, and design elements of the applications. The extracted data was collated into a database with open access to the general public, for this study the data was also presented in the form of tables and figures to identify trends and patterns.

Overall, this research method provided a structured approach to analysing the VR applications available for educational purposes. Classifying the applications based on learning theory, content, and design elements, allowed for a clear understanding of the different features and learning outcomes of each application. This comprehensive approach can be useful for educators and developers to identify which VR applications are most suitable for their learning objectives.

6.1.1 Results

The number of applications published each year between 2016 and 2020 was evenly spread, with the lowest number of applications released in 2016 and the highest in 2018. The results show that the number of single-player experiences is significantly higher than that of multiplayer equivalents (Figure 6-1), while most of the applications tested are suitable for all age ranges (Figure 6-2). Applications also provide different gameplay styles, such as seated, standing, or room-scale, and the majority of the applications allow the user to learn through a 'hands-on' experience (Figure 6-3).

Figure 6-1 Single-player and Multiplayer experiences

Figure 6-2 Age range rating of the application

Figure 6-3 Gameplay type

In Figure 6-4 the results indicate that VR applications were most frequently used to deliver declarative knowledge, while language learning was the least covered learning content in the applications surveyed. Analytical and problem-solving and behavioural impact have a similar number of applications delivering this content, with procedural-practical knowledge following closely behind.

Figure 6-4 Learning content

The study examined the learning theories (Figure 6-5) and principles used in the applications. The data showed that the applications tested presented a wide variety of learning theories, with the largest number being categorized as experiential learning (84.7%).

Figure 6-5 Learning Theory

The design elements of VR applications were also analysed (Figure 6-6), with the most common elements being realistic surroundings and basic interaction, it can be concluded that these are the core design requirements for educational VR applications.

Figure 6-6 Design Elements

The Venn diagram presented in Figure 6-7 shows how the four leading design elements overlap between the applications. The largest crossover can be found between moving around and basic interaction with objects, and many applications also share design elements such as realistic surroundings and basic interaction with objects. Only a small number of applications include passive observation, basic interaction, and basic interaction with objects together.

Figure 6-7 Overlapped design elements Venn diagram

The study found that the largest number of applications (33.9%) were categorised as delivering learning within the science subject area (Figure 6-4). Applications within the science discipline were further broken down in Figure 6-9, revealing a wide variety of science categories covered by the VR

applications, including earth science, biology, physics, chemistry, and environmental science, among others. The data presented in the study shows that there are a significant number of VR applications available that offer a fun and engaging way to teach science concepts and theories, making learning more interactive and immersive for students. It is important to note that some applications cover more than one subject area, and in some cases, a single exhibit in a virtual museum application can encompass subjects such as art and history.

Figure 6-8 Subject Area

Figure 6-9 Science category breakdown

The study also found that most of the applications were designed to cater to a wide age range (Figure 6-10), with the majority being suitable for all ages (84.7%). The number of single-player experiences (93.2%) was higher than that of multiplayer equivalents, which is likely due to the cost of developing multiplayer applications.

Figure 6-10 Age range rating of the application

6.1.2 Conclusion

A systematic review of VR applications for educational purposes was conducted, examining learning theory, content, and design elements. The study found that there is a wide variety of applications and games that cover a broad range of subjects and age ranges and deliver core learning outcomes to students in a novel and exciting way. However, VR for education is still in an experimental stage, capable of offering a fun way to present a subject to students, but not ready to be included in a curriculum in a meaningful way.

The study found that the majority of the applications tested were aimed at all ages, with only a small percentage catering to specific age ranges. Furthermore, most of the applications were single-player experiences, with only a small number of multiplayer equivalents. The data also showed that there is little difference in popularity between the three gameplay types, with standing gameplay being the largest number of applications.

The educational field targeted by each application was also analysed, with science being the largest overall category. VR applications were most frequently used to deliver declarative knowledge, with language learning being the least covered learning content in the applications surveyed. Basic interaction with objects in the virtual space was also represented highly in the testing, allowing a user to interact with objects and provide an increased feeling of immersion. This is a crucial aspect of VR technology, but it is still in its infancy, and there is still ambiguity surrounding what should be understood by the term. By its nature, VR is immersive, but the wearing of a heavy headset and holding controllers can still remind a user that they are in a fake representation of a world. Thus, technological developments such as haptic feedback, field of view, and screen resolution are necessary to improve immersion.

The study examined the learning theories being used in these applications, with the largest amount being categorized as experiential learning. However, none of the applications claims to implement a specific learning theory. The data shows that VR applications that aim to improve declarative knowledge can be a way to bring VR to an educational setting as this area is widely covered in the applications tested. The study also found that the realistic surroundings and basic interaction with object design elements occur in the largest section of VR applications in the sample. Thus, they can be seen as the core design requirements for educational VR applications. However, the study found limited results concerning VR aimed at improving communication, collaboration, soft skills, behavioural impacts, and analytical skills to be able to derive recommendations for the most useful design elements that will meet specific learning goals.

In conclusion, the study provides a generalisation of trends found in VR educational applications, but it is possibly only a small representation of all VR applications and games that may be used to provide an educational experience. VR for education is still in an experimental stage, but it offers a fun way to present a subject to students. Thus, it is important to continue collecting, receiving, and curating data on current and future VR applications for use in education. The survey form that collects the data and collated data spreadsheet has been made available to the general public to add to and build a larger database of these applications that will maintain currency as the sector grows.

Overall, this systematic review provides valuable insight into the current state of VR applications for education and serves as a starting point for future research in this area.

7 STUDY 3: MoonBase VR: Learning to Program in a Virtual Reality Game

Computer programming is a fundamental skill for students entering the workforce in the 21st century (Chiruguru, 2020). With an increasing demand for computer programmers across industries, it has become crucial for educational institutions to provide their students with the necessary skills to succeed in a technology-driven world. However, teaching programming concepts to students can be a challenging task, particularly for those who may not have any prior experience in coding (Garcia, Falkner and Vivian, 2018). As such, researchers and educators have been exploring alternative approaches to teaching programming, including the use of virtual reality (VR) technology (Burdea and Coiffet, 2003).

The use of VR technology in education has been gaining popularity in recent years. Research has shown that VR can provide an immersive and engaging learning experience that promotes knowledge retention and enhances learning outcomes (Gavish *et al.*, 2011). VR technology can also provide students with a safe and controlled environment to explore and learn without the risks associated with real-world scenarios (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). One such application of VR technology in education is MoonBase VR, a game that teaches programming concepts to students. MoonBase VR is a virtual reality game that allows players to build and program robots to perform tasks on a lunar base. The study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of using a VR programming game for learning computer programming concepts. The research questions guiding this study were:

- how usable is manipulating code blocks within a virtual reality game to build computer programs effectively?
- what are participants' perceptions of using a VR game to learn to program?

The objective of this study was to evaluate the usability of manipulating code blocks within a virtual reality game to build computer programs effectively and examine the participants' perceptions of using a VR game to learn programming. The study involved 40 participants who completed a pre-experience questionnaire, played Moonbase VR, and completed a post-experience questionnaire and a NASA-TLX survey to assess workload. The findings showed that a large majority of participants felt that using a VR game offered a fun and engaging way to learn to program and increased their interest in this part of computer science. These results suggest that VR has the potential to enhance computer science education and inspire the future development of VR programming applications.

7.1.1 Advantages and Limitations of Using VR Technology in Education

The use of VR technology in education has several advantages. VR can provide students with an immersive and engaging learning experience that promotes knowledge retention and enhances learning outcomes (Gavish *et al.*, 2011). VR technology can also provide students with a safe and controlled environment to explore and learn without the risks associated with real-world scenarios (Stavroulia *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, VR can enable students to visualise complex concepts and ideas in ways that may not be possible using traditional teaching methods (Hanson, Andersen and Dunn, 2019). However, the use of VR technology in education also has some constraints with one significant limitation being the cost of VR equipment, which can be prohibitive for some schools and educational institutions. Additionally, the technology required to support VR can be complex and may require specialised knowledge and expertise to operate and maintain (Abriata, 2020). Finally, the use of VR technology may not be suitable for all types of learning objectives or subject areas, as some concepts may be better taught using traditional teaching methods (Alwedaie *et al.*, 2018).

7.1.2 Overview of MoonBase VR

MoonBase VR is a virtual reality game that allows players to build code to program robots to perform tasks on a lunar base. The game employs a block-based coding interface that enables players to create code using drag-and-drop code blocks. The game also incorporates puzzles that require players to apply programming concepts to solve challenges. MoonBase VR was developed specifically for this study.

The application is available for PCVR platforms, including Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, and Windows Mixed Reality. The game is a single-player campaign where the player progress through a series of levels, 10 in total, each with its own set of challenges and puzzles. The game's coding interface takes inspiration from popular 2D visual scripting platforms such as Scratch (*Scratch - Imagine, Program, Share*) with a drag-and-drop system that allows players to create code by selecting and arranging code blocks. In this application the code blocks a 3D object the player can hold and 'snap' together. The code blocks represent programming concepts, such as loops, conditions, and variables. The game provides a unique immersive experience that enables students to learn programming concepts in a way that is engaging, interactive, and fun. This project aims to explore the effectiveness of MoonBase VR as a tool for teaching programming concepts to students.

Figure 7-1 MoonBase VR title graphic

7.1.3 Programming

The study begins with an overview of the importance of teaching programming skills to students. Discussing the role that programming plays in our society and the growing demand for workers with programming expertise. Also exploring the challenges that teachers face when teaching programming to students and the limitations of traditional teaching methods.

Programming skills have become increasingly important in today's digital age. From developing software to building websites and mobile applications, programming skills are in high demand in virtually all industries. One of the key benefits of teaching programming skills is that it helps to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Harangus and Kátai, 2020). Programming requires students to think logically and systematically, breaking down complex problems into smaller, more manageable tasks. By learning how to code, students can develop the ability to approach problems in a methodical and structured way, a skill that can be applied in a wide range of contexts. In addition, learning to program can also foster creativity and innovation (Apiola, Lattu and Pasanen, 2012). As students gain proficiency in programming, they are able to use their skills to create their own software applications, websites, and games (Judd, 2018). Overall, the importance of teaching programming skills cannot be overstated.

The use of visual programming environments is a popular way to introduce young people to the world of programming and computer science. Scratch, Kodable, Roblox Coding, Code.org, and LightBot are all examples of visual programming applications that are widely used in educational institutions (Meerbaum-Salant, Armoni and Ben-Ari, 2013). Scratch, in particular, is a visual programming platform designed for children aged 8 to 16. It allows them to work on personal expressive projects while learning to code. The platform also promotes self-directed learning through exploration and cooperation with others. Scratchers, users of Scratch, are encouraged to upload their projects to the site, with source code freely available for sharing and remixing. The assortment of projects on Scratch is vast and varied, including video games, interactive newsletters, science simulations, virtual tours, birthday cards, and interactive tutorials (Resnick *et al.*, 2009). As Scratchers learn mathematical and computational concepts, they also develop important soft skills such as creative thinking, systematic reasoning, and collaboration, which are essential skills for the 21st century.

Despite the fact that many young people are considered to be "digital natives" (Prensky, 2001) due to their fluency with digital technologies, few can create their own games, animations, or simulations. The ability to program computers is crucial in enhancing one's creativity and learning potential. Moreover, programming supports "computational thinking", which helps in acquiring vital problem-solving and design strategies that can be used in non-programming domains (Wing, 2018). Visual programming, therefore, lays the foundation for becoming fluent in computer programming, with many professional game engine applications including visual scripting systems that developers can use to create interactive experiences, visualisations for film and architecture, and game development.

7.1.4 The Game

This section provides a detailed description of MoonBase VR and its features. Examining the design of the game and how it incorporates programming concepts into the gameplay mechanics. Also discussing the user interface and how it enables students to create and manipulate code blocks to achieve specific outcomes.

Figure 7-2 (left to right) menu UI, console with controllers functions, the player handling a code block, ghost walking movement

The game is set in a fictional lunar base, where players take on the role of a new employee tasked with programming various aspects of the base's operations. The challenges presented in the game are structured around real-world programming concepts such as loops, conditionals, and variables. The gameplay is divided into different levels, each building up the payers' programming skill set as they progress.

The development process involved careful planning and research, with a focus on finding the ideal target audience for the game. The game design included best practices for VR development, such as designing for specific inputs and ensuring player comfort. The game included features like teleportation and ghost-walking options to limit the possibility of motion sickness, and realistic physics collisions for code blocks. The game also included a highlight and snap function for code blocks that could be joined together, making it easier for players to understand programming concepts. The development process included prototyping and testing all aspects of the game in VR, including art, sound, and user interfaces.

Figure 7-3 Moonbase VR game images showing (left to right) the moon base environment, the coding problem and code blocks, the hologram project of the level to solve and a player building the program.

The puzzle the player is present with is to build the program that will instruct a maintenance robot to a valve at the end of a maze in order to avert disaster on the moon base. A 3D hologram display of the maze, robot and valve is provided to the player. This allows them to understand where the start and end points of the maze are and work out the instruction to get the robot to move to that location.

One of the key features of MoonBase VR is its use of code blocks. Code blocks are drag-and-drop programming elements that players use to create and run programs within the game. These blocks are based on the fundamental concepts of most programming languages and are designed to be intuitive and easy to learn. Each block has a label that represents an instruction such as move forward, left, right and loop. By using code blocks as a visual scripting tool, players can quickly and easily create programs without complex syntax or typing.

The code blocks in the game are spawned from a touch screen provided to the player who can then grab, move and drop these blocks in a physically realistic way. The block is placed via a highlight and snapping system. This is where bringing the block close to another block or an 'anchor' in the environment will show a green highlight where the block can be placed. Letting go of the block will then allow that block to 'snap' into place. Placing the blocks on a coding station allows the player to build the instructions to send to the robot and guide it through the maze. Although just because a block snaps into place doesn't mean it is in the correct order for the program to work.

Once the player has built a program, they can send the instructions to the robot. The game also features a tutorial system that guides players through each challenge, providing feedback via text, audio dialogue and sound cues to ensure that they understand if they have been successful or not. This tutorial system is designed to be accessible to players of all skill levels, from complete beginners to more experienced

programmers. This system will inform the player if the program they have built is correct or not. If the code blocks are in the right order the player can see the robot move through the maze on the hologram. Once the maintenance robot has reached the goal the next level is displayed. The game challenges players to complete each level with its own set of objectives and programming requirements. Each level builds on the learning concepts from the previous level and introduces an additional concept or an extra level of complexity.

Figure 7-4 Code station, blocks and hologram

The game ends with the player reaching level 10, for this study, we implemented a no-win scenario, with an explosion in the lab area the player is located and instructions to construct a network of pipes and open a valve, a countdown timer ticks until a final explosion ends the experience. This was done as a way to give an end to the testing session while leaving the player wanting more.

Overall, MoonBase VR is an innovative and engaging way to learn programming concepts. Its use of immersive virtual reality, combined with intuitive programming tools and comprehensive tutorials, makes it an ideal tool for educators looking to introduce their students to the world of coding. With its emphasis on real-world applications and problem-solving, MoonBase VR provides an exciting and challenging learning experience that is sure to inspire the next generation of programmers.

7.1.5 Brief overview for the development process

Conceptualisation and Ideation

- Initial concept development focusing on gamifying programming education using VR.
- Research of other software that provide the same functionality.
- Identification of target audience: beginners in programming with interest in games and new technologies.

Design Phase

- Pre-production activities, including defining ideation, planning the VR experience, and researching resources.
- Focus on PCVR platforms with motion-tracked controllers for enhanced interactivity.
- Development of user profiles to create a game that resonates with the target audience.

Development Tools and Technologies

- Utilisation of Unreal Engine 4 for game development for quick iteration due to access to ready made assets, engine code and VR support.
- Specific focus on the Oculus PC (now Meta) platform for VR deployment.

Game Mechanics and Interaction Design

- Prototyping basic mechanics like object interaction, code block manipulation, and game movement.
- Implementation of realistic physics, highlight and snap functions for object interactions.
- Emphasis on player comfort and ease of use, including various movement options like teleportation and 'ghost' walking.
- Game logic to create the puzzle logic allowing the player to gain success/fail feedback, with several 'sanity checks' for making sure the player has completed the required task.

User Interface and User Experience

- Designing intuitive user interfaces and ensuring smooth transitions within VR to enhance user experience.
- Prototyping art, sound, and user interfaces, followed by VR testing and iterations.

Finalisation and Launch

- Development of a vertical slice representing the game's final look and feel.
- Iterative improvements based on interim builds leading to the first prototype.

7.1.6 The Study

The study will then move on to a discussion of the research conducted on the effectiveness of MoonBase VR as a tool for teaching programming. We collected data from 40 participants who played the game and used a mixed-methods approach to collect both quantitative and qualitative data to evaluate the effectiveness of the game as a tool for teaching programming concepts. This section will provide a detailed description of the methods used to collect data in the MoonBase VR study.

Firstly, we used pre and post-tests to assess the participants' knowledge and understanding of programming concepts. The pre-test was conducted before the participants played the game, while the post-test was administered immediately after the participants completed the game. The tests included both multiple-choice and short-answer questions, covering topics such as programming concepts, debugging, and algorithm design. We used these tests to evaluate the participants' programming skills and to determine whether the game had improved their understanding of programming concepts. In addition to the pre- and post-tests, we also used observational data to evaluate the participants' interactions with the game. This allowed us to gain insights into how the participants were using the game to identify areas where the game could be improved to enhance the learning experience.

The players also had the opportunity to write about their experience after they completed the game. This was designed to elicit feedback on the participants' experience playing the game, including their perceptions of its effectiveness as a tool for teaching programming concepts and provided qualitative data that complemented the quantitative data collected through the pre- and post-tests and the observational data.

To analyse the data collected in the study, we used statistical analysis for the quantitative data from the pre- and post-tests and the observational data, while the qualitative data was analysed thematically. By using a mixed-methods approach, we were able to gain a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of the game as a tool for teaching programming concepts.

Overall, the methods used in the MoonBase VR study allowed us to collect a range of data that provided insights into the effectiveness of the game as a tool for teaching programming concepts. The pre- and post-tests allowed us to measure the impact of the game on the participants' knowledge and understanding of programming concepts, while the observational data and feedback provided a more in-depth understanding of how the game was used by the participants and its effectiveness as a learning tool. The mixed-methods approach used to analyse the data allowed the researchers to draw more robust conclusions about the effectiveness of the game and to identify areas where it could be improved to enhance the learning experience.

7.1.7 Findings

One of the key findings of the study was that MoonBase VR had a positive effect on student motivation. The immersive nature of the virtual reality environment and the game-like mechanics of the program engaged students and motivated them to continue learning. Additionally, the study found that the program was effective at teaching programming concepts to students who had no prior experience with coding. Another important finding was that the use of virtual reality allowed for more efficient and effective learning. In traditional classroom settings, it can be difficult for students to visualise the concepts being taught, which can hinder their understanding of the material. However, in the virtual reality environment of MoonBase VR, students were able to interact with the concepts they were learning, which made them easier to understand and remember. The study also found from the NASA-TXL data that the use of virtual reality helped to reduce the cognitive load on students. When learning a new skill, such as coding, students must juggle multiple concepts and ideas in their minds simultaneously. This can be overwhelming and lead to cognitive overload, which can hinder learning. However, by providing a visual and interactive learning environment, virtual reality can help to reduce cognitive load and make learning more effective.

The pre-experience survey questions were used to gain an understanding of the study group's general trends and experience levels with virtual reality, computer programming, and educational games. Of the participants, 87.5% identified as male and 12.5% identified as female (Figure 7-5), with Figure 7-6 showing the majority being 15 to 30-year-olds (62.5%).

Figure 7-5 What gender do you identify as?

Figure 7-6 What is your age?

Almost half (47.5%) had a bachelor's degree as their highest level of education, followed by high school (30%), a master's degree (15%), and a Ph.D. (7.5%). Over a third of participants had an intermediate level of VR experience, with nearly a third being beginners and another third made up of experienced, expert, and no experience at all.

More than half (57.5%) had previous experience with visual scripting systems (Figure 7-7), while a larger portion (62.5%) had experience with object-oriented programming. All participants had used VR before the study, but only 15% had used it in an educational setting. The largest fields where people had experienced a VR learning experience were history and science, with no one experiencing these in an educational application for arts, English, or mathematics (Figure 7-8).

Figure 7-7 Have you used any form of visual scripting?

Figure 7-8 If you have used VR for education, in what subject area?

The post-experience questionnaire was conducted after participants played the MoonBase VR game. Participants were asked to grade statements using a scale of 1 to 5, indicating whether they strongly agreed (level 1) or strongly disagreed (level 5) with the statement.

Results show that a majority of participants found the headset and joysticks to be comfortable to use (Figure 7-9), while 100% of participants liked the look of the game. Few participants reported feeling discomfort while playing the game in VR, with 90% reporting little to no dizziness.

Figure 7-9 Movement is simple and natural.

A large number of participants found the placement highlighting feature useful when working with the visual scripting blocks (Figure 7-10), with most finding the initial position of the blocks adequate. The method of snapping the blocks together was found to work well, and participants generally understood the use of the blocks.

Figure 7-10 Highlighting the areas where the blocks can be placed is useful.

Participants also found that the difficulty of the game increased progressively and that the number of actions required to solve each level was appropriate (Figure 7-11). The environment was generally well-received, with most participants finding it aesthetically pleasing and not distracting. Transitions between levels were reported to be smooth by all participants.

Figure 7-11 The difficulty of the game increases progressively at each level

Additionally, 75% of participants agreed that programming with this application can be fun (Figure 7-12), and the majority found the game engaging (Figure 7-13). Furthermore, most participants agreed that visualising code using code blocks in VR made it easier to understand programming, and 75% of participants found that undertaking visual programming using a VR game increased their interest in learning computer programming (Figure 7-14).

Figure 7-12 I think programming like this can be fun

Figure 7-13 How engaging was the game?

Figure 7-14 Did visualising code in this way make it easier to understand?

Overall, the post-experience survey suggests that the MoonBase VR game was well-designed and enjoyable to play.

7.1.8 Conclusion

The article introduces Moonbase VR, a programming game in virtual reality. The game offers a highly visual, semantic VR programming language that enables effective manipulation of code blocks to build computer programs. The study evaluated the game's usability and the participants' perception of using a VR game to learn programming. The results indicate that most participants found the VR game to be a fun and engaging way to learn programming and that it would increase their interest in this area of computer science. Future development of the platform could involve uploading learning outcomes and implementing further puzzle mechanics, and multi-user/player functionality for teacher observation and guidance. The article concludes by highlighting the potential for VR to enhance learning outcomes and the excitement it brings to computer science education. Further empirical research and application development is necessary to confirm the game's potential fully.

The research has shown that the game provides an effective and engaging way for students to learn programming skills and that virtual reality has the potential to revolutionise the way we teach programming. Our research has important implications for educators, students, and developers, and we hope that it will inspire further research and development in this exciting and rapidly evolving field.

8 Discussion

The overall theme of these studies is the exploration of virtual reality's potential in education, focusing on creating engaging and effective learning experiences. They investigate how VR can make complex subjects more accessible and enjoyable for learners; how VR compares to traditional interfaces; the key elements of effective VR-based learning; and the potential of gamifying complex subjects using VR. These studies contribute to our understanding of whether VR can be used to enhance learning outcomes and make complex topics more approachable. They demonstrate that virtual reality has the potential to revolutionise the way we learn and teach. By offering immersive experiences, VR can help learners better understand complex concepts, retain information and stay engaged.

The research also highlights the importance of identifying effective approaches to incorporating VR into education. This includes understanding user preferences, optimising VR design, and developing best practices for various subjects. As the technology continues to evolve, there is an opportunity for educators and developers to collaborate and create even more impactful learning experiences using VR.

In the future, we can expect to see more widespread adoption of VR in educational settings, spanning from primary schools to professional training. This shift could lead to a deeper understanding of complex subjects, enhanced problem-solving skills, and more engaged and motivated learners. As the research progresses and VR technology becomes more accessible, the possibilities for its use in education will continue to expand.

The three studies highlight the potential of virtual reality for creating immersive gamification frameworks, building effective immersive technology, and designing impactful immersive experiences. By exploring these areas, they open discussion about how we can improve learning outcomes and make complex topics more accessible.

- Frameworks for immersive technology: The first study compared traditional flat screen interfaces (pancake) with VR environments. The study found that participants were open to using VR to explore virtual spaces, even employing their whole body for interaction. This suggests that immersive technology like VR has potential advantages over traditional interfaces and can help build effective frameworks for user engagement.
- Building immersive experiences: The second study focused on a systematic review of VR applications for education. The review highlighted key elements for effective VR-based learning, such as experiential learning theory and realistic surroundings. By understanding these elements, we can build immersive experiences that improve educational outcomes.
- Developing frameworks for immersive gamification: The third study used VR to gamify computer programming education. By creating a virtual reality game with a self-directed learning path, the study aimed to make coding more accessible and engaging. This approach

showcases how VR can be utilised to create immersive gamification frameworks to enhance learning experiences.

These contributions help pave the way for further research and development in the field, ultimately improving educational experiences and outcomes.

8.1 Framework for the use of Immersive Gamification

In recent years, the intersection of gaming and education has gained significant attention as a novel approach to enhancing learning experiences. The studies undertaken have explored the use of immersive gamification and its implications within the educational landscape. Several aspects of discussion have been raised to explore and contribute to a comprehensive understanding of this growing field. The discussion points raised encompass a diverse range of themes, including the historical origins of gamification, its theoretical foundations, and the examination of contemporary frameworks and applications designed to optimise learning experiences. Additionally, the potential benefits and challenges associated with the implementation of immersive gamification in educational settings, taking into consideration the perspectives of both learners and educators. Having a well-rounded examination of gamification in education, exploring not only its positive impact on motivation and engagement but also addressing potential concerns and limitations is imperative to the development of the field. By fostering an open discourse on this topic, striving to contribute to the ongoing conversation about the role of gamification in shaping the future of education, and in turn, inspire further research and innovation in this captivating area.

Game-based learning is not a new concept, and many educators routinely incorporate games into their lesson plans, particularly at the preschool and early elementary school levels. “Gamification” of digital content for use within education is a concept that was introduced by British IT expert Nick Pelling at the beginning of the 2000s, but it has only recently become popular (Smith, 2014; Kunkel, Lock and Doyle, 2021). Educational digital games can be considered a very specialised use of the technology; it refers to the use of game frameworks and practices in the development of digital content for e-learning (i.e., game-informed learning) (Kickmeier-Rust *et al.*, 2007; Yusny, 2013; Smith, 2014; Kunkel, Lock and Doyle, 2021). Although it could be argued that the development of digital games has always been linked to education. The earliest development of computer games can be traced back to students and educators programming games on university computers. These machines were prohibitively expensive and mainly only found in government departments, large industries and on academic campuses for use in research. In their spare time, those with access to such machines would experiment with their capabilities by making digital versions of well-known games such as tic-tak-toe; draughts; and tennis, later leading to the making of Pong (Kent, 2001; Stanton, 2019; Lowood, 2009). Other notable games

developed through this early experimentation took the video game beyond the possibilities of non-digital games such as SpaceWar! In 1962, built by a collection of colleges at Harvard and MIT, this game as the title suggests took the players into space where they could battle against each other. Although these games were not made to educate the player the programmers used the making of these games to learn from the building of the game. Many of these programmers went on to help create the games industry either directly by setting up companies like Atari or indirectly by inspiring many more to build on what they had already made. In the mid-1980s we see the merging of games for entertainment and education in several edutainment games. The 1985 game The Oregon Trail taught history, exploring the migration of people into the west of America in the 1800's as well as the dangers of the times such as dysentery, typhoid and 'rivers' (an in-joke for those who played the game). Also released in 1985, Where in the World is Carmen Santiago (WWCS) taught geography. Aside from the education element they offered enjoyable gameplay with The Oregon Trail being a strategy game with emergent storytelling and roguelike random generation years before the game that coined this term 'Rogue' existed and WWCS being a well-made adventure game with strong replay ability. In some ways the education elements of these games were 'light' but this did not stop them showing up into thousands of schools, tricking children into learning or tricking teachers into letting children play games during school, depending on your perspective.

In an era where education seeks innovative ways to captivate learners, gamification emerges as a compelling force. Nevertheless, one might ponder: Must a teacher be a gaming enthusiast to employ such techniques? Schulz, Isabwe and Reichert (2015) argue that user-centered ICT tools should bolster educators' motivation, regardless of their gaming and prowess.

The complexities of integrating immersive technologies can even further complicate the situation, making it difficult for educators to effectively teach their subject matter. With various cutting-edge innovations significantly contributing to the development and implementation of immersive gamified learning experiences over recent years the role of technology in gamification must be a prominent discussion point. Among these advancements, virtual and augmented reality immersive technology has emerged as a particularly influential factor in driving the transformation of traditional educational methods and practices. Virtual and augmented reality technologies have been leveraged to create immersive learning environments that foster deeper understanding and engagement (Çakiroğlu *et al.*, 2021). By visualising abstract concepts and situating learners within virtual worlds, these technologies offer enriched learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles and preferences. Moreover, the adaptability of these technologies allows for tailored educational content that aligns with the unique needs and profiles of individual students, ensuring a more personalised and effective approach to learning (Lau *et al.*, 2022). Immersive technologies can further enhance the impact of gamification on education by offering a heightened sense of presence and immersion. This allows learners to become

active participants in their educational journey, promoting greater motivation, curiosity, and retention of knowledge (Javornik *et al.*, 2018).

Therefore, a crucial aspect in the discussion of immersive gamification in education is the role of user-centred ICT tools (Schulz, Isabwe and Reichert, 2015). These tools emphasise the importance of designing educational experiences that cater to the needs and preferences of both learners and educators. Ensuring that these tools are accessible, regardless of an educator's technical knowledge or skills, the potential benefits of gamification can be maximised for all involved parties. This reinforces the notion that educators do not need to be gaming or computing enthusiasts to effectively harness the power of gamification in their teaching practices. The role of technology in gamification, coupled with the importance of user-centered tools, exemplifies the vast potential of this approach to revolutionise the educational landscape (Chen, Cheng and Chew, 2016). By acknowledging and addressing the challenges associated with the integration of these innovations, we can pave the way for a more engaging, personalised, and effective learning experience for students and educators alike.

Ultimately, the discussion points presented emphasise the potential of immersive gamification and as the field continues to evolve, these insights provide a foundation for understanding the key factors driving its success and the opportunities for further innovation and development.

8.2 Considerations for the use of Immersive Technology

Research found that there is a lack of knowledge on how to use immersive technologies in educational settings effectively. This section explores how immersive technology can be used to personalise learning by identifying areas of need, supporting remote learning, and selecting the appropriate technology for different education levels. Through a comprehensive analysis of the benefits, challenges, and opportunities presented by immersive technology, a practical guide for educators and stakeholders interested in leveraging these tools for personalised learning experiences.

To effectively implement immersive technology in education, it is crucial to

- (i) identify appropriate theories and models guiding its design and development,
- (ii) investigate how its attributes support learning and improve performance, and
- (iii) assess its impact on learners with diverse aptitudes (Chen, 2006). Several studies have attempted to explore these aspects within different contexts.

Chen (2006) investigated the design, development, and evaluation of virtual reality-based learning environments, particularly focusing on novice car driver instruction. Savin-Baden *et al.*, (2010) examined the impact of immersive virtual worlds on teachers and teaching, while Lorenzo, Ángel Sicilia

and Sánchez, (2012) conducted an experimental study on collaborative evaluation in a multi-user immersive online learning setting.

Embodied learning technologies, which capitalise on the unique characteristics of immersive technologies, have gained attention. Lindgren *et al.*, (2013) proposed six principles for embodied learning technology researchers to ensure that the rationale, design, and execution of empirical studies are sound. Additionally, Huang, Hood and Yoo, (2013) investigated the role of computer anxiety in influencing female college students' perceptions of Web 2.0 applications for learning within the context of the gender digital divide.

Keane, Keane and Blicblau, (2016) explored the relationship between deep learning, 21st-century skills, and appropriate use of information and communication technologies (ICT). Shen *et al.*, (2018) examined the contributing factor affecting students' reasons for using head-mounted displays (HMD) in learning by testing hypotheses related to information technology acceptance and Kolb's learning styles. O'Connor and Andrews, (2018) employed descriptive statistics and thematic analysis to describe students' perspectives on how mobile apps can support learning and how to effectively implement and use them in practice.

(Han, 2020) investigated the influence of immersive virtual field trips (VFTs) using HMDs on students' sense of presence and perceived learning. Other influential work includes Okechukwu and Udoka (2011) examination of virtual reality technology advances and applications.

The integration of immersive technology in educational settings is a developing area of research. As more studies are conducted, our understanding of the best practices and potential drawbacks of this technology will deepen. The goal is to ensure that the implementation of immersive technology in education leads to improved learning experiences and outcomes for diverse learners. To accomplish this, researchers and educators need to continue to explore novel approaches for incorporating immersive technology in various educational contexts. This includes understanding how students with different learning styles and aptitudes can benefit from tailored experiences using these technologies. Additionally, it is essential to examine the long-term effects of immersive technology on learning outcomes and retention, as well as the potential for reducing educational disparities among different student populations.

To effectively use immersive technology for personalised learning, it is crucial to first identify the specific needs, strengths, and weaknesses of individual students. This process involves assessing learning styles, proficiency levels, and personal interests to create tailored learning experiences that address each student's unique requirements which can encompass a wide range of academic disciplines, such as psychology, cognitive science, and education.

Samimy (2008) employed multiple data sources, including interviews, observation, and document analysis, to explore the multifaceted characteristic of a language learner, language tutor, and a (non)member of a target language community. This study illustrates the complex interactions between an individual's personal and social contexts in the process of language acquisition. Joy and Kolb (2009) delved into the role of culture in shaping individuals' learning processes. This research underscores the importance of acknowledging and incorporating cultural diversity when designing educational programs and curricula. Ory et al. (2015) conducted an empirical user study to identify and assess the main graphical characteristics employed to recognise the design principles of topographic mapping styles, specifically those adopted by France's Institut National de l'Information Géographique et Forestière (IGN). This study highlights the significance of effective visual communication in the dissemination of geographic information. Retrosi, Morris and McGavock (2019) carried out a pilot study investigating the association between learning styles and variation in laparoscopic skill acquisition. This research offers valuable insights into the role of individual differences in the development of surgical competencies. Kancharla (2020) studied learning style preferences among adolescent school students, utilising the Learning Channel Preference tool (O'Brien, 1990). This investigation contributes to our knowledge of how students' learning preferences evolve during adolescence and the implications for educational practice. Demydovych and Holik (2020) aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the Speaking Club in learning English for professional purposes at medical universities. This study emphasises the relevance of context-specific language instruction for the development of professional competencies. Sze et al. (2021) analysed themes such as leadership in organizational culture, leadership styles, and leadership qualities to assess the effectiveness of medical leadership in healthcare organisations. This research highlights the influence of professionals at lower hierarchical levels on decision-making processes in healthcare settings. Heinonen et al. (2022) investigated the patterns of self-reported quality of life in a multinational sample of 1,214 psychotherapist trainees, as part of the Society for Psychotherapy Research Interest Section on Psychotherapist Development and Training study. This research offers valuable insights into the factors that contribute to the well-being and professional development of psychotherapy practitioners.

These studies, along with other influential works (e.g., Tucker and Cooper (1987)), provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between learning styles, proficiency levels, and personal interests, highlighting the complexity and multi-dimensionality of human learning and development. One crucial aspect that emerges from these studies is the importance of considering individual differences when designing educational programs. Factors such as cultural background, personal interests, and learning preferences play a significant role in determining an individual's learning trajectory (Joy and Kolb, 2009; Kancharla, 2020). By acknowledging these differences and tailoring instructional methods accordingly, educators can better cater to the diverse needs of their students and foster an inclusive learning environment.

Another essential element is the role of context-specific learning experiences in the development of professional competencies (Demydovych and Holik, 2020; Sze et al., 2021), context-specific education can help individuals develop the necessary skills and knowledge required for their respective fields. This suggests that educational programs should aim to provide real-world, relevant experiences to facilitate the development of practical competencies.

In summary, the analysis of learning styles, proficiency levels, and personal interests offers valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of human learning and development. By considering individual differences, context-specific learning experiences, and the underlying physiological and cognitive mechanisms, educators and researchers can create more effective and inclusive educational practices. This comprehensive understanding can ultimately contribute to the betterment of education systems and promote the lifelong learning and development of individuals across diverse contexts.

This research is relevant to education using immersive technologies because it highlights the importance of understanding learning styles, proficiency levels, and personal interests when designing educational experiences. Immersive technologies, such as VR, AR, and MR, offer unique opportunities to create tailored, engaging, and effective learning environments that cater to diverse learners' needs.

(i) Individual differences and learning styles: Immersive technologies can be designed to accommodate various learning styles, enabling learners to interact with content in ways that best suit their preferences. For example, VR can provide kinesthetic learners (Hernandez et al., 2020) with hands-on experiences, while AR can enhance visual learning by overlaying digital information onto the physical world. By understanding the diverse learning styles of students, educators can develop immersive experiences that cater to individual needs, thereby enhancing learning outcomes.

(ii) Context-specific learning experiences: Immersive technologies can simulate real-world scenarios, providing students with opportunities to apply their knowledge and skills in context-specific situations. For instance, medical students can practice surgical procedures in a virtual operating room, while language learners can immerse themselves in a virtual environment that mimics the target language's cultural context. By offering context-specific learning experiences, immersive technologies can help bridge the gap between theory and practice, leading to the development of practical competencies.

(iii) Cultural diversity and personal interests: Immersive technologies can be designed to incorporate cultural diversity and address personal interests, making the learning experience more engaging and relatable for students. For example, an AR application could be developed to teach history by allowing students to explore their local cultural heritage sites, or a VR game could be designed to align with students' personal interests, fostering intrinsic motivation and engagement.

(iv) Cognitive mechanisms: Research on the underlying cognitive and physiological mechanisms of learning, as discussed in the studies, can inform the design of immersive technologies. By understanding how learners process information and navigate complex environments, educators can create immersive experiences that optimise learning and performance.

The educational landscape has been enriched by the arrival of immersive and adaptive learning technologies. The choice of immersive technology depends on the educational level and learning objectives. Here are some recommendations for selecting the appropriate technology for different education levels:

- Primary Education: Younger students may benefit from AR-based applications that promote exploration, curiosity, and basic skill development. These applications can provide interactive, gamified experiences that encourage students to engage with educational content in a playful and intuitive manner.
- Secondary Education: Middle and high school students can benefit from more advanced VR and AR applications that focus on critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration. For example, VR simulations that allow students to conduct virtual lab experiments or AR applications that overlay contextual information onto physical objects can provide valuable learning opportunities.
- Higher Education: College and university students may require advanced VR simulations and AR tools for complex problem-solving, skill development, and specialised training. For instance, medical students can use VR to practice surgical procedures, while architecture students can use AR to visualise and manipulate 3D models of building designs.

Chen, Huang and Lin (2009) conducted experiments to establish the Second Campus of Peking University, utilising Open Simulator and Second Life Viewer. Abulrub, Attridge and Williams (2011) described an interactive educational environment developed at WMG, the University of Warwick. The adaptive approach to computer-based training featured in these studies has not yet achieved widespread adoption in less structured or well-defined fields, such as immersive serious games and scenario-based simulations. To bridge this gap, Aslan, Öztürk and Inceoğlu (2014) discuss advancements in areas such as student modelling, pedagogical strategy, knowledge assessment, natural language processing, and virtual assistants.

Serious gaming has emerged as a potential solution to the limitations of traditional educational methods, offering a more immersive and interactive learning experience. Ottis (2014) presented a lightweight tabletop exercise format that successfully demonstrated numerous concepts to Master's level students in two European universities over five years. Argyriou, Economou and Bouki (2017) focused on educating users on the importance of cultural heritage, while Tumkor (2018) investigated the

personalisation of engineering education using mixed reality mobile applications. This latter study proposed the research question of whether certain students benefit more from immersive technologies.

Further research has sought to understand the state of the art in immersive head-mounted display virtual reality as applied to post-secondary education and skill training (Concannon, Esmail and Roduta Roberts, 2019). Fealy *et al.* (2019) explored the application and integration of immersive VR within nursing and midwifery tertiary education programs. Additionally, Marks and Thomas (2022) evaluated the adoption of VR technology in higher education over five teaching semesters in a purpose-designed laboratory at The University of Sydney, housing 26 Oculus Rift headset units, this investigation builds upon the influential work of Richard *et al.* (2006).

From these studies, we can see that integrating the right immersive technology for the different levels of education is crucial for several reasons, as it ensures the maximum potential benefits are harnessed while minimising the risk of disengagement or adverse outcomes. The following factors highlight the importance of selecting appropriate immersive technologies for each educational level:

- (i) Age-appropriate content and complexity: Students at various educational levels have different cognitive abilities, learning preferences, and backgrounds. Integrating age-appropriate immersive technologies ensures that the content and complexity are tailored to the learners' cognitive development, promoting a more effective learning experience.
- (ii) Maximising engagement: Immersive technologies have the potential to increase student engagement, but only when the chosen tool aligns with the learners' interests, abilities, and prior experiences. Matching the right technology to the educational level ensures that students remain motivated and engaged throughout the learning process.
- (iii) Ensuring positive learning outcomes: The primary goal of education is to facilitate learning and promote the acquisition of knowledge and skills. Selecting the appropriate immersive technology for each educational level ensures that the learning outcomes align with the objectives of the curriculum and the needs of the learners.
- (iv) Efficient resource allocation: Educational institutions often operate with limited resources. By integrating the right immersive technology for each level of education, institutions can optimise resource allocation and ensure the most significant impact on learning outcomes.
- (v) Minimising negative effects: Inappropriate use of immersive technologies may lead to negative effects such as motion sickness, disorientation, or overstimulation. Matching the technology to the educational level can help mitigate these risks and ensure a positive and safe learning environment.
- (vi) Facilitating successful technology adoption: The integration of immersive technologies in education requires a significant investment of time, effort, and resources. Selecting the right

technology for the educational level increases the likelihood of successful adoption by ensuring that the benefits outweigh the costs, fostering a more receptive attitude among educators, students, and stakeholders.

- (vii) Enhancing equity in education: Appropriate use of immersive technologies can contribute to bridging the achievement gap among diverse student populations. By selecting the right technology for each educational level, educators can provide equal access to engaging, personalised, and effective learning experiences for all students.

Therefore, integrating the right immersive technology for different educational levels is essential to ensure the most significant positive impact on learning experiences and outcomes. By carefully considering the needs, abilities, and interests of students at each level, educators can optimise the potential benefits of these innovative tools while minimising potential risks, leading to more effective and engaging learning environments.

In this rapidly evolving field, we see a ‘new’ term being spawned to bring together all of these technologies, which is Extended Reality (XR). This new term encompasses virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality, and according to some is poised to revolutionise various aspects of human existence, including education, healthcare, transportation, and multimedia communication. By examining recent research on XR from diverse disciplines, aiming to provide an overview of the theoretical foundations, practical applications, and potential challenges associated with the expanding technology.

Design fiction, as talked about by Johnstone *et al.* (2022), serves as thought experiments that allow researchers to investigate the potential implications of XR technologies by crafting hypothetical scenarios. These exercises not only underscore the numerous possibilities for device-specific interaction but also highlight the need for standardisation across devices and applications, as evidenced by Spittle *et al.* (2022) systematic review and evaluation of task-based interaction methods in immersive environments. In the field of healthcare, Zagury-Orly *et al.* (2023) have conducted a review of the current state of XR use in otolaryngology (Ear, nose and throat surgery) training, revealing its potential for enhancing medical education. Sra *et al.* (2022) have identified experiential artefacts (EAs) as a potential challenge in XR usage, as users report lingering experiential structures that disrupt their daily life upon transitioning from virtual to real environments.

Although there is still ambiguity to the definition and meaning of the term ‘The Metaverse’, as a model for education and skill development, it is emerging as a concept to be an ideal platform for extended reality and Internet of Everything (IoE) integration, according to Jagatheesaperumal *et al.* (2022). This convergence of technologies is poised to revolutionise educational services in the future metaverse. In a similar vein, Lee and Takenaka (2022) propose the use of XR in public health education to better

prepare trainees for complex, real-world public health scenarios necessitating public engagement, investigative skills, and critical decision-making.

Transportation is another domain that stands to benefit from XR advances, with Zhou *et al.* (2022) envisioning a Vehicular-Metaverse that encompasses digital twins of intelligent transportation systems (TS-Metaverse) and customised XR services within individual vehicles (IV-Metaverse). This blended immersive realm is expected to scale up to entire cities and countries. From a multimedia communications standpoint, Dong and Lee (2023) delves into the metaverse, elucidating its requirements and parameters, while Zhi and Wu (2023) adopt a cognitive-affective model of immersive learning to investigate the use of XR in language learning. Connelly *et al.* (2023) contribute to this growing body of research, offering additional insights into the development and implementation of XR technologies.

Over the next decade, advancements in XR technologies, including hardware and software, are expected to flourish, revolutionising human-computer interactions and experiences (Herur-Raman *et al.*, 2021). Innovations in display technology, sensor systems, and computing capabilities will drive the development of next-generation XR devices. These advancements may lead to lightweight, ergonomic headsets that offer higher resolutions, wider fields of view, and improved eye-tracking capabilities (Marr, 2022). Furthermore, haptic feedback systems are anticipated to become more sophisticated, allowing users to experience more realistic and natural interactions within virtual environments. In terms of software, breakthroughs in artificial intelligence, machine learning, and computer vision will contribute to the creation of more immersive and interactive XR applications. These innovations are expected to enable a more seamless integration of virtual and physical worlds, enriching user experiences (Marr, 2022).

Immersive technologies potential in various contexts, such as entertainment, education, and socialisation. As one of the most promising and rapidly evolving technologies of the 21st century, VR has captured the imagination of researchers, developers, and users alike. By providing immersive, interactive, and highly realistic experiences, VR offers a unique opportunity to redefine the way we engage with digital content and the world around us. Let us consider the key aspects of immersive technology:

- Sensory simulation: The technology relies on sensory simulation, such as vision, auditory, touch, and force feedback, to create realistic and immersive experiences for users.
- Immersion and presence: Immersion is crucial for the success of these experiences. When users feel present in the virtual environment, they are more likely to engage with and believe the simulation.

- Interaction: Interactions with the virtual environment are essential for a successful VR experience. Devices such as head-mounted displays, handheld controllers, gloves with movement sensors, and external sensors facilitate these interactions.
- Storytelling and narratives: VR technology allows for highly immersive and participatory storytelling experiences. Users can actively engage in the story, progressing the narrative through their actions, making VR a powerful tool for education, entertainment, and socialization.
- Challenges and research needs: The chapter highlights several challenges that must be addressed in the development and application of VR technology, such as identifying appropriate theories and models to guide design and development, investigating how VR attributes can support learning and performance, and studying the impact of VR on learners with different aptitudes.
- Comparing VR to other media: The chapter draws parallels between the current state of VR and the transition from theatre to movies, suggesting that VR may develop its own unique ways of presenting stories and experiences over time.

8.2.1 Sensory simulation

Sensory simulation is at the heart of virtual reality technology and plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of virtual reality experiences. By stimulating multiple senses, VR has the potential to create an immersive and realistic environment that closely mimics real-world experiences. Looking at several aspects of sensory simulation:

- Visual Simulation:

The foundation of most VR experiences is a visual simulation, which aims to recreate a realistic and convincing representation of the environment. High-quality graphics, rendering techniques, and display technologies contribute to the sense of presence in virtual environments (Benford *et al.*, 1998). Stereoscopic displays, which present slightly different images to each eye, create a perception of depth, while high refresh rates and low latency ensure smooth and responsive motion (Robinett and Holloway, 1995).

- Auditory Simulation:

Spatialised audio is essential for enhancing immersion in VR. By simulating sound sources in a 3D environment, users can perceive the direction and distance of objects and events around them. Binaural audio and advanced sound processing techniques, such as head-related transfer functions

(HRTFs) (Geronazzo *et al.*, 2019), contribute to a realistic and dynamic auditory experience, complementing the visual aspects of the virtual world.

- Haptic Feedback:

Haptic feedback, or tactile simulation, adds another layer of immersion to VR experiences by allowing users to feel physical sensations in the virtual environment. This can range from simple vibrations to more complex force feedback systems that reproduce the sensation of touch, pressure, and texture. Haptic feedback can greatly enhance interaction and engagement, but developing realistic and responsive haptic devices remains a challenge (Zhang, Chembumroong and Sureephong, 2021).

- Olfactory Simulation:

Although still in its infancy, olfactory simulation has the potential to further enhance the sense of presence in VR (Baus and Bouchard, 2017). By incorporating smells into the virtual environment, users can experience a more vivid and multi-sensory simulation. However, technical difficulties, such as creating a wide range of odours and delivering them in a controlled manner, pose significant challenges to the development and adoption of olfactory simulation in VR.

Sensory simulation is a key aspect of virtual reality that aims to create immersive and convincing experiences by engaging multiple senses. While significant advancements have been made in visual, auditory, and haptic simulations, challenges remain in perfecting these technologies and incorporating additional senses, such as olfaction. Overcoming these challenges will be crucial in developing more realistic and engaging VR experiences that closely resemble real-world interactions.

8.2.2 Interaction

Interaction is a fundamental aspect of virtual reality experiences, enabling users to engage with and manipulate the virtual environment in ways that feel natural and intuitive. This section will explore various interaction techniques and devices used as well as their benefits and weaknesses.

- Gesture-based Interaction:

Gesture-based interaction allows users to control virtual environments using natural body movements, such as hand gestures or head orientation. This approach has several benefits, including a more intuitive and immersive experience, as it mimics real-world interactions (Spittle *et al.*, 2022). However, gesture-based interaction can be limited by the accuracy and responsiveness of the tracking system, which may result in a less satisfying experience if not implemented properly.

- Controller-based Interaction:

Many immersive technology systems rely on handheld controllers for user input. These devices often feature buttons, joysticks, and other controls, as well as motion-tracking capabilities. Controller-based interaction offers precise and reliable input, allowing users to perform complex actions in the virtual environment. However, this approach can feel less natural than gesture-based interaction and may require a learning curve for users to become proficient with the controls (Johnson-Glenberg, 2018).

- Voice Recognition:

Voice recognition enables users to interact with virtual environments using spoken commands, offering a hands-free and intuitive method of interaction. This approach can be particularly useful for users with limited mobility or when other interaction methods are impractical (Y. C. Shih and Yang, 2008). However, voice recognition can be limited by background noise, accents, and other factors that affect the system's ability to accurately interpret commands.

- Eye-tracking Interaction:

Eye-tracking technology allows users to interact with virtual environments using their gaze, providing a highly intuitive and natural method of interaction. This approach can enhance the sense of presence in VR experiences by enabling more realistic eye contact with virtual characters and objects (Pietro *et al.*, 2014). However, eye-tracking systems can be expensive and may not always provide accurate or reliable input.

Interaction in virtual reality is crucial for creating engaging and immersive experiences. While various interaction techniques and devices offer unique benefits, each method also has its own set of weaknesses. The ideal VR interaction system would combine the strengths of each approach, providing users with a seamless and intuitive means of engaging with the virtual environment. As technology continues to advance, it is likely that new and improved interaction methods will emerge, further enhancing the potential of immersive experiences.

8.2.3 Storytelling and narratives

The integration of storytelling and narratives in virtual reality experiences can significantly enhance user engagement and emotional investment. By incorporating narrative elements, VR experiences can transcend mere simulations and become meaningful, immersive stories. This section will discuss various approaches to storytelling in VR and their respective benefits and weaknesses.

- Linear Narratives:

Linear narratives follow a set storyline that progresses in a predetermined sequence. This approach to storytelling can be beneficial as it allows creators to craft a polished, cohesive narrative with carefully planned pacing and dramatic arcs. However, linearity can limit the sense of agency and interactivity, as users are confined to a predetermined path with little room for exploration or deviation (Jones, 2017).

- Non-linear Narratives:

Non-linear narratives offer multiple branching paths and story outcomes, allowing users to influence the story's direction through their choices and actions within the virtual environment. This approach can enhance user agency and immersion, as it provides a sense of control and personal investment in the narrative. However, non-linear storytelling can be challenging to design and implement effectively, as it requires the anticipation and management of numerous story variations and the potential for narrative inconsistencies (Riedl and Young, 2011).

- Environmental Storytelling:

Environmental storytelling utilises the virtual environment to convey narrative elements, such as through visual cues, audio logs, or other in-world objects. This approach can create a more immersive experience by subtly embedding the story within the environment, encouraging users to explore and discover the narrative at their own pace. However, this method can sometimes result in a less cohesive and focused narrative, as users may miss key story elements or experience them out of order (Shin, 2018).

- Emergent Narratives:

Emergent narratives arise from the interactions between users and the virtual environment, with the story unfolding organically based on user actions and choices. This approach can lead to highly engaging and personalized experiences, as users actively shape the narrative through their actions. However, emergent narratives can be unpredictable and difficult to control, which may result in an inconsistent or less satisfying overall story (Jones, 2017).

Various approaches to storytelling in immersive experiences offer unique benefits, but as in other forms of media, each method also comes with its own set of challenges and weaknesses. Striking the right balance between narrative structure and user agency is essential for creating compelling and immersive VR experiences. As the medium continues to evolve, storytellers will have the opportunity to experiment with new narrative techniques and push the boundaries of immersive storytelling in virtual reality.

8.2.4 Comparing VR to other media

Virtual reality offers unique opportunities and experiences compared to traditional forms of media, such as television, film, and video games. This section will explore the benefits and drawbacks of VR in relation to other media platforms.

- **Immersion and Presence:**

One of the key benefits of virtual reality is its ability to provide users with a heightened sense of immersion and presence (Chen *et al.*, 2019). By leveraging sensory simulation and interaction capabilities, VR can create a more convincing and engaging experience compared to passive media like television and film. However, a drawback of this increased immersion is the potential for motion sickness or discomfort (Kelly *et al.*, 2021), particularly among users who are sensitive to the visual and vestibular discrepancies that can occur in virtual environments.

- **Interactivity and Engagement:**

Virtual reality offers users the opportunity to interact with and influence their environment in ways that are not possible in traditional media. This increased interactivity can lead to more engaging and memorable experiences, particularly in educational or training contexts. However, the drawback is that the development of interactive VR content can be more complex and time-consuming than creating linear, passive media. This can lead to higher production costs and potentially limit the availability of high-quality VR experiences.

- **Social Connectivity:**

VR has the potential to revolutionise social interactions (Jagatheesaperumal *et al.*, 2022) by allowing users to connect with others in shared virtual spaces, regardless of their physical location. This can be a benefit in terms of fostering collaboration, empathy, and understanding among users. However, the drawback is the potential for social isolation, as individuals may choose to spend more time in virtual worlds than engaging with others in the physical world. Balancing the social opportunities of VR with the need for real-world connections is an ongoing challenge.

- **Accessibility and Equipment Requirements:**

Compared to other forms of media, virtual reality often requires more specialised and expensive equipment, such as VR headsets and controllers. This can be a barrier to entry for some users, limiting the accessibility and reach of VR experiences. On the other hand, the benefits of VR in terms of immersion, interactivity, and engagement may justify the investment in equipment for those who can afford it. The ongoing development of more affordable and user-friendly VR technology will be crucial in addressing this drawback.

The technology presents unique opportunities and challenges compared to other media forms. While VR offers unparalleled levels of immersion, interactivity, and social connectivity, it also faces drawbacks related to user comfort, content development complexity, and accessibility. Understanding the benefits and drawbacks of VR in comparison to other media can help guide the development of more compelling, inclusive, and effective virtual experiences, ultimately shaping the future of digital storytelling, communication, and education.

8.2.5 Challenges and research needs

As the sector continues to evolve and gain traction, a number of challenges and research needs have emerged. This section will highlight the benefits of addressing these challenges, as well as the weaknesses or limitations that currently exist in the field.

- **Technological Limitations:**

While advancements in VR technology have been impressive, there are still limitations that affect the quality and accessibility of VR experiences. Addressing these technological constraints can lead to more realistic and immersive experiences for users. However, current weaknesses include limited field of view, latency issues, and the need for improved haptic feedback systems. Overcoming these challenges will require ongoing research and development in areas such as display technology, motion tracking, and haptic interfaces.

- **Accessibility and Inclusivity:**

Ensuring that virtual reality experiences are accessible to a wide range of users, including those with disabilities, is crucial for the growth and acceptance of VR as a medium (Rizzo *et al.*, 2004). Developing adaptive interfaces and customizable settings can lead to more inclusive experiences, benefiting a broader audience. However, the current weakness is the lack of standardised guidelines and tools to support the creation of accessible VR content. Research is needed to identify best practices and develop frameworks for designing inclusive virtual environments.

- **Ethical Considerations:**

As VR becomes more immersive and realistic, ethical questions surrounding user safety, privacy, and the potential for harmful content must be addressed (Jagatheesaperumal *et al.*, 2022). Developing guidelines and policies to ensure responsible use of VR can benefit users by fostering a safer and more ethical virtual landscape. However, the current weakness is the limited research and understanding of the long-term psychological effects of immersive VR experiences. Further studies are needed to inform ethical guidelines and practices within the industry.

- User Experience and Interface Design:

Creating intuitive and user-friendly interfaces is essential for the widespread adoption of virtual reality. Improving the usability of VR systems can benefit users by reducing the learning curve and promoting more natural interactions within virtual environments (Dong and Lee, 2023). However, a weakness in the field is the lack of established design principles and best practices specific to VR. Research is needed to explore effective interaction techniques and develop guidelines for designing user-friendly virtual interfaces.

Addressing the challenges and research needs will be vital for the ongoing development and acceptance of the medium. By tackling technological limitations, promoting accessibility and inclusivity, considering ethical issues, and refining user experience design, VR has the potential to become an even more powerful and immersive tool for entertainment, education, and communication. Collaborative efforts among researchers, developers, and users will be essential in overcoming these challenges and shaping the future of virtual reality experiences.

This section has discussed the potential benefits and drawbacks of sensory simulation, interaction, storytelling and narratives, challenges and research needs, as well as the comparison of VR to other media platforms. Virtual reality offers unparalleled opportunities for immersion and presence, enabling users to experience and interact with digital worlds in ways that were once considered science fiction.

However, these opportunities come with their own set of challenges, including user comfort, accessibility, and the complexity of content development. Balancing the potential benefits with the inherent challenges of virtual reality will be crucial as the technology continues to mature. Further research and development will be required to address issues such as motion sickness, social isolation, and the high costs associated with VR hardware. By understanding and addressing these challenges, the VR industry can ensure that the medium reaches its full potential, providing users with engaging, immersive, and transformative experiences across a wide range of applications. As we continue to explore and develop the technology, it is essential that we remain mindful of both the benefits and drawbacks, working collaboratively to create a virtual landscape that is inclusive, accessible, and meaningful for all users.

8.3 Considerations for the Implementation of Immersive Experiences

The use of advanced visualisation technologies and immersive experiences is becoming increasingly popular across different fields, ranging from architecture and engineering to education and cultural heritage. The development of augmented reality and virtual reality experiences relies on a combination of hardware and software technologies.

Choosing the right immersive technology device is crucial but the technology could still be classed as being in its infancy with this making it difficult to get up to date and reliable information and as the market for immersive technology devices expands, it becomes increasingly important to understand the essential features and characteristics that define an effective and satisfactory immersive experience. Various studies have been conducted to evaluate the efficacy, satisfaction, and motivation associated with these immersive learning experiences. For instance, Stepan *et al.* (2017) focused on assessing the effectiveness of VR simulation in teaching medical students neuroanatomy. This study aimed to provide insights into the extent to which immersive VR simulations can enhance the students' understanding of complex neuroanatomical concepts, as well as their overall satisfaction and motivation levels. Stojšić, Ivkov-Džigurski and Maričić (2018) conducted a literature review of VR applications in education, emphasising both technological and pedagogical aspects, integration, and evaluation criteria. They also presented the results of a small qualitative study with teachers and an educational media specialist in the Republic of Serbia, who were familiar with using VR as a teaching tool. This study aimed to identify the most effective instructional strategies for guiding students during immersive virtual field trips (Cheng and Tsai, 2019). Serrano Vergel *et al.* (2020) acknowledged the challenges of selecting the appropriate 3-D technology or setup for specific problems within the medical field. Their comprehensive comparative study involving 82 participants examined two different 3-D interactive setups: an optical-based AR setup using a Microsoft HoloLens device and a semi-immersive setup based on a VR table. The findings from this study can serve as a valuable reference for selecting the optimal 3-D technology for various educational applications. Aracena, Fautier and Oyman (2020) analysed live VR workflows from an end-to-end perspective, including production, contribution, distribution, and consumption aspects. Their work explored how these workflows can complement traditional broadcast services, offering a 4K-like experience for viewers.

Steed *et al.* (2020) and Vega *et al.* (2020) investigated the status of community discussions surrounding the short-term, medium-term, and long-term implications of VR and AR technologies in education. Their research aimed to identify potential use cases and the required technological building blocks to support these applications. Atta, Romli and Majid (2021) attempted to answer the question of why AR is more effective than VR in preserving knowledge in learners' minds. Their study reviewed the most important theories and reports on AR in education and its connection to human spatial memory. This research highlighted the cognitive processes underpinning the effectiveness of AR in educational settings. Niu, Lo and Yu (2021) proposed a novel teaching framework that combines classroom learning with VR technology. Their work represents another influential study in this field, contributing to our understanding of the potential benefits of integrating VR and AR technologies into pedagogical practices (Bastug *et al.*, 2017).

When choosing an immersive technology device, educational facilities should consider display quality, comfort, performance and compatibility, input and control, content availability, price, and portability.

Choosing the right immersive technology device can provide an exciting and unique experience that blurs the lines between the physical and digital worlds. Here are some key factors to consider when selecting an immersive technology device:

- **Quality of Display:** Display quality is an important factor to consider when choosing an immersive technology device. The resolution of the device's display should be high enough to provide clear and sharp images. The field of view (FOV) should also be wide enough to provide an immersive experience. Higher FOV means a more immersive experience.
- **Comfort:** As immersive technology devices are often worn for extended periods, user comfort is a significant consideration. Factors such as weight, ergonomics, and fit should be assessed, as they can influence the user's willingness to engage with the technology. In addition, proper ventilation and adjustable straps can contribute to the overall comfort of the device. Some dissenting opinions argue that the current generation of immersive devices may be uncomfortable for some users, potentially limiting their widespread adoption. However, ongoing research and development in this domain are expected to yield more comfortable and ergonomic designs.
- **The performance of an immersive technology device is a critical determinant of the user's experience.** High-quality visuals and smooth rendering are essential for creating a realistic and engaging environment. To achieve this, devices should be equipped with powerful processors and graphics capabilities, capable of delivering high-resolution images at a consistent frame rate. Latency, or the time delay between user input and system response, should be minimized to prevent motion sickness and discomfort. Researchers should also consider the device's tracking accuracy and the responsiveness of its motion.
- **Input and Control:** Immersive technology devices require an input and control system. Consider the input and control options available and choose a device that offers the most natural and intuitive interaction methods. Look for devices that come with controllers or motion tracking devices that allow for natural hand gestures and movements.
- **Content Availability:** The availability of content is an essential factor to consider when choosing an immersive technology device with a diverse range of content is an essential factor to consider. Consider the amount of content available and whether it is relevant to your needs or interests. Look for a device that offers a wide range of content, including games, educational content, and other experiences. Additionally, developers should ensure that content is accessible to users with disabilities, conforming to universal design principles..
- **Price:** Immersive technology devices come in a wide range of prices. Determine the amount you are willing to spend on a device and choose one that fits your budget.
- **Portability:** The portability of an immersive technology device is an important factor to consider. Consider how easily the device can be transported and used in different environments.

- **Usability:** Ease of use is another crucial aspect to evaluate when selecting an immersive technology device. Devices should be designed with intuitive interfaces that enable users to navigate the virtual or augmented environment effortlessly. Furthermore, the device should be compatible with various platforms and operating systems, allowing for seamless integration with existing hardware and software ecosystems. In educational settings, for instance, devices should be adaptable to various pedagogical methods, facilitating smooth implementation into existing curricula.

When selecting and implementing immersive technology devices, stakeholders must carefully consider factors such as performance, usability, comfort, and content compatibility. A thorough understanding of these aspects can contribute to the successful integration of immersive technology devices into various fields, including education. Ultimately, the careful consideration and selection of immersive technology devices can pave the way for transformative experiences across a multitude of domains, unlocking the full potential of VR and AR technologies in shaping the future of human-computer interaction.

The research has found that a variety of hardware devices are available for creating AR and VR experiences, including head-mounted displays, mobile devices, and specialised peripherals. HMDs, manufactured by Meta, HTC, and Sony, are specifically designed for consumer VR experiences. These devices offer high-resolution displays, precise head-tracking, and integrated audio systems. Hardware is also produced for the enterprise market that may provide higher quality or specialised experiences. However, they can be expensive and may require a powerful computer and additional accessories to run smoothly. In contrast, mobile VR solutions like the Samsung Gear VR or Google Cardboard are more affordable and accessible but may offer lower-quality visuals and less accurate tracking. For AR experiences, devices like the Microsoft HoloLens and Magic Leap One offer sophisticated spatial mapping and gesture recognition capabilities. Mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, are also commonly used for AR applications due to their widespread availability and built-in cameras. However, these devices may be limited in processing power and may struggle to deliver high-quality, real-time AR experiences. Specialised peripherals, such as haptic gloves, motion controllers, and omnidirectional treadmills, can enhance the sense of immersion in AR and VR experiences. However, the cost and complexity of integrating these peripherals may pose challenges for developers and users.

Several hardware-related factors to ensure optimal user experience and interaction should be considered. Some of these key factors include:

- **Hardware Compatibility:** Developers should be familiar with the specific hardware requirements and limitations of the VR or AR platform they are targeting. This includes understanding the capabilities of the headset, controllers, sensors, and other peripherals.

Building for a wide range of devices may require adjustments and optimisations to accommodate different performance levels, input methods, and display resolutions.

- **Tracking and Sensing Technologies:** VR and AR platforms utilise various tracking and sensing technologies, such as inside-out tracking, outside-in tracking, or marker-based tracking. Developers should understand the nuances of these technologies to design experiences that make the best use of the platform's tracking capabilities while minimising any potential limitations or inaccuracies.
- **Latency and Frame Rate:** Ensuring low latency and a high frame rate is crucial for maintaining user comfort and immersion. Developers should optimise their applications to reduce rendering times and minimize latency, especially when targeting less powerful hardware. This may involve techniques such as level-of-detail (LOD) optimisation, efficient asset management, and optimising physics calculations.
- **Controller and Input Support:** Different VR and AR platforms may offer various input methods, including hand tracking, motion controllers, or traditional game controllers. Developers should design their experiences to support the input devices available on the target platform, creating intuitive and natural interaction mechanisms.
- **Haptic Feedback:** Some VR and AR hardware supports haptic feedback, providing users with tactile sensations that can enhance immersion. Developers should consider integrating haptic feedback into their experiences, ensuring that it is used effectively and meaningfully.
- **Display Characteristics:** Developers should be aware of the display characteristics of the targeted VR or AR devices, such as resolution, refresh rate, field of view, and stereoscopic rendering. Building experiences that accommodate these characteristics will ensure that the visuals are presented effectively and without distortion.
- **Power Consumption and Thermal Management:** VR and AR devices, especially standalone headsets or those powered by mobile devices, can have limitations in terms of power consumption and thermal management. Developers should optimise their applications to minimise power usage and prevent overheating, which could lead to device throttling or user discomfort.
- **Cross-platform Development:** If targeting multiple VR and AR platforms, developers should consider using cross-platform development tools and frameworks, such as Unity or Unreal Engine, to streamline development and ensure compatibility across various hardware configurations.
- By taking these hardware-related factors into account, developers can create immersive experiences that effectively leverage the unique capabilities of VR and AR platforms while ensuring compatibility, performance, and user comfort.

Developing AR and VR experiences also requires specialised software tools and platforms. Unity and Unreal Engine are popular game engines that offer robust support for AR and VR development, including built-in features, plugins, and libraries for handling rendering, physics, and user interaction. These engines are highly versatile and have extensive documentation and community support but may have a steep learning curve for beginners. AR development platforms like ARCore (Google) and ARKit (Apple) provide developers with frameworks for creating AR experiences on Android and iOS devices. These platforms offer features like environmental understanding, motion tracking, and light estimation, but may be limited to specific devices and operating systems.

Building an immersive experience for VR and AR involves careful consideration of several key elements:

- **Content design:** The narrative, storyline, or educational material must be engaging and relevant to the user's needs, goals, or interests. This includes creating high-quality visuals, interactive objects, and realistic environments.
- **User interface and interaction design:** Intuitive, user-friendly, and accessible interfaces are crucial in VR and AR experiences. The design should accommodate various input methods, such as hand gestures, gaze, voice commands, or controller inputs, to make the experience seamless and engaging.
- **Spatial audio:** Integrating spatial audio enhances the sense of immersion and presence in the virtual environment. It helps users understand their surroundings better and creates a more realistic experience.
- **Personalisation and adaptability:** Tailoring the experience to individual users or user groups increases engagement and relevance. This may involve adjusting the difficulty level, providing alternative content, or catering to different learning styles or preferences.
- **Multi-sensory integration:** Various sensory inputs can be employed to enhance the user's sense of presence and immersion in a virtual environment; for example, haptic feedback, as well as olfactory or thermal cues.
- **Interactivity and collaboration:** Enabling users to interact with the environment, objects, or other users promotes active engagement and enhances the overall experience. Collaboration can encourage teamwork, communication, and problem-solving in shared virtual spaces.
- **Accessibility and inclusivity:** Designing experiences that cater to users with different abilities and backgrounds ensures a broader audience can benefit from the VR or AR application. This includes incorporating features like adjustable text size, captions, or alternative navigation methods.

- Performance optimisation: Ensuring the VR or AR experience runs smoothly on various devices is critical to maintaining immersion. This involves optimising graphics, reducing latency, and maintaining a high frame rate.
- User safety and comfort: Addressing potential issues like motion sickness, eye strain, or disorientation is essential for a positive user experience. This can be achieved by implementing best practices in VR and AR design, such as limiting camera movement and providing clear navigation cues.
- Evaluation and feedback: Assessing the effectiveness of the immersive experience, gathering user feedback, and iterating the design helps improve and refine the application to better meet user needs and expectations.

Advancements in visual display technologies have significantly improved the quality and realism of virtual environments. These improvements have focused on several key aspects, including resolution, field of view (FOV), and focus cues. High-resolution displays, such as those presented by Huang et al. (2015), offer users a more detailed and realistic visual experience. By combining stereoscopic display principles with factored light field technology, a wearable VR display was developed that supports high image resolution and focus cues, enabling users to perceive depth and focus naturally in virtual environments (Huang *et al.*, 2015).

Field of view (FOV) is another important factor influencing the user experience in VR. A wide FOV enhances the sense of presence in the virtual environment but may also contribute to VR sickness. A trade-off between FOV and VR sickness has been explored by studying the effect of dynamically changing a user's FOV in response to visually perceived motion (Fernandes and Feiner, 2016). This approach has the potential to reduce VR sickness while maintaining a high level of immersion. In addition to the above factors, advances in head-mounted display (HMD) technology have led to more immersive and interactive experiences. For instance, it has been demonstrated the use of VR on the HTC Vive headset to interact with cell structures in a compelling immersive environment, highlights the potential applications of VR in scientific research and education (McGhee *et al.*, 2016).

Several studies have been found related to the development and application of virtual reality technology in various fields. (Robinett and Holloway, 1995) present a complete model for the visual display transformation for a VR system; that is, the series of transformations used to map points from object coordinates to screen coordinates. (Tweedie *et al.*, 1996) described two Interactive Visualisation Artifacts (IVAs) for engineering design: The Influence Explorer and The Projection Matrix. This data is often multivariate and increasingly, the datasets are very large. To help (Ellis and Dix, 2007) explore all this data, numerous visualisation applications, both commercial and research prototypes, have been designed using this variety of techniques and algorithms. Despite the progress in visualization and visual display technologies, several challenges remain in the field of VR. One

such challenge is the development of more efficient rendering techniques. (Boos, Chu and Cuervo, 2016) presented FLASHBACK, an unconventional VR head mounted display design that avoids real-time scene rendering. This approach may pave the way for more efficient and scalable VR systems. Continued research is needed to address issues related to user comfort and satisfaction, as well as the development of novel visualization techniques that can accommodate growing data complexity and volume.

Image 8-1 Exploded view of a typical VR headset. (Uncross those eyes: Researchers solve VR's depth-of-focus headaches | Ars Technica, no date)

Looking ahead, several emerging technologies could further advance the field of AR and VR development. For example, advancements in display technologies, such as microLED or light field displays, may offer higher resolutions, wider fields of view, and improved colour accuracy. Improvements in tracking and interaction technologies, such as eye tracking, brain-computer interfaces, or advanced haptics, could lead to more natural and intuitive user experiences.

Image 8-2 NVIDIA's new version of VR light field display appeared at the VRLA venue, the display principles of the old and new generations are quite different | T Kebang, (2016)

Developments in artificial intelligence and machine learning may enable more realistic and dynamic virtual environments, as well as improved spatial understanding and object recognition for AR

applications. Furthermore, the integration of 5G and edge computing technologies could enhance the performance and responsiveness of AR and VR experiences, particularly for mobile and cloud-based applications.

The implementation of immersive experiences for VR and AR platforms is a multifaceted process that requires careful consideration of numerous factors. Developers must be mindful of the hardware capabilities and limitations, tracking and sensing technologies, latency, frame rate, controller and input support, haptic feedback, display characteristics, power consumption, thermal management, and cross-platform development. By taking these factors into account and optimising the experience for the target platforms, developers can create engaging, interactive, and visually compelling applications that fully utilise the potential of VR and AR technologies.

It is currently difficult for the layperson to build an immersive experience although there are several resources and tools that have made VR and AR development more accessible to non-experts:

- **Game engines:** Platforms such as Unity and Unreal Engine offer built-in support for VR and AR development. These engines provide a user-friendly interface, extensive documentation, and a wealth of tutorials that can help beginners create immersive experiences with little to no prior knowledge in programming or 3D modelling.
- **SDKs and libraries:** Software development kits (SDKs) and libraries for popular VR and AR platforms, such as SteamVR, Oculus, and ARKit, simplify the development process by providing pre-built features and components that can be easily integrated into projects.
- **Online tutorials and courses:** There is an abundance of online resources, including tutorials, courses, and forums, that cater to different levels of expertise and guide newcomers through the process of creating immersive experiences.
- **Asset stores and marketplaces:** Online marketplaces, such as the Unity Asset Store or Unreal Engine Marketplace, offer a variety of pre-built assets, including 3D models, animations, and scripts, that can be used to speed up the development process and reduce the need for specialised skills.

The future of democratisation in VR and AR technology is promising. As hardware becomes more affordable and software tools continue to evolve, we can expect an increase in the number of people who can create and consume immersive experiences. This is likely to lead to more diverse content and applications, as well as foster innovation and collaboration among developers, artists, and enthusiasts.

Additionally, the integration of AI and machine learning tools into the development process may further simplify the creation of immersive experiences, enabling users with limited technical skills to generate high-quality content. Furthermore, advancements in cloud computing and edge processing could make it easier for developers to create and deploy resource-intensive VR and AR experiences on a wider

range of devices, enhancing accessibility for users across the globe. There are already user-friendly tools within some VR applications that utilise graphical user interfaces for a player of the experience to build elements within these virtual worlds. Horizon Worlds, VRChat, and Rec Room are platforms that enable users to create, share, and explore virtual worlds and experiences using built-in creation tools. Each platform offers a unique set of tools and features that cater to different user needs and preferences.

- Horizon Worlds (Meta Quest, 2022) (formerly Facebook Horizon): Developed by Meta (formerly Facebook), Horizon Worlds is a social VR platform that allows users to create, explore, and interact with others in a virtual environment. The platform provides an in-world creation tool known as the World Builder, which enables users to design and build their own virtual worlds using a variety of 3D objects, materials, and interactive elements. The World Builder is designed to be intuitive and easy to use, even for users with no prior experience in 3D modelling or programming. Users can also collaborate with others in real-time, allowing for a more dynamic and social creation experience. Additionally, Horizon Worlds supports scripting using the visual scripting language called Horizon Script, which allows creators to add interactivity and logic to their worlds without requiring traditional coding knowledge.

Image 8-3 Horizon Worlds scripting tools. (Heath, 2023)

- VRChat (VRChat, nd) is a popular social VR platform that lets users create and share custom virtual worlds, avatars, and experiences. The platform relies on external tools like Unity and the VRChat SDK to create content, allowing for a higher degree of flexibility and customisation compared to other platforms. Users can import 3D models, animations, and other assets into Unity, and then use the VRChat SDK to add interactivity, custom scripts, and other elements

necessary for the virtual world. This approach, however, requires a certain level of familiarity with Unity and programming concepts, making it more suitable for users with some experience in game development or 3D design.

- Rec Room (*Rec Room, nd*) is a social VR platform that focuses on user-generated content, including games, activities, and custom rooms. The platform features an in-game creation tool called the Maker Pen, which allows users to create 3D objects, environments, and interactive elements directly within the virtual space. The Maker Pen is designed to be accessible and easy to use, with a simple interface and a variety of pre-built shapes, materials, and gadgets to choose from. Users can also add interactivity and logic to their creations using Circuits, a visual scripting system that simplifies programming concepts for non-experts. Rec Room's focus on accessibility makes it an ideal platform for users who are new to VR development or those who want to create content quickly and easily

Image 8-4 Rec Room MakerPen. (How to Creative Tutorials — Rec Room, no date)

Therefore, Horizon Worlds, VRChat, and Rec Room each offer unique creation tools that cater to different levels of expertise and preferences. While Horizon Worlds and Rec Room emphasise

accessibility and ease of use with their in-world creation tools, VRChat provides more advanced customisation options through the use of Unity and the VRChat SDK. These platforms enable users to create and share a wide variety of immersive experiences, encouraging creativity and community-building within the virtual space.

As the field of VR and AR continues to evolve, it is essential for developers to stay updated on emerging trends, new hardware capabilities, and advancements in software tools and frameworks. By staying informed and adapting to these changes, developers can ensure that their immersive experiences remain cutting-edge, relevant, and accessible to a growing user base. Ultimately, the successful creation of immersive experiences in VR and AR hinges on the developer's ability to balance technical considerations with a deep understanding of user needs and expectations, resulting in innovative and captivating experiences that push the boundaries of these rapidly developing technologies.

8.4 Immersive Computer Science Education

In recent years, the use of AR and VR has gained momentum in various fields, including education. AR and VR technologies provide new avenues for enhancing the learning experience by providing a highly interactive and immersive environment. This section will focus on the potential of AR and VR technologies in learning computer science. Exploring how AR and VR experiences can be designed to provide an engaging and effective learning experience in computer science education.

8.4.1 AR and VR Experiences in Computer Science Education

AR and VR technologies offer several advantages in computer science education (Lanier, 2017). One of the primary benefits is that they provide a highly immersive and interactive learning experience (Ryan, 2015). With AR and VR technologies, students can explore complex concepts and theories in a more engaging and interactive manner. For instance, AR and VR experiences can be designed to enable students to visualise and manipulate three-dimensional models of computer systems, networks, and algorithms. This approach can help students to understand complex concepts better than traditional approaches that rely on textbooks and lectures.

Highly Immersive and interactive learning experiences:

Benefits:

- Enhanced engagement: Immersive and interactive learning experiences provided by AR and VR technologies can increase student engagement, as they offer more captivating and stimulating environments than traditional learning methods.
- Improved retention: Studies have shown that immersive learning experiences can lead to better information retention, as students are more likely to remember what they have learned when they can actively participate in the learning process (Javornik *et al.*, 2018).
- Personalised learning: AR and VR technologies can be tailored to individual students' needs, allowing for customised learning experiences that cater to different learning styles and preferences.
- Collaboration and teamwork: Immersive and interactive learning experiences can promote collaboration and teamwork among students, as they work together to solve problems and complete tasks within the virtual environment (Pan *et al.*, 2006).

Weaknesses:

- Cost and accessibility: The implementation of AR and VR technologies can be expensive, potentially making it difficult for schools and institutions with limited budgets to adopt these technologies (Abriata, 2020).
- Technical limitations: Current AR and VR technologies may have limitations in terms of graphics, user interface, and interaction capabilities, which can negatively impact the overall learning experience (Hanson and Shelton, 2008).
- Learning curve: Students and educators may need to invest time in learning how to effectively use AR and VR technologies, which could detract from the time spent on learning the actual subject matter.
- Dependence on technology: Overreliance on immersive and interactive learning experiences may reduce the importance of traditional learning methods, such as reading and writing, potentially hindering the development of essential skills (Blyth, 2018).

Another advantage of AR and VR technologies in computer science education is that they provide students with a safe and risk-free environment to practice their skills (Stuckless, Hogan and Kapralos, 2014). For instance, in programming courses, AR and VR experiences can be designed to provide a simulated environment where students can write and test code without risking damage to real systems. This approach can help students to gain practical experience in programming while minimising the risk of errors and system failures.

Safe and risk-free environment for skill practice:

Benefits:

- Error tolerance: AR and VR technologies provide a simulated environment in which students can practice their skills without fear of causing damage or making irreversible mistakes, encouraging a growth mindset and inspiring experimentation (Herbst *et al.*, 2021).

- Realistic scenarios: Immersive environments can accurately replicate real-world scenarios, allowing students to gain practical experience and improve their problem-solving abilities in a controlled setting (Albeaino *et al.*, 2022).
- Immediate feedback: AR and VR technologies can provide instant feedback on students' performance, enabling them to learn from their mistakes and make adjustments more quickly than in traditional learning environments (Simonetti *et al.*, 2020).
- Reduced risk: By practising in a virtual environment, students can develop their skills without the risks associated with real-world situations, such as damage to equipment or harm to others (Bosché, Abdel-Wahab and Carozza, 2016).

Weaknesses:

- Limited scenarios: While AR and VR technologies can simulate a wide range of scenarios, they may not cover every possible situation that students might encounter in the real world.
- Overemphasis on technology: Relying solely on simulated environments for skill practice may lead to an overemphasis on technology, neglecting the importance of hands-on experience with real-world equipment and systems.
- Loss of human interaction: Practicing skills in a virtual environment may reduce the opportunities for students to interact with instructors and peers, potentially hindering the development of interpersonal skills and collaborative problem-solving abilities (Schulz, Isabwe and Reichert, 2015).
- Technical issues: Technical problems with AR and VR hardware and software can disrupt the learning experience and potentially hinder skill development.

Balancing the use of AR and VR with traditional learning methods can help ensure that students gain a well-rounded education and develop the necessary skills for success in their chosen field.

AR and VR technologies can also help to bridge the gap between theory and practice in computer science education. With AR and VR technologies, students can visualise and interact with complex concepts and systems, making it easier to relate theoretical concepts to real-world applications. This approach can help students to develop a deeper understanding of how computer systems work and how they can be used to solve real-world problems.

The integration of AR and VR technologies in computer science education has shown promising potential in enhancing learning outcomes compared to traditional methods. As these immersive technologies become more widely accessible, it is important to recognise how they can be effectively implemented to improve computer science education, specifically in learning to program. One of the most significant advantages of AR and VR technologies is their ability to create immersive and interactive learning experiences, capturing students' attention and stimulating their curiosity. This heightened engagement can lead to increased motivation to learn programming concepts and a deeper

understanding of the subject matter. Through these technologies, complex programming concepts can be visualised in three-dimensional space, making abstract ideas more accessible and intuitive for students. In addition to improved engagement, AR and VR technologies promote experiential learning by allowing students to apply their knowledge in practical, real-world scenarios. Simulated environments offer a safe space for students to experiment, test, and refine their programming skills without the risk of causing damage to actual systems. This hands-on learning approach provides valuable practical experience that traditional methods, such as lectures and textbooks, may lack.

Furthermore, AR and VR technologies can provide personalised learning experiences tailored to individual students' needs and preferences. Adaptive content and real-time feedback enable students to progress at their own pace, focusing on areas where they need improvement in their programming abilities. These technologies can also enhance collaboration and communication among students and between students and instructors, providing shared virtual spaces where they can work together, discuss ideas, and solve programming problems collectively.

Despite the advantages of AR and VR technologies in computer science education, it is essential to recognise that these technologies may not be a one-size-fits-all solution. Different students have different learning styles and preferences, and some may still benefit from traditional methods. Additionally, access to AR and VR technologies may be limited for some students due to socioeconomic factors. Therefore, a blended approach may be to combine the best of both traditional and technology-driven methods might be the most effective way to enhance learning outcomes in computer science education, specifically in learning to program. By leveraging the strengths of AR and VR technologies while acknowledging their limitations, educators can create a more engaging, interactive, and effective learning experience for students in the field of computer science.

8.4.2 Designing AR and VR Experiences for Computer Science Education

Designing effective AR and VR experiences for computer science education requires careful consideration of several factors. One of the key considerations is the learning objectives of the experience. The experience should be designed to support specific learning objectives, such as understanding programming concepts or developing problem-solving skills. Learning objectives play a critical role in designing AR and VR experiences tailored for computer science education. When these experiences are specifically designed to support learning objectives such as understanding programming concepts or developing problem-solving skills, they can enhance the educational outcomes and make the learning process more engaging and efficient (Pink, Ardèvol and Lanzeni, 2016).

In the context of computer science education, focusing on learning objectives allows developers to create experiences that address specific areas of the subject matter. For instance, an AR or VR experience can be designed to teach students a particular programming language like JavaScript or C#. The immersive environment can enable them to visualise and manipulate code, allowing them to understand the syntax, structure, and flow of the language which may be better than traditional methods like textbooks or lectures. One significant benefit of aligning AR and VR experiences with learning objectives is that it can lead to improved retention of information and a deeper understanding of complex concepts (Souza *et al.*, 2020). For example, an AR experience might help students visualise how a sorting algorithm works, enabling them to see the steps and processes involved in sorting data more clearly. This immersive and interactive approach can facilitate a more intuitive understanding of the algorithm compared to reading about it in a book or hearing about it in a lecture.

Image 8-5 Engage VR virtual classroom. (Engage VR Review 2019 December – ancient backstage, 2019)

However, there is also a potential weakness in tailoring AR and VR experiences too narrowly to specific learning objectives. If the focus is too narrow, the experience may not provide students with a comprehensive understanding of the broader context in which the programming concepts or problem-solving skills are applied. This could limit their ability to adapt their knowledge and skills to real-world situations and different programming challenges. To overcome this weakness, it is essential to design AR and VR experiences that strike a balance between targeting specific learning objectives and providing a broader context for the application of the acquired knowledge and skills.

Another important consideration is the user interface and interaction design. The user interface should be intuitive and easy to use, allowing students to focus on the learning objectives rather than struggling with the technology. The interaction design should also be carefully designed to provide an engaging and immersive experience while ensuring that the experience supports the learning objectives. Designing engaging and immersive interactions further enhances the learning process, helping students to better understand and retain complex concepts.

For computer science education, having an intuitive user interface and well-designed interactions can make a significant difference in the learning process (Zucchi *et al.*, 2020). For example, an AR or VR experience for teaching programming concepts can offer a user-friendly interface where students can easily input, edit, and manipulate code, allowing them to experiment and learn without being overwhelmed or frustrated by the technology. Immersive interactions, such as the ability to navigate through a 3D representation of a data structure or algorithm, can provide students with a more engaging and memorable learning experience. The benefits of intuitive user interfaces and engaging interactions in computer science education are many, they can lead to improved comprehension of complex concepts, increased motivation, and more efficient learning. For instance, students might be more likely to spend time working on a programming problem in an immersive VR environment that offers instant feedback and visually appealing representations of the code they are writing.

However, there are potential weaknesses associated with focusing too heavily on user interface and interaction design. One possible drawback is that creating sophisticated interfaces and interactions can be resource-intensive and time-consuming, which may lead to higher development costs and longer development times (Crandall *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, there is a risk of overemphasising the visual and interactive elements at the expense of the underlying learning objectives. This could result in experiences that are visually impressive but do not provide the depth of knowledge and understanding required for effective computer science education (Cummings and Bailenson, 2016). To strike the right balance, it is essential to prioritise the learning objectives and ensure that the user interface and interaction design serve to support and enhance these objectives, rather than overshadow them. By doing so, AR and VR experiences can provide significant benefits to computer science education, making learning more engaging, effective, and enjoyable for students.

Content design plays a pivotal role in developing effective AR and VR experiences for computer science education. It is essential to create content that supports learning objectives and is engaging and relevant to students. This is particularly important in programming courses, where practical examples and exercises should be relatable to real-world applications, allowing students to see the applicability of the concepts they are learning (Kolb and Kolb, 2014). Well-designed content can make a significant difference in the learning process in the framework for computer science education. For example, an AR or VR experience designed to teach algorithm design can provide students with real-world scenarios

that require the application of specific algorithms. By working through these scenarios, students can gain a deeper understanding of the algorithm's purpose and functionality while learning how to implement it in practice. Content that is relevant, engaging, and tied to real-world applications can lead to improved comprehension, increased motivation, and better retention of concepts (Chiang, Yang and Hwang, 2014). For instance, students might be more likely to remember a sorting algorithm they learned in an immersive VR environment where they had to sort virtual objects by interacting with them directly, rather than simply reading about the algorithm in a textbook. There is a risk of focusing too much on the impressiveness of the content at the expense of the underlying learning objectives, resulting in experiences that are visually impressive but lack depth and substance. It is essential to prioritise the learning objectives and ensure that the content design serves to support and enhance these objectives, rather than overshadow them. Additionally, incorporating feedback from students and educators during the development process can help ensure that the content is relevant, engaging, and effective. By doing so, AR and VR experiences can provide significant benefits to computer science education, making learning more engaging, effective, and enjoyable for students.

Assessing the effectiveness of AR and VR experiences in computer science education involves considering several factors, such as learning outcomes, engagement, satisfaction, and the transferability of skills learned to real-world applications. Evaluating the effectiveness of these experiences is crucial in determining their overall impact on student learning and growth. The transferability of skills learned in AR and VR experiences is particularly important in this field. For example, an AR or VR experience designed to teach programming concepts should provide students with the necessary skills and knowledge to develop real-world applications, such as creating web applications, mobile apps, or software systems. The benefits of effectively assessing AR and VR experiences in computer science education include:

- Ensuring that the learning objectives are met: By assessing learning outcomes, educators can determine whether students have successfully grasped the intended concepts and developed the necessary skills (Dimitropoulos, Manitsaris and Mavridis, 2008).
- Evaluating student engagement and satisfaction: Monitoring engagement and satisfaction levels can help identify areas where improvements may be needed, ensuring that the experiences are both enjoyable and educationally effective (Zhang and Issa, 2015).
- Measuring the transferability of skills: By assessing the extent to which students can apply the skills learned in AR and VR experiences to real-world applications, educators can determine the practical value of these experiences (Ryan *et al.*, 2022).

However, as found in many other teaching paradigms there are potential weaknesses associated with assessing the effectiveness with one possible challenge to determine the appropriate assessment methods and metrics, as traditional assessment tools, such as written exams or quizzes, may not fully

capture the learning outcomes achieved in immersive environments. Developing new assessment methods that accurately evaluate learning in AR and VR experiences can be time-consuming and may require additional resources.

Another potential weakness is that measuring the transferability of skills can be complex, as it involves assessing the extent to which students can apply the knowledge and skills gained in AR and VR experiences to real-world situations. This may require long-term tracking of students' performance in related tasks and projects, which can be resource intensive. While there are potential challenges and weaknesses associated with this process, developing appropriate assessment methods and focusing on the transferability of skills can help ensure that these experiences provide significant benefits to computer science education.

In conclusion, AR and VR technologies provide a new and exciting avenue for enhancing computer science education. These technologies offer several advantages, including providing an immersive and interactive learning experience, a safe environment for practicing skills, and bridging the gap between theory and practice. Designing effective AR and VR experiences for computer science education requires careful consideration of the learning objectives, user interface and interaction design, and content design. Assessing the effectiveness of AR and VR experiences in computer science education requires consideration of the learning outcomes, engagement and satisfaction of the students, and transferability of the skills learned.

8.4.3 Accessibility

Despite the importance of these technologies, there is a lack of research focusing on their usefulness and ease of use for users and cultural content providers (Loumos, Kargas and Varoutas, 2018) with the research landscape surrounding the accessibility of AR/VR technologies still relatively small. However, various studies have begun to assess the potential benefits and challenges associated with their implementation. This analysis delves into the current state of research in the field and highlights the contributions of various researchers to assess and improve the implementation of AR/VR technologies.

Accessibility and inclusivity are critical concerns when integrating VR into education. Students with physical or cognitive disabilities may face difficulties engaging with immersive content, and not all students may have equal access to the necessary hardware and software.

To promote accessibility and inclusivity in AR/VR education, the following steps can be taken:

- Ensuring that educational VR content adheres to accessibility guidelines and standards, such as the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG).

- Developing adaptive VR experiences that can accommodate diverse learning needs and abilities.
- Exploring alternative and affordable VR solutions, such as smartphone-based VR headsets, to increase access for students in under-resourced schools.

Several keynote speeches and demonstrations from industry giants such as Microsoft, Google, and Verizon, as well as leading academic institutions, have been instrumental in showcasing the latest accessibility research in the field (Biswas, Segedy and Bunchongchit, 2016). Khomtchouk (2021) highlights the potential of Web Assembly (Wasm) as a developer solution that can deliver near-native low latency performance for web-based applications, thus enabling hardware-agnostic interoperability on a large scale through portable bytecode compatible with any WiFi or cellular data network-enabled AR/VR device. In an effort to provide a systematic insight into the current maturity of AR/VR technologies in operations and supply chain management (OSCM), Akbari, Ha and Kok (2022) analysed the existing literature, modern concepts, data, and identified gaps for future research directions. Lastly, Susloparov, Krasilov and Khorov (2022) propose a Delay-Based Traffic Balancing (DBTB) algorithm that minimizes resource consumption of low-frequency links while adhering to strict AR/VR quality of service (QoS) requirements.

As the adoption of AR/VR technologies continues to grow, it is vital to ensure that these immersive experiences remain inclusive and accessible for individuals with disabilities. To this end, several research directions and strategies can be pursued to maximise inclusivity and cater to the unique needs of users with various impairments.

Firstly, guidelines and best practices for designing accessible AR/VR applications need to be established and refined. Researchers should explore how principles from the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) can be adapted and applied to immersive environments (Heilemann, Zimmermann and Münster, 2021). The development of new guidelines tailored to AR/VR experiences should be grounded in empirical research and inclusive design principles, taking into account the specific challenges faced by users with disabilities, such as limited mobility, visual or auditory impairments, and cognitive differences (Biswas, Segedy and Bunchongchit, 2016; Biswas *et al.*, 2021).

Secondly, the development of novel input modalities and interaction techniques can help accommodate the diverse needs of users with disabilities. For instance, researchers should investigate how voice commands, haptic feedback, and gesture recognition can be integrated into AR/VR experiences to offer alternative means of interaction and navigation for users with limited motor skills or sensory impairments (Kaimaris *et al.*, 2021).

It is also crucial to involve users with disabilities in the design and evaluation process of AR/VR technologies. Participatory design methodologies can ensure that the perspectives and experiences of

these users are adequately represented and accounted for when developing new applications and interfaces (Nersesian, 2020). By actively involving users with disabilities in the design process, researchers can better understand the specific needs and preferences of this population, resulting in more accessible and inclusive AR/VR experiences.

Furthermore, research should also focus on the development of adaptive and personalised AR/VR environments. An environment that can dynamically adjust to the individual needs and preferences of users with disabilities, offering tailored experiences that accommodate their unique limitations and capabilities (Rambach *et al.*, 2021). Machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques can be employed to analyse user behaviour and preferences, enabling the creation of personalised and adaptable immersive environments (Susloparov, Krasilov and Khorov, 2022).

Finally, it is important to raise awareness and promote the importance of accessibility and inclusivity within the AR/VR development community. This can be achieved through workshops, conferences, and publications that emphasise the need for accessible design and highlight innovative approaches to fostering inclusivity in immersive environments (Loumos, Kargas and Varoutas, 2018).

8.4.4 Guidelines for Educators

The sum of all these considerations is that with advent of immersive technologies like Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) has opened new horizons in education, particularly in the field of computer science. Here is a framework designed to guide educators in effectively integrating these technologies into their teaching practices. It aims to harness the potential of VR and AR to enhance learning experiences, making complex concepts more accessible and engaging. Rooted in sound pedagogical theories and addressing practical challenges, this framework provides a comprehensive roadmap for educators to navigate the integration of immersive technologies in their curriculum, ensuring that these innovative tools are utilized to their fullest potential in shaping the future of education.

- **Pedagogical Foundations:** Begin with a clear understanding of educational theories such as constructivism, situated cognition, and experiential learning. These theories provide a basis for using immersive technologies like VR and AR to create engaging, interactive learning experiences.
- **Curriculum Integration:** Design curriculum plans that integrate immersive technologies effectively. This involves identifying subjects and topics where VR and AR can enhance understanding, such as complex abstract concepts in computer science.

- **Technology Selection and Implementation:** Educators must choose the right technology based on learning objectives, budget, and infrastructure capabilities. Considerations include hardware requirements, software compatibility, and ease of use for both teachers and students.
- **Developing Content and Learning Activities:** Create or source educational content that is specifically designed for immersive environments. This includes simulations, interactive exercises, and gamified elements that align with learning goals.
- **Training and Professional Development:** Provide training for educators to familiarise them with the technology, its educational applications, and best practices for classroom integration.
- **Assessment and Evaluation:** Develop assessment tools that accurately measure learning outcomes in immersive learning environments. This could include traditional assessments adapted for VR/AR settings and new metrics that leverage the unique capabilities of these technologies.
- **Addressing Accessibility and Inclusivity:** Ensure that the implementation of VR and AR in education is accessible to all students, including those with disabilities. Explore adaptive technologies and design learning experiences that are inclusive and equitable.
- **Managing Challenges:** Address common challenges such as high costs, technical issues, and the potential for cognitive overload. Develop strategies to mitigate these challenges, such as phased implementation, shared resources, and careful content design.
- **Continuous Review and Adaptation:** Implement a process for regular review and adaptation of the technology and teaching methods. Stay abreast of advances in immersive technology and pedagogy to continually enhance the learning experience.
- **Collaboration and Community Building:** Foster collaboration among educators, developers, and researchers in the field of immersive technology in education. Encourage sharing of best practices, resources, and research findings.

This framework provides a comprehensive guide for educators looking to incorporate immersive technologies into their teaching practices. It emphasises the need for a balanced approach that considers pedagogical theories, technological capabilities, content development, and continuous adaptation to evolving educational needs and technological advancements.

9 Conclusions

This Ph.D. thesis, "Analysis of the Application of Immersive Technologies and Gamification to Computer Science Education" aims to explore the efficacy of virtual reality and other immersive technologies as educational tools in the field of computer science. The primary objective of this research has been to examine the potential benefits of implementing immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education to enhance student engagement, learning outcomes, and knowledge retention.

The thesis has been structured to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state of immersive technology, including virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality, as well as the emerging technologies converging in the metaverse. It delves into the pedagogical implications of these technologies in various educational settings and examines the role of gamification and game-based learning in education.

This research identifies several key trends in the application of VR, AR, and MR in education. Immersive technologies have demonstrated their potential to enhance learning experiences, empower learners through personalised educational tools, and break the barriers of distance education. Additionally, the research has explored the implications of these technologies in various educational settings, such as science laboratories and virtual classrooms, and has examined the factors influencing the choice of immersive technology devices for education.

9.1 Key Contributions and Findings

This research identifies several key trends in the application of VR, AR, and MR in education. Immersive technologies have demonstrated their potential to enhance learning experiences, empower learners through personalised educational tools, and break the barriers of distance education. Additionally, the research has explored the implications of these technologies in various educational settings, such as science laboratories and virtual classrooms, and has examined the factors influencing the choice of immersive technology devices for education.

Gamification and game-based learning have been found to be effective in improving student engagement and learning outcomes across various subjects, including computer science. The research has examined the pedagogical applications of virtual reality in education, outlining the potential benefits and challenges of using immersive technology in educational settings.

This thesis provided a comprehensive analysis of the application of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education. The key achievements of the research include:

- Investigating the potential of immersive technologies, such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR), for enhancing teaching and learning in computer science.
- Exploring the use of gamification and game-based learning elements to increase engagement, motivation, and knowledge retention in computer science education.
- Evaluating the effectiveness of immersive technology in various educational settings, including distance education, personalised learning, and accessibility.
- Developing frameworks for the implementation of immersive gamification and technology use in computer science education, addressing challenges and providing practical guidelines for educators.
- Conducting experimental studies, including the comparison of VR and traditional screen environments for interaction, a systematic review of VR applications for education, and the development and evaluation of a VR game for teaching programming concepts.
- Identifying the need for further research and development in the field of immersive technology and gamification in computer science education, to refine best practices and explore new pedagogical approaches.

The thesis demonstrated the promising potential of immersive technologies and gamification in revolutionising computer science education, offering insights and recommendations for educators and researchers aiming to harness the power of these emerging tools to create engaging, interactive, and effective learning experiences for students.

9.1.1 Theoretical Contributions

This research significantly contributes to and challenges existing theories in educational technology and computer science education. By exploring the integration of immersive technologies in educational settings, it aligns with constructivist theories, emphasising active, experiential learning. The findings reinforce the constructivist view that learning is enhanced in interactive and engaging environments, as provided by VR and AR technologies. Moreover, the research contributes to the evolving understanding of gamification in education. It supports the theory that gamification can improve motivation and learning outcomes, as posited by Deterding et al. (2011), but also highlights the need for careful design to align with educational objectives.

In the realm of computer science education, the study challenges traditional pedagogical approaches, advocating for more innovative and interactive methods. It aligns with Papert's (1980) theory of constructionism, suggesting that students learn best when they are actively involved in constructing tangible objects in the real world or through digital means. The research contributes to a deeper understanding of how immersive technologies can be effectively integrated into education, providing

empirical evidence that supports and extends existing theories in educational technology and computer science education.

9.2 Critical Evaluation of Research Limitations

In this PhD thesis, the researcher acknowledges the limitations and potential biases to present a more balanced view of the results, demonstrating a transparent and critical approach to the research process, and inviting further exploration of the topics studied. Several studies conducted within the scope of this thesis have shed light on the potential applications of immersive technology and gamification in computer science education.

9.2.1 Study 1:

The first study, "Virtual Reality vs Pancake environments: Immersive & traditional screens interface interaction comparison," compares user interactions in virtual reality environments with those in traditional flat-screen environments. The study reveals that participants are open to using VR to explore virtual spaces and interact with the environment in unconventional ways, such as using their whole bodies to interact. The research also highlights the need to develop best practice conventions for the emerging field of VR education. The study's main findings revealed that participants felt more engaged and immersed in the 3D virtual environment, largely due to the sense of presence provided by VR technology. The study identified several advantages of VR environments over flat screen environments. One advantage is the heightened sense of presence in VR, which can lead to more engaging and memorable experiences. Another advantage is the greater sense of agency and control VR offers, enabling users to interact with objects and manipulate their surroundings in ways not possible in pancake environments. This can be particularly useful in education and training, where users need to practice complex tasks or procedures in a safe, controlled environment.

However, the study also acknowledged some limitations and challenges associated with VR environments, such as discomfort or motion sickness experienced by some users and the cost and technical requirements of creating high-quality VR experiences. In contrast, pancake environments are generally more accessible, less expensive, and easier to use. The study concluded that while VR has shown promising results as a more effective learning tool than traditional pancake environments, further research is needed to draw definitive conclusions and identify best practices for using VR in different educational and training contexts. It also emphasized the importance of considering the limitations and challenges associated with VR when deciding whether to implement the technology in a given setting.

9.2.2 Study 2:

The second study, "A systematic review of virtual reality applications for education," investigates the current landscape of VR applications for education available to educators, students, and the general public. The study uncovers several trends in VR applications for education, such as the prevalence of experiential learning theory and the use of declarative knowledge and realistic surroundings to deliver learning outcomes. The research identifies 307 VR applications for education, demonstrating the growing diversity of subject matter being developed and delivered using immersive technology. The review found a wide variety of VR applications covering various subjects such as science, history, art, and language learning. Most applications were single-player experiences, aimed at all ages, with few multiplayer options or applications tailored to specific age ranges. The applications were classified based on learning theory, content, and design elements, providing insights into the features and learning outcomes of each application. The study concluded that VR applications in education are still in an experimental stage, offering exciting ways to present subjects to students but not yet ready for meaningful inclusion in curricula. Technological advancements in immersion, such as haptic feedback, field of view, and screen resolution, are necessary to enhance the user experience. Overall, this comprehensive review provides valuable insights for educators and developers looking to incorporate VR applications in their educational settings.

9.2.3 Study 3:

Lastly, the study "MoonBase VR: Learning to program in a virtual reality game" explores the potential of using VR games to teach programming concepts to novice learners. The research demonstrates an interest in learning programming within a VR game setting, indicating that immersive technology can be a viable tool for teaching computer science concepts. The study contributes to the broader understanding of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education. MoonBase VR is a virtual reality game that allows players to build and program robots to perform tasks on a lunar base. The study aimed to investigate the usability of manipulating code blocks within a virtual reality game and the participants' perceptions of using a VR game to learn programming. The research involved 40 participants who completed pre- and post-experience questionnaires and a NASA-TLX survey to assess workload. The findings revealed that most participants found the VR game to be a fun and engaging way to learn programming, which increased their interest in computer science. The study highlights the potential of VR technology to enhance learning outcomes and bring excitement to computer science education. However, further empirical research and application development are needed to fully realise the game's potential.

9.2.4 Limitations:

- **Sample size and diversity:** The thesis might have a limited sample size or lack diversity in the participants' age, educational background, or prior experience with technology. This limitation may affect the generalisability of the findings, making it difficult to apply the results to a broader population.
- **Access to technology:** The thesis may assume that all participants have equal access to immersive technologies and equipment, which might not be true in reality. This can lead to an overestimation of the potential benefits of immersive technologies in computer science education.
- **Short-term focus:** The thesis may focus on the short-term effects of using immersive technologies in education, which might not provide a complete picture of their long-term impact on learning outcomes and retention.
- **Experimental settings:** Studies conducted within the thesis in controlled experimental settings might not fully represent real-world classroom environments. This limitation could affect the transferability of the results to actual educational contexts.
- **Research design:** The research design used in the thesis may have some inherent limitations, such as the use of self-reported data, which could be subject to social desirability bias, or the lack of a control group, which might hinder the ability to draw causal conclusions.

9.2.5 Potential biases and gaps:

- **Selection bias:** The participants in the studies included in the thesis might not be representative of the target population, leading to selection bias. This can limit the external validity of the research findings.
- **Confirmation bias:** The researcher may have unconsciously favoured data or results that support their hypothesis, leading to confirmation bias. It is essential to remain aware of this potential bias and ensure a rigorous, unbiased analysis of the data.
- **Publication bias:** The thesis may include studies with significant or positive findings, while studies with non-significant or negative findings might be underrepresented. This can lead to an overestimation of the effectiveness of immersive technologies in computer science education.

Addressing these limitations and potential biases, the researcher encourages further exploration of the topics studied. Future research could focus on larger and more diverse samples, longitudinal studies to

assess long-term effects, and real-world classroom implementations. By being transparent and critical about the research process, the researcher contributes to a more robust and reliable body of knowledge on the use of immersive technologies in computer science education.

9.3 Implications for Practice

Based on the findings from the studies and the comprehensive analysis of the literature, the thesis presents several conclusions and implications for the application of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education. First, immersive technologies, such as VR, AR, and MR, have the potential to revolutionise computer science education by providing engaging, interactive, and immersive learning experiences. These technologies can enhance learning outcomes, improve student engagement, and reinforce knowledge retention.

Secondly, gamification and game-based learning can be effectively integrated into computer science education to further enhance the learning process. By incorporating game-like elements, such as puzzles and challenges, into the teaching of programming concepts, educators can make learning more enjoyable and interactive for students. Gamification and game-based learning have been found to be effective in improving student engagement and learning outcomes across various subjects, including computer science. The research has examined the pedagogical applications of virtual reality in education, outlining the potential benefits and challenges of using immersive technology in educational settings. However, the implementation of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education requires careful planning and consideration of various factors, such as the choice of technology devices, the development of best practice conventions, and the suitability of these tools for different learners and learning frameworks. While VR games and other immersive tools show promise in teaching programming concepts, they should not be viewed as replacements for traditional teaching methods but rather as complementary tools that can be integrated into the overall learning experience. Furthermore, the research highlights the importance of tailoring educational experiences using immersive technology to cater to the diverse needs of learners, with special attention to accessibility and inclusivity. In this regard, educators must consider the varying levels of technological literacy and cognitive abilities of students to ensure that immersive tools are effectively utilised in the learning process.

The application of immersive technology in distance education offers new opportunities for bridging the gap between remote learners and on-campus students. By leveraging the capabilities of virtual classrooms, virtual meeting spaces, and other immersive tools, educational institutions can provide more equitable access to high-quality computer science education for students across the globe.

The research findings have significant implications for various stakeholders, including educators, administrators, policymakers, and developers. Educators can leverage the insights gained from these studies to design more engaging and effective learning experiences using immersive technologies like VR. By incorporating VR applications and games into their teaching methods, educators can improve knowledge retention, provide a safe and controlled environment for learning, and increase students' interest in computer science. Furthermore, educators can tailor VR experiences to address different learning styles and preferences, catering to a diverse range of students. Administrators and policymakers can use the findings to integrate immersive technologies into existing curricula and allocate resources for their implementation. By understanding the potential benefits and limitations of VR technology in education, administrators can make informed decisions about the feasibility of adopting VR in their institutions. This might involve investing in the necessary hardware and software, providing training for educators, and developing strategies to ensure that VR technology is accessible to all students. Policymakers can also explore the possibility of incorporating VR applications and games as supplementary materials to traditional computer science courses, ensuring that students receive a well-rounded education.

Developers of VR applications and games can utilise the research findings to create more effective educational tools that address the needs of students and educators. By incorporating the design elements and learning outcomes identified in the research, developers can create immersive experiences that support different learning theories and address various subject areas. This can lead to the development of innovative and engaging VR applications that have a lasting impact on computer science education. By understanding and acting upon these insights, educators, administrators, policymakers, and developers can work together to create a more engaging and effective learning experience for students in computer science, ultimately preparing them for success in a technology-driven world. The thesis emphasises the need for further research and development in the field of immersive technology and gamification in computer science education. By exploring new pedagogical approaches and refining best practice guidelines, educators and researchers can continue to expand the potential of these emerging technologies in enhancing the teaching and learning of computer science.

In conclusion, the analysis of the application of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education demonstrates their potential to transform the way the subject is taught and learned. By leveraging the unique capabilities of VR, AR, and MR, and integrating gamification and game-based learning elements, educators can create more engaging, interactive, and immersive learning experiences for students. These technologies are particularly relevant to computer science education, as they allow for the visualisation and interaction with complex programming concepts, algorithms, and systems, thus bridging the gap between theory and practice. However, to ensure the successful implementation of these technologies, it is crucial to view them as complementary tools to traditional teaching methods and to carefully plan and consider various factors, such as technology devices, best

practice conventions, and suitability for diverse learners and learning frameworks. As the field continues to evolve, further research and development are necessary to refine pedagogical approaches and best practice guidelines, ultimately unlocking the full potential of immersive technology and gamification in computer science education.

9.4 Future Works

Based on the finding of this thesis, several future research directions can be suggested to further advance the understanding and application of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education:

- Longitudinal studies: Conduct long-term studies to evaluate the effects of immersive technologies and gamification on student learning outcomes, motivation, and retention in computer science education over an extended period.
- Diverse populations: Investigate the impact of immersive technologies and gamification on different age groups, learning styles, and cultural backgrounds to determine the most effective approaches for diverse student populations.
- Comparison with other emerging technologies: Compare the effectiveness of immersive technologies and gamification with other cutting-edge educational technologies, such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and adaptive learning systems, to determine their relative benefits and drawbacks.
- Integration with traditional teaching methods: Examine the optimal balance between immersive technology-based learning and traditional teaching methods in computer science education, exploring the potential for blended learning approaches that combine the best of both worlds.
- Customisable learning experiences: Develop and evaluate personalised, adaptive immersive learning environments that respond to individual student needs, preferences, and learning styles, enabling more effective and targeted educational experiences.
- Assessing learning outcomes: Investigate reliable and valid assessment tools and techniques for evaluating student learning in immersive and gamified environments, including the use of analytics and data-driven approaches.
- Teacher training and support: Research the necessary professional development and support required for educators to effectively implement immersive technologies and gamification in their computer science classrooms.
- Ethical considerations: Examine the ethical implications of using immersive technologies and gamification in education, including issues related to privacy, data security, and potential negative effects on student well-being.

- Cost-effectiveness: Investigate the cost-effectiveness and scalability of immersive technologies and gamification in computer science education, considering factors such as hardware and software costs, infrastructure requirements, and ongoing maintenance and support.

By pursuing these future research directions, the field of computer science education can continue to refine and expand the application of immersive technologies and gamification, further enhancing the quality and effectiveness of teaching and learning in this critical domain.

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11 Appendix

The subsequent tables encapsulate the documents reviewed pertinent to each section of the Literature Review. Every table succinctly summarizes the findings of the individual papers, focusing on the research content and context, and delineates any benefit or risk factors spotlighted within the respective publication. These crucial elements have been meticulously culled from the author's research spreadsheets, which served as an organised mechanism to track relevant publications.

- Table 2: Provides a summary of the Literature Review for Immersive Technology in Education.
- Table 3: Offers an overview of the Literature Review for the Benefits of Immersive Technologies.
- Table 4: Illustrates a summary of the Literature Review for the Challenges of utilizing Immersive Technology.
- Table 5: Presents a summary of the Definitions found in the Literature Review for Gamification in Education.
- Table 6: Contains a summary of the Literature Review for Challenges faced in Computer Science Education.
- Table 7: Displays a summary of the Literature Review for Innovative Teaching Methods in Computer Science.

This collection of tables aims to simplify the understanding of the literature review's main points and to allow the reader to quickly reference the main findings and concepts derived from various publications.

Table 2 Summary of the Literature Review for Immersive Technology in Education

Summary of the Literature Review for Immersive Technology in Education					
Authors	Definition	Research Context	Research Content	Main Factors of Benefit	Main Factors of Risk
Connolly (2005)	Evaluates the impact of virtual reality technology on education, providing a review of the literature.	Impact of virtual reality technology on education	A review of the literature evaluating the impact of virtual reality technology in educational settings	N/A	N/A
Bell et al. (2008)	Explores the pedagogical purposes of using digital spaces, specifically virtual worlds, for learning.	Virtual worlds for learning	New ways of considering the pedagogical purposes of using digital spaces in education	Enhanced engagement	Under-researched
Cai (2013)	Focuses on the applications of 3D immersive and interactive learning across various educational domains.	3D immersive and interactive learning	Innovative efforts using 3D immersive technology across various	Applicable across a wide spectrum of education	N/A

			educational domains		
Fealy et al. (2019)	Investigates the integration of immersive virtual reality in nursing and midwifery tertiary education programs.	Nursing and midwifery tertiary education	Application and integration of immersive virtual reality in nursing and midwifery education programs	Realistic simulations, skill development, safe practice	N/A
Peña-Rios et al. (2020)	Examines the use of situated cognition theory for developing an immersive VR application in telecommunications engineering education.	Telecommunications engineering education	Using situated cognition theory to develop an immersive VR application for training students	Workplace preparation, enhanced learning experience	Limited participants
Kriukova et al. (2021)	Provides an understanding of the current and future applications of immersive technology in the education sector.	Education sector	Understanding the current and future applications of immersive technology in education	Enhanced learning experiences	High costs, need for further research
Wu et al. (2021)	Studies the use of RFID technology enhanced learning performance evaluation using mixed reality in higher education.	Higher education, RFID technology	Examining RFID-assisted learning using mixed reality technologies and evaluating learning performance	Improved retention, transfer of knowledge, problem-solving skills	N/A
Suri (2023)	Reviews the impact of virtual reality on education through a comprehensive literature review.	Education	Impact of virtual reality on education, based on a literature review	N/A	Cybersickness, cognitive overload
Gnanadurai et al. (2021)	Analyses the impact of immersive technologies on education for smart cities.	Education and the economy	Investigating the impact of immersive technologies on education and the economy	N/A	High costs.

Dreimane (2022)	Explores the applications of immersive technology in education, highlighting the need for empirical research and best practices.	Immersive technology in education	Exploring the applications of immersive technology in education	N/A	Need for empirical research, best practices
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Table 3 Summary of the Literature Review for Benefits Immersive Technologies

Summary of the Literature Review for Benefits Immersive Technologies					
Authors	Main Focus / Research Question	Research Context	Research Content	Main factors of benefit	Main factors of risk
Moro et al. (2017)	Assessing the effectiveness of VR and AR in health sciences and medical anatomy education	Health sciences and medical anatomy	VR/AR effectiveness in learning structural anatomy compared to tablet-based applications	Enhanced student learning, engagement, and performance	Technological limitations, cost
Alwedaie et al. (2018)	Investigating EEG-based analysis for learning through a virtual reality environment	Mobile game-based English learning	Self-regulated mobile game-based English learning in a virtual reality environment	Improved motivation, self-regulation, and language acquisition	Limited access to VR devices, addiction
Ruiz-Cantisani et al. (2020)	Exploring the use of virtual reality as a tool for active learning and student engagement in industrial engineering	Industrial engineering education	Virtual reality as a tool for active learning and student engagement	Increased student interest, better understanding of complex concepts	Cost, technical difficulties, limited content

Chen & Hsu (2020)	Examining self-regulated mobile game-based English learning in a virtual reality environment	Medical education	Incorporating medical ethics into clinical decision-making using virtual reality	Enhanced ethical reasoning and application to clinical practice	Initial setup cost, limited scenarios
Calvert & Abadia (2020)	Studying the impact of immersing university and high school students in educational linear narratives using virtual reality technology	Medical imaging and radiation therapy	Virtual reality computed tomography simulation within undergraduate programs	Improved understanding of CT scanning, increased student engagement	Cost, limited availability of VR simulations
Torda (2020)	Evaluating the use of virtual reality in incorporating medical ethics into clinical decision-making	Online collaborative learning	Analysing student engagement in online synchronous VR co-creation	Increased collaboration, engagement, and creativity	Technological limitations, connectivity issues
Gunn et al. (2020)	Investigating the use of virtual reality computed tomography simulation within a medical imaging and radiation therapy undergraduate programme	Remote learning	Design and implementation of a virtual classroom environment in VR	Enhanced involvement, attentiveness, and immersive learning	Technical difficulties, limited access to VR devices

Wang & Sun (2021)	Analysing behavioural patterns of online synchronous VR co-creation from the perspective of student engagement	Learning through VR environment	EEG-based analysis for learning through a virtual reality environment	Improved understanding of cognitive processes, better learning outcomes	Data privacy concerns, potential overstimulation
Karan et al. (2021)	Proposing and evaluating the design and implementation of a virtual classroom environment in VR for remote learning	University and high school students	Immersing students in educational linear narratives using virtual reality technology	Enhanced comprehension, retention, and engagement	Limited content, potential motion sickness
Brown et al. (2023)	Assessing a large-scale, multiplayer virtual reality deployment as a novel approach to distance education in human anatomy	Human anatomy education	Large-scale, multiplayer virtual reality deployment for distance education in human anatomy	Increased access to education, enhanced collaborative learning	Technological limitations, cost of VR devices

Table 4 Summary of the Literature Review for Challenges of Using Immersive Technology

Summary of the Literature Review for Challenges of Using Immersive Technology					
Authors	Main Concepts/Technologies Explored	Research Context	Research Content	Main Factors of Benefit	Main Factors of Risk
Dunleavy et al. (2009)	Augmented Reality (AR) Simulations	Teaching and learning	Immersive participatory AR simulations	Increased engagement, contextualized learning, collaborative problem-solving	Technological constraints, data accuracy, cognitive overload
Divaharan et al. (2011)	Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Tools	Pre-service teachers	Learning of ICT tools for knowledge creation	Immersion in ICT tools, continuous adaptation and improvement	Need for continuous adaptation and improvement
Han (2014)	Immersive Projection	Historical buildings analysis	Immersive projection and design communication	Combining immersive environments with traditional methods	Not explicitly mentioned in the summary
Messadi et al. (2017)	Immersive Learning	Sustainable building design	Immersive learning for sustainable building design and construction practices	Enhanced understanding of sustainable design and construction practices	Not explicitly mentioned in the summary
Hanson et al. (2019)	Three-dimensional Visualization	Nursing and midwifery education	Three-dimensional visualization in pharmacology	Improved knowledge and achievement in pharmacology	Not explicitly mentioned in the summary
Young et al. (2020)	Virtual Reality (VR)	Higher education	Virtual reality in the higher education classroom	Building knowledge and understanding through VR	Not explicitly mentioned in the summary

Table 5 Summary Of The Definitions In The Literature Review for Gamification in Education

Summary Of The Definitions In The Literature Review for Gamification in Education					
Authors	Definition	Research Context	Research Content	Main Factors of Benefit	Main Factors of Risk
Hallifax et al. (2019)	Gamification: the use of game elements, mechanics, and frameworks in non-game contexts, such as education, to enhance user engagement, motivation, and participation.	Education	Adaptive gamification	Tailoring game elements to learners, increasing motivation and engagement	Risk of over-reliance on extrinsic rewards, potential for disengagement if game elements are not well-designed
Ivanova et al. (2019)	Gamification: the use of game elements and mechanics in non-game contexts, such as education, to enhance learning outcomes and engagement.	Software engineering education	Gamification in teaching methods and concepts	Engagement, promoting higher-order skills, simulations	None mentioned
Oforu-Ampong et al. (2019)	Gamification: the use of game elements, mechanics, and strategies to enhance engagement and motivation in learning.	Developing country education	Gamification acceptance	Perception and acceptance of gamification in learning	None mentioned
Kepceoglu (2019)	Gamification: the use of game elements and mechanics in educational contexts to enhance motivation and engagement in learning.	Education	Gamification in teaching methods	Perception and attitudes towards educational gamification	None mentioned
Gentry et al. (2019)	Serious gaming/gamification: the use of games, simulations, and game elements in educational contexts, particularly health professions education, to enhance learning outcomes and engagement.	Health professions education	Serious gaming/gamification effectiveness	Improving patient outcomes, knowledge, skills, attitudes, and satisfaction; economic outcomes of education	Risk of reinforcing unhealthy gaming habits
Bai et al. (2020)	Gamification: the use of game elements and mechanics in educational contexts to enhance learning outcomes and engagement.	Education	Gamification in student learning	Improved learning outcomes, motivation, and satisfaction	None mentioned

Aini et al. (2020)	Gamification: the use of game elements, mechanics, and frameworks in educational contexts, particularly management education, to enhance engagement, motivation, and metacognitive skills.	Management education	Blockchain technology and gamification	Engaging and interactive learning experience, motivation, and enhancing metacognitive skills	None mentioned
Andreu (2020)	Gamification: the use of game elements and mechanics in educational contexts to enhance motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes.	University education	Gamification and motivation	Influence of gamification on motivation and learning outcomes	None mentioned
Kalogiannakis et al. (2021)	Gamification: the use of game elements and mechanics in science education to enhance motivation, engagement, and scientific thinking.	Science education	Gamification in science education	Enhancing motivation, engagement, and scientific thinking	None mentioned
Saleem et al. (2021)	Gamification: the use of game elements and mechanics in online education to enhance learning outcomes, motivation, and engagement.	E-learning	Gamification in online education	Improved learning outcomes, motivation, and satisfaction	None mentioned

Table 6 Summary of the Literature Review for Challenges Faced in Computer Science Education

Summary of the Literature Review for Challenges Faced in Computer Science Education					
Authors	Definition	Research Context	Research Content	Main Factors of Benefit	Main Factors of Risk
Sentance et al. (2013)	Challenges faced in integrating CS into secondary schools and supporting teacher development	UK Secondary Schools	Integration of CS and teacher professional development	Empowering teachers, professional development	Not specified
Escherle et al. (2016)	The adaptation of the Scalable Game Design CS Ed Week activity for a Mexican pilot study	Mexico	Scalable Game Design CS Ed Week activity and feasibility pilot study	Engaging students, adaptability to different contexts	Not specified
Malik et al. (2018)	Factors that can improve the performance and structure of the education system	Saudi Arabia	Performance and structure of the education system	Improved education system, IT integration	Not specified
Epifânio et al. (2019)	Teaching Requirements Engineering in undergraduate CS courses in Brazil	Brazil	Requirements Engineering in undergraduate CS courses	Better understanding of Requirements Engineering	Not specified
Harangus et al. (2020)	The promotion of computational thinking in secondary and higher education	Secondary and Higher Ed	Computational Thinking	Promoting computational thinking	Not specified
Souza et al. (2021)	The didactic formation of teachers/professors in IT and CS in Tocantins, Brazil	Tocantins, Brazil	Didactic formation of IT and CS teachers/professors	Improved teacher education	Not specified
Haris et al. (2021)	Challenges faced in higher education during the Covid-19 lockdown in Qatar	Qatar	Challenges in Higher Education during Covid-19 lockdown	Not specified	Lack of interaction, stress, connectivity issues
Riese et al. (2021)	Challenges faced by CS teaching assistants in Europe	Europe	Challenges faced by CS Teaching Assistants	Not specified	Not specified
Radenski (2006)	Making CS1 course offerings more attractive using Python, online resources, and self-guided labs	Not specified	CS1 course offerings using Python, online resources, and self-guided labs	Increased student engagement, ease of learning	Not specified
Falkner et al. (2009)	Integrating cooperative learning techniques and authentic problem-solving in CS education	Not specified	Integrating cooperative learning techniques and authentic problem solving in CS	Increased student engagement, problem-solving skills	Not specified

Henderson (2009)	The confusion and challenges around the term "computer science"	Not specified	Challenges and confusion around the term "computer science"	Not specified	Confusion and decreased interest in CS
Basawapatna et al. (2010)	Using Scalable Game Design to teach fundamental and complex CS concepts	Various levels	Scalable Game Design to teach CS concepts	Engaging students, adaptability across different levels	Not specified
Apiola et al. (2012)	Providing CS students with a creativity-supporting learning environment	Not specified	Practically oriented learning environment to support student creativity	Enhanced creativity, practical skills	Not specified
Fraser (2014)	The nature of academic dishonesty in CS coursework	Not specified	Academic dishonesty in CS coursework	Not specified	Collaboration, collusion, plagiarism
Rodriguez-Cerezo et al. (2014)	The development of educational serious games for computer language implementation courses	Tertiary Education	Educational serious games for computer language implementation courses	Improved comprehension, engagement	Not specified
Wang et al. (2016)	Exploring perceptions, access, and barriers to K-12 CS education in the United States	United States	Perceptions, access, and barriers to K-12 CS education	Not specified	Limited access, barriers to CS education

Table 7 Summary of the Literature Review for innovative teaching methods in CS

Summary of the Literature Review for innovative teaching methods in CS					
Authors	Definition				
Hedley et. al., 2002	Augmented reality for geographic visualization	Research Context	Research Content	Main factors of benefit	Main factors of risk
Talaba et. al., 2010	Virtual and augmented reality technologies in product design	Geographic data visualization	Use of augmented reality for collaborative geographic data visualization	Better spatial understanding, increased engagement, more effective collaboration	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Bashabsheh et. al., 2019	Virtual reality technology in architectural pedagogy for building constructions	Product design	Virtual and augmented reality technologies in product design	Improved design process, more efficient communication, better product visualization	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Huang et. al., 2019	Augmented and virtual reality mobile applications for education	Architectural pedagogy	Application of virtual reality technology in architectural pedagogy for building constructions	Improved spatial understanding, increased engagement, more effective collaboration	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Filter et. al., 2020	Virtual reality nature experiences involving wolves	Science education	Comparison of augmented and virtual reality technologies in education	Better science knowledge retention, increased engagement, more effective learning	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Hilty et. al., 2020	Telepresence, virtual reality, and augmented reality applied to clinical care	Nature experiences	Virtual reality nature experiences involving wolves	Increased presence, positive emotions, improved attitudes	Technological challenges, potential for simulation sickness
Nersesian et. al., 2020	Binary counting using virtual reality	Clinical care	Review of telepresence, virtual reality, and augmented reality in clinical care	Increased access to care, improved patient outcomes, better training opportunities	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Bourguet et. al., 2020	Virtual and augmented reality for teaching materials science	Binary counting	Use of virtual reality for teaching binary counting	Improved understanding of binary counting, increased engagement, more effective learning	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Zhang et. al., 2020	Hotspots and trends of virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality in education field	Materials science	Use of virtual and augmented reality for teaching materials science	Improved understanding of materials science concepts, increased engagement, more effective learning	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction

Oleksiuk et. al., 2020	Augmented reality for teaching school computer science	Education field	Hotspots and trends of virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality in education	Identification of future research directions, potential for innovation	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Turhan et. al., 2022	Virtual and augmented reality in systems biology	Computer science education	Use of augmented reality for teaching school computer science	Improved understanding of computer science concepts, increased engagement, more effective learning	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Parmar et. al., 2022	Immersion and self-avatars in virtual reality for learning programming and computational thinking	Systems biology	Use of virtual and augmented reality in systems biology	Improved understanding of complex biological systems, more effective research, potential for innovation	Technological challenges, cost, potential for distraction
Xie et. al., 2022	Computer self-efficacy, perceived immersion, and intention to use virtual reality training systems	Computer programming education	Comparison of immersion and self-avatars in virtual reality for learning computer programming	Improved learning outcomes, increased engagement, more effective learning	Technological challenges, potential for simulation sickness
Kuang et. al., 2022	Application of virtual reality technology to university teaching	VR training systems	Factors influencing behavioural intention when using VR training systems	Improved learning outcomes, increased engagement, more effective learning	Technological challenges, potential for distraction
Jong, 2022	Spherical video-based immersive virtual reality in support of pre-lecture individual learning in pre-service teacher education	Pre-service teacher education	Use of spherical video-based immersive virtual reality in pre-lecture individual learning	Increased motivation, improved learning outcomes, more effective teaching	Technological challenges, potential for distraction
Veer et. al., 2022	Mixed reality for knowledge retention in interdisciplinary education	Interdisciplinary education	Use of mixed reality for teaching physiology, anatomy, pathology, and pharmacology	Improved understanding of complex medical concepts, increased engagement, more effective learning	Technological challenges, potential for distraction
He et. al., 2022	Virtual reality technology in cognitive rehabilitation application	Cognitive rehabilitation	Use of virtual reality technology in cognitive rehabilitation application	Improved cognitive function, increased motivation	

Agbo et. al., 2022	Virtual reality game-based application to support computational thinking	Virtual reality game-based application to support CT knowledge	Design and implementation of iThinkSmart	Engaging and motivating way of learning CT; increased knowledge	Possible negative effects of gaming addiction or overuse
Asadzadeh et. al., 2022	Digital games and virtual reality applications in child abuse	Digital games and VR applications in child abuse	Conceptual framework for managing child abuse with VR and digital games	Improved management of child abuse; innovative and engaging approach	Possible desensitization to violence or trauma exposure in vulnerable populations
Li et. al., 2022	Interior environment design for entrepreneurship education under virtual reality and artificial intelligence-based learning environment	Interior environment design for entrepreneurship education	Method using distributed VR technology for teaching entrepreneurship	Realistic learning experience; improved learning outcomes	Possible negative effects of VR sickness or discomfort; technical issues with VR technology

